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PROPOSALS FOR IMPLEMENTING A METHODOLOGY OF COMBINATORIAL OPTIMIZATION OF AUTOMATED PROCESS CONTROL SYSTEMS BASED ON QUANTUM COMPUTING DEVICES AND THEIR EMULATION

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***Abstract.** The problem of implementing intelligent control methods for technological processes in enterprises is considered, including the application of quantum and neural network technologies. Proposals are presented for modifying standard architectures of automated process control systems (APCS) in light of current trends in industrial digitalization (Industry 4.0). Specific recommendations are provided for the selection of tools and the organization of computational processes in hybrid environments (cloud, edge computing), and principles for the development of mathematical models enabling effective use of quantum and neural network methods are discussed. The main conclusion is the necessity of phased implementation of new technologies in existing production systems to achieve maximum benefit and minimize risks.*

***Keywords:** neural network technologies; quantum computing; Industry 4.0 architecture; optimal control; Production processes; Intelligent control methods; mathematical models; digital enterprise.*

Introduction

The development and implementation of intelligent methods for managing technological processes have become a priority for many industrial sectors. The transition to modern technologies, such as quantum and neural network optimizers, can significantly enhance the productivity and cost-efficiency of production systems. This paper examines practical steps for implementing these technologies in industrial automated process control systems (APCS) [1].

Traditionally, the architecture of APCS is based on the international standard ISA-95, which defines multiple management levels: from lower levels (PLCs, RTUs) to upper levels (SCADA, MES, ERP). However, the full integration of modern technologies requires substantial modifications to this classical structure.

This material is dedicated to addressing the following issues:

- How can quantum and neural network technologies be integrated into the existing structure of APCS?
- What requirements are imposed on the modernized information systems?
- How to correctly select the appropriate tool for each specific control task?

Materials and Methods

A key point is the correct selection of the location for placing new functionality within the traditional structure of APCS. The proposed solution is as follows:

1. **Cloud processing:** most complex analysis and optimization tasks are performed in a cloud environment that provides powerful GPU, TPU, and quantum services (e.g., IBM Quantum Experience, Amazon Braket, Google TensorFlow Quantum). This approach is effective for large-scale forecasting and global optimization tasks but increases system latency.

2. **Edge processing:** fast local computations (predictive models, emergency control commands) are performed directly on-site with minimal response time, using hardware systems (microcontrollers, GPU cards, FPGA processors). This strategy is suitable for situations requiring immediate responses to real-time events.

The most rational option is a combined architecture that integrates the advantages of both approaches. For example, the main computationally intensive tasks (historical data analysis, development of long-term control strategies, neural network training) are hosted in the cloud, while operational control is performed on edge devices (Edge Computing).

A crucial stage is the transformation of control tasks into corresponding mathematical formats suitable for neural network or quantum solutions. Thus, resource planning and optimization tasks are conveniently represented in the form of quadratic unconstrained binary optimization (QUBO) problems, which are ideally suited for quantum computers and certain types of neural network optimizers.

Results

The implementation of the proposed methodology enables a significant transformation of traditional approaches to managing production processes and opens up opportunities for the introduction of innovative solutions at the level of industrial automation. Let us examine in greater detail the key aspects of the practical implementation of this concept.

Modernization of Information Infrastructure.

The creation of a unified digital space based on open standards (open data) ensures the integration of various types of sensors and measurement equipment into a unified system for data collection and processing. Such infrastructure involves the extensive use of IoT technologies and the network architecture of the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), enabling efficient transmission of large volumes of information in real time.

For example, the use of specialized data transmission protocols (MQTT, CoAP) guarantees the reliability of communication channels and the timely delivery of critically important messages. The application of the MQTT-SN standard enables compatibility of low-latency wireless networks with general-purpose protocols.

Application of Quantum Computers.

The integration of quantum computing is particularly beneficial for multi-criteria optimization tasks and modeling of complex technological processes. Examples of successful applications of quantum simulators demonstrate the superiority of these tools over classical computers in identifying the optimal strategy for enterprise resource management.

In particular, the application of QUBO (Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimization) models has proven to be an effective approach for representing classical linear programming problems and obtaining optimal solutions via the quantum approximation method.

In addition to the use of physical quantum machines (IBM Q System One, D-Wave), efficient quantum-inspired emulators such as Qiskit Aer are also being developed, enabling preliminary testing and calibration of quantum algorithms prior to deployment on actual devices.

Intelligent Forecasting and Optimization.

The use of well-established neural network architectures, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs), recurrent neural networks (RNNs), and graph neural networks (GNNs), facilitates solving problems related to forecasting the technical condition of units and optimizing energy consumption in production.

Preliminary adaptation and training of the neural network on large datasets of historical data enhances the accuracy of predicting equipment malfunctions and failures, enabling advanced planning of preventive maintenance and reducing costs.

Graph neural networks have proven effective for predicting the states and behaviors of complex systems consisting of numerous interconnected components, thereby providing high-quality diagnostics and facilitating prompt management decision-making.

Organization of the Management Architecture.

The new control structure is a three-level architecture comprising a lower sensory layer, a middle operational level, and an upper analytical block that primarily operates within a cloud environment. The lower level contains sensors and actuators that ensure the collection of primary data and the execution of control commands. The middle level includes local controllers and processing devices capable of promptly responding to changes in the environment and issuing instructions to the lower level. The upper level is responsible for solving strategic tasks and long-term process optimization through the processing of large volumes of data in the cloud.

This approach enables the simultaneous use of powerful cloud resources for highly complex calculations and minimal latency at the control and regulation levels, thanks to decentralized processing at the network edge (edge computing).

Thus, the proposed approach demonstrates potential for significantly improving the quality of technological process control through the integration of modern information technologies and high-performance computing platforms.

Discussion

The proposed methodology for combining traditional control methods with the latest quantum and neural network computing technologies holds significant potential for enhancing existing production management systems. Nevertheless, there are several aspects that warrant additional attention and further study.

Issues of Coherence and Reliability in Quantum Algorithms.

One of the primary obstacles to the widespread adoption of quantum computing is the low stability of qubits and the stringent environmental requirements. Errors caused by noise and decoherence can negatively impact the quality of the obtained solutions. This problem is further compounded by the need to perform multiple repetitions of the same calculation to achieve a stable result.

Although existing error correction tools are continually improving, additional efforts are necessary to adapt them to the specific requirements of industrial applications. One direction for further work may be the development of specialized error correction protocols that consider the specifics of particular industrial application scenarios.

Selection of the Appropriate Mathematical Formulation of the Problem.

Another important issue is the proper formulation of the problem to effectively leverage the capabilities of quantum and neural network methods. Although the QUBO approach is widely used to represent optimization problems, not all types of problems are easily convertible into this format. Therefore, further development of universal methods for transforming various classes of problems into a form suitable for quantum and neural network optimizers [2] is required.

The development of intermediate abstraction layers automating the translation of real engineering problems into a form convenient for computer processing is possible.

Challenges of Scalable Implementation and Practical Efficiency Assessment.

Despite successful pilot projects, many large corporations still refrain from large-scale deployment of quantum-neural network technologies due to uncertainty regarding economic benefits and high initial costs. A thorough calculation of ROI (Return on Investment) and the demonstration of convincing examples of successful integration into practical applications are necessary.

Particular attention should be paid to monitoring the improvements achieved to justify investments in such solutions. It is advisable to organize a series of tests and experiments on small production sites, followed by a gradual scaling of the implemented solutions.

It is also important to consider regional and national differences in IT system infrastructure and the personnel's readiness to adopt new technologies. The development of training courses and training programs will facilitate faster adaptation to new conditions and achieve the desired economic effect.

Therefore, the present time represents a favorable period for the active adoption of quantum and neural network technologies in the industrial sector. It is recommended to conduct a series of pilot tests within individual enterprise units to identify the optimal methods for integrating these approaches into existing production systems [3].

Conclusion

In summary, it is necessary to emphasize a comprehensive approach to the development and implementation of quantum and neural network methods in APCS. The developed concept envisages the use of both cloud resources for computationally intensive tasks and local Edge Computing systems for rapid response to failures and incidents. The primary outcome should be a unified digital environment that integrates all levels of production and management into a single efficient mechanism.

Given the complexity of integrating new technologies, future research should concentrate on the following aspects:

- Design of adequate mathematical models,
- Adaptation of control system architectures,
- Organization of reliable information exchange among all participants of the system.

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STUDY OF STRUCTURAL PHASE TRANSITIONS IN OIL DURING THE DEVELOPMENT OF OIL FIELDS

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Abstract. *This article presents the results of studies on the processes of structural transformations in reservoir and degassed oil from deposits in development. The subject of study consists of oil deposits from Carboniferous strata of the Paleozoic system within the Volga-Ural oil and gas province, where the oil experiences a structural phase transition during oil field development, induced by the natural preferential extraction of light fractions. A phase transition in oil can occur due to changes in the oil composition and thermobaric conditions during field development. Changes in the phase state of the high-molecular-weight components of oil (asphaltenes, resins, and paraffins) result in a phase transition in the oil, complicating the field development process. The difficulty in predicting this phase transition in oil is caused by the presence of diverse organic compounds comprising the oil and their mutual interactions. The efficiency of oil field development depends on accounting for the structural and mechanical properties of oil arising from the diversity and interaction of components within the oil system.*

Keywords: *oil viscosity, structural phase transition, thermobaric parameters of the reservoir.*

The development of oil reservoirs is accompanied by the preferential extraction of light fractions. In the reservoir, at late stages of development, the heavy fraction of hydrocarbons remains. Oil exhibits viscosity anomalies caused by the formation of structures from high-molecular components in the liquid due to changes in the phase state of the dispersed oil component [1]. A phase transition, or phase transformation, is defined as the transition of a substance from one thermodynamic phase to another under changing external conditions, which may include variations in temperature, pressure, or the concentration of one or more components in the system under consideration [2]. Phase transitions characterized by changes in structural and mechanical properties due to alterations in the phase state of the

high-molecular components of oil are typical for oil deposits of the Carboniferous strata of the Paleozoic system in the Volga-Ural oil and gas province.

The oil from the fields is characterized by varying compositions depending on the location of the deposits within the sedimentary cover and the thermobaric conditions of occurrence. The sedimentary cover of the Volga-Ural oil and gas province consists of Devonian, Carboniferous, and Permian deposits. Oil deposits in Devonian sediments are characterized by low concentrations of high-molecular-weight compounds and high thermobaric conditions. Permian oils are characterized by high concentrations of resins and asphaltenes; the deposits are located near the earth's surface and therefore exhibit low thermobaric parameters. The oil in these deposits is highly viscous. Development of these deposits without the application of thermal methods is impossible. Within the geological interval between the Devonian and Permian strata, among others, there are deposits with a high concentration of high-molecular-weight compounds in the oil; the oil is highly viscous. The development of these deposits disrupts the thermobaric balance, which can lead to transformations in the oil resulting in a loss of recoverable reserves. It is well known that oil viscosity depends on temperature and the concentration of the high-molecular component [3]. Based on experimental studies, a comparison was made of oil viscosity under reservoir conditions and the quantitative composition of high-molecular components in the Carboniferous and Permian systems, which demonstrated that the average oil viscosity of the Permian system significantly exceeds that of deposits associated with the Carboniferous system at approximately equal total concentrations of asphaltenes, resins, and paraffins. This fact led to the hypothesis of a geological environment whose temperature conditions affect qualitative changes in the structural and mechanical properties of oil [4]. The reservoirs considered are those in which the oil contains more than 20% by mass of high-molecular components.

Phase transitions associated with changes in the structure of high-molecular hydrocarbons occur due to changes in ambient temperature and only minor effects of pressure [5, 6]. Temperature is a factor that significantly influences the physico-chemical properties of oil. When optimizing various oil extraction processes, such as selecting and implementing treatments on productive formations, it is necessary to know the dependence of oil rheological parameters on temperature. In determining the dependence of rheological properties on temperature for oil samples from the Volga-Ural oil and gas-bearing province, the authors [7, 8] confirmed that as the oil temperature decreases, there is a transition from Newtonian to non-Newtonian behavior. Experiments were conducted using a rotational viscometer, which enabled the determination of steady-state shear stress–shear rate relationships with a high degree of accuracy, allowed for thermostating, and automated the research process. Based on the measurements, flow curves were constructed

with high accuracy and approximated using the binomial rheological equation. It was established that viscosity at low shear rates and plastic viscosity, characterizing non-Newtonian systems, exhibit an exponential dependence on temperature [9, 10]. The phase transition temperature in the oil of the Tournaisian horizon of the Kalmaurskoye field was determined graphically. Both methods determined that for the highly viscous oil of the Tournaisian section of the Kalmayur field, the structural phase transition temperature is in the range of 26.5-27.6 °C. At the same time, the oil sample is enriched with asphaltenes, with a content of 15-16%. The elevated phase transition temperature of this oil is precisely due to the high concentration of asphaltenes [9]. In fact, the structural phase transition for this oil has already occurred, and it is necessary to consider the structural phase transition temperature when designing methods to influence reservoir oil with a high content of asphaltene-resin substances.

Fig. 1. Viscosity distribution versus temperature during heating and cooling of the sample at shear rates of 14 and 11 s⁻¹.

Some researchers [11-13] report reversible phase transitions and the possibility of regulating them in the oil system by changing the concentration of asphaltenes, temperature, and the solvent capacity of the dispersion medium. The establishment of temperature hysteresis of the structural phase transition was obtained through laboratory experiments during heating (red line) and cooling (blue line) of the sample [14]. Figure 1 illustrates the hysteresis by presenting viscosity versus temperature curves of the oil during heating (red line) and cooling (blue line) at a shear rate of 14.11 s⁻¹. The cooling line is situated below the

heating line. This correspondence is explained by the difference in melting and crystallization temperatures of the high-molecular components of oil. Cooled oil, in which phase transformations of high-molecular structures have occurred, requires more energy to restore mobility. A correlation has been established between the temperature difference value of the structural phase transition, caused by the hysteresis process, and the content of high-molecular components: a larger temperature difference corresponds to a higher concentration of the high-molecular component. This can be explained by the complex structure of organic molecules, the presence of heteroatoms, and the ability to form strong bonds between high-molecular components themselves, as well as subsequent structural transformations of these compounds [14].

During the study, a non-isothermal hydrodynamic model was developed, which allowed for the consideration of temperature changes in the near-wellbore zone resulting from the injection of a cold agent. A three-dimensional geological model constructed using a geological modeling software package enabled the estimation of oil losses accounting for the hysteresis of relative phase permeabilities at various temperatures of the injected water into the reservoir and considering viscosity values dependent on temperature [15].

The pilot site for investigating the processes of structural phase transitions was selected by ranking oil reservoirs based on a criterion characterizing the tendency of the oil in these reservoirs to undergo structural phase transitions. The geological and technical measures conducted have enabled the identification of conditions for the occurrence of structural phase transitions: high oil viscosity and density, development under reservoir energy depletion mode, and the influence of a displacing agent with a temperature below the reservoir temperature [16].

Fluid analysis constitutes an essential part of the process used to describe the characteristics of the productive reservoir and to make decisions regarding its operational parameters. The initial data for design must be of high quality; errors in their determination can lead to serious adverse consequences. During extraction, a reduction in thermobaric conditions occurs, which can cause changes in the physical state of fluids, thereby complicating the extraction process. The cause of such complications may be a structural phase transition.

Based on the conducted studies of phase transition processes, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- changes in oil properties during development should be reflected in the comprehensive research and considered when developing conditions and technologies that enable adaptation to these changes;

- One of the parameters that will help to effectively plan geological and technical operations (GTO) is the temperature of the structural phase transition. This parameter allows for selecting the optimal conditions for conducting GTO, using

fluids with temperatures not lower than the reservoir temperature, especially during the cold season.

— The temperature of the structural phase transition is a parameter dependent on the oil composition and its changes during the development process. The rate of change of the structural phase transition temperature depends on the initial characteristics of the reservoir oil and the selected reservoir exploitation regime.

— Accounting for the parameter ‘temperature of the structural phase transition’ during the design and implementation of development will prevent the phase transition in oil under reservoir conditions.

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DC-DC CONVERTER TOPOLOGIES FOR CHARGING ELECTRIC VEHICLE TRACTION BATTERIES

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Abstract: *The article presents a comparative analysis of the DC converter topologies used in the charging systems of electric vehicle traction batteries. Buck, Boost, Flyback, and LLC converters are examined in terms of their operation principle, energy efficiency, electromagnetic interference levels, and application areas. The advantages and disadvantages of each topology are evaluated based on their power level and operating conditions. It is shown that resonant LLC converters offer the most practical solution for electric vehicle traction battery charging systems, as they provide high efficiency and reduced switching losses. The results obtained can be used in the design of electric vehicle chargers.*

Keywords: *electric vehicle charger, converter topologies, rectifiers, charging station.*

Introduction. Direct current to direct current converters (DC/DC converters) are used in electronic devices, telecommunications equipment, automated control systems (ACS), and transport systems. DC/DC converters are classified according to their purpose (step-down, step-up, inverting), the presence of galvanic isolation (isolated, non-isolated), the direction of power flow (unidirectional, bidirectional), the power source (powered by a current source, powered by a voltage source), and the type of switching (hard or soft switching). A common feature of all DC/DC converters is the presence of an LC filter in their circuit, a node designed to smooth

the shape of the current and voltage curves and ensure correct load operation. As a rule, hybrid electromagnetic elements are used as LC filters.

The task of justifying the choice of traction batteries for electric vehicles based on an analysis of the topologies of DC-DC converters for charging traction batteries for electric vehicles is relevant.

Figure 1 — Models of step-up DC-DC converters

Materials and methods of research. To solve the tasks set, an analysis of modern domestic and foreign scientific and technical sources was carried out, as well as a comparative analysis of DC/DC converter topologies according to the following criteria:

- Principle of operation;
- Energy efficiency;

- Presence of galvanic isolation;
- Electromagnetic interference (EMI) level;
- Power and scope of application;
- Circuit implementation complexity.

Research. Various DC-DC converter topologies are used to charge electric vehicle traction batteries: Buck (step-down), Boost (step-up), Flyback (step-down with transformer) and LLC (resonant). Below, we will conduct a comparative analysis of these topologies, taking into account their operating principles, advantages and disadvantages [4, p. 54].

A boost DC-DC converter is an electronic device that converts a constant input voltage into a higher constant output voltage. The operation of a DC-DC boost converter is based on the cyclic accumulation of energy in the inductance and its transfer to the load with an increased voltage. The main stages of operation are: accumulation of energy in the inductance coil; release of energy; cyclic repetition.

Some models of step-up DC-DC converters are shown in Fig. 1.

A buck converter (also known as a step-down converter) is a type of switching voltage (or current) converter with galvanic isolation between the primary and secondary circuits. The purpose is to provide a stable, lower output voltage from a higher input voltage in order to save energy [1, p. 96].

There are two main stages of operation in the circuit (Fig. 1).

Figure 2 — Operating Stages of the Buck Converter

A flyback converter is a type of pulse voltage (or current) converter with galvanic isolation between the primary and secondary circuits [3, p. 96].

The main element of such a converter is a multi-winding storage choke, which is sometimes called a transformer, although the processes occurring here and in a transformer have significant differences.

The principle of operation involves two main stages (see Figure 3)

Figure 3 — Operating principle of the Flyback converter

Figure 4 — Schematic diagram of the resonant LLC converter

An LLC resonator is a resonant circuit consisting of two inductors and one capacitor located in front of the power transformer. The basis of the resonator is a capacitor-inductor pair (LR, CR). Another coil — the magnetising inductance of the power transformer (LM) — is added to the circuit, allowing the voltage to be regulated under light load [2, p. 85].

The schematic diagram of the LLC resonator is shown in Fig. 4.

Some features of the LLC resonator:

- Provides a sinusoidal current waveform on the transformer instead of a rectangular one.

- The circuit’s operating mode becomes smoother, parasitic harmonics are eliminated, and heat losses are reduced.

- Due to the action of self-induction in the resonator circuit, the sink-source current on the field-effect transistors lags behind the voltage, which provides ZVS switching, i.e., switching at zero voltage [5, p. 66].

Discussion of the results obtained. Next, we will consider the results of a comparative analysis of DC-DC converter topologies for charging electric vehicle traction batteries.

Table 1— Results of a comparative analysis of DC-DC converter topologies for charging electric vehicle traction batteries

Converter type	Principle of operation	Efficiency	Galvanic isolation	Advantages	Disadvantages	Typical power	Cost, RUB
Boost (elevating)	Cyclical accumulation of energy in inductance and its transfer to the load with increased voltage.	85-95%	No	High efficiency; converts low input voltage into higher power with minimal energy loss; compact and lightweight, uses fewer components; flexible design can operate over a wide range of input voltages and load conditions.	The pulse current increases significantly, leading to increased losses, which reduces the efficiency of the converter.	Up to 1kW	1300

Convert type	Principle of operation	Efficiency	Galvanic isolation	Advantages	Disadvantages	Typical power	Cost, RUB
Buck (reverse)	Periodic connection and disconnection of the	90-95%	No	High efficiency (usually above 90%); the ability to pre-	Requires that the input voltage always be	Up to 2kW	3650
	load via a key element, which allows maintaining a stable output voltage below the input voltage.			cisely control the output voltage by adjusting the duty cycle of the PWM signal.	higher than the output voltage, otherwise the converter will not function correctly.		
Flyback (reverse-running with transformer)	Conversion of input voltage to output voltage by accumulating and storing energy in the transformer core during the power switch on time, and transferring it to the secondary circuit during its off time (on the return stroke).	70-85%	Yes	Ease of implementation, small number of components; ability to regulate output voltage within a wide range.	Power is limited by the energy stored in the choke (in practice, no more than 200 W); increased level of electromagnetic interference generated both in the power supply network and in the load; large dimensions for the same power.	Up to 200W	1300
LLC (resonant)	The converter operates in the inductive reaction range of the resonant circuit, with the voltage leading the current, which reduces switching losses in semiconductor switches.	95-98%	Yes	Wide-range output voltage; zero voltage switching (ZVS) capability.	Achieving a wide output voltage range requires special attention during design. To do this, several stages of a single converter or series-connected converters are usually used.	1-10kW	650

Conclusion. A comparative analysis of DC/DC converter topologies has shown that non-isolated Buck and Boost converters are mainly suitable for auxiliary circuits and low-power applications. Flyback converters are limited in power and are characterized by increased electromagnetic interference, which reduces their applicability in traction battery charging systems.

The most promising topology for electric vehicle chargers is the LLC resonant DC/DC converter, which provides high efficiency, reduced switching losses, and improved weight and size characteristics. The results obtained can be used in the development and optimization of electric transport chargers.

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ANALYSIS OF THE SIGNIFICANCE OF USING DATA MINING TOOLS

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Abstract: *The prevalence of data extraction tools among developers at both the global and Russian levels is assessed.*

Keywords: *data extraction; GitHub; labor market; frameworks; vacancy analysis.*

Data extraction is a critically important component of modern software development, encompassing a wide range of tasks—from web scraping and natural language processing to code analysis and automation. [1] Understanding the scale of the use of data extraction tools among developers both globally and within the Russian context enables the assessment of their significance and impact on the industry. This study aims to quantitatively evaluate the proportion of programmers actively employing data extraction by utilizing statistics on framework usage from GitHub and analyzing job vacancies on HeadHunter (hh.ru).

To assess the global popularity of data extraction tools, several key libraries and frameworks widely employed in the developer community were selected [2]. Their popularity can be assessed by the number of uses on GitHub (i.e., repositories), which serves as an indicator of community interest and engagement. Below is a diagram showing the tool name and the number of uses.

The total number of uses on GitHub for the selected data mining tools amounts to 2,795,100. Assuming that each use corresponds to a unique developer who has shown interest in the tool (which is a simplification, but provides an idea of the scale), it is possible to calculate that the share of developers worldwide using or

interested in data mining tools is. According to SlashData, there are 47,000,000 developers worldwide [3].

$$(2\,795\,100 / 47\,000\,000) * 100\% = 5,95\%$$

Fig. 1. Popularity of data mining tools on GitHub

The total number of uses on GitHub for the selected data mining tools amounts to 2,795,100. Assuming that each use corresponds to a unique developer who has shown interest in the tool (which is a simplification, but provides an idea of the scale), it is possible to calculate that the share of developers worldwide using or interested in data mining tools is. According to SlashData, there are 47,000,000 developers worldwide [3].

$$(2\,795\,100 / 47\,000\,000) * 100\% = 5,95\%$$

According to GitHub's annual report [4], the proportion of registered Russian developers on this platform was 7.3%. Thus, the potential proportion of developers who have used frameworks is:

$$2\,795\,100 * 7,3\% = 204\,042$$

Considering that the number of developers in Russia, according to the Russian government, is 1,100,000 [5], the proportion of developers in Russia who use or are interested in parsing tools is

$$(204\,042 / 1\,100\,000) * 100\% = 18,55\%$$

A visual diagram illustrating the difference is presented below:

Fig. 2. The proportion of developers using data extraction tools.

To deepen the analysis of the Russian labor market, data from the hh.ru platform were utilized. Two search queries were conducted: one with the keyword “парсинг” to identify vacancies requiring data extraction skills, and another with the keyword “программист” to determine the total number of developer vacancies. This enabled the evaluation of the proportion of vacancies related to data extraction in the Russian market.

A job search on hh.ru using the keyword “parsing” in Russia identified 278 vacancies. The total number of IT vacancies in Russia at the time of the study was 32,827. This makes it possible to calculate the proportion of vacancies requiring data extraction skills:

$$(278 / 32827) * 100\% = 0,85\%$$

Overall, according to GitHub data, approximately 6% of all developers worldwide use libraries for data extraction to some extent. This suggests that data extraction is a niche yet stable competence, sought after in automation, data analysis, testing, and NLP tasks. Extrapolating GitHub data to the Russian context, approximately one in five ($\approx 18.5\%$) Russian developers show interest or have experience working with data extraction tools. This is above the global average level, which can be explained by the active application of data mining in analytics, e-commerce, and automation in the Russian market. The proportion of vacancies mentioning ‘parsing’

is only 0.85% of all IT vacancies on hh.ru. This suggests that the skill is primarily in demand as a supplementary competency rather than as a core one. Employers expect it as part of other roles — analysts, backend developers, and data specialists.

Share of vacancies requiring data extraction skills on hh.ru

Fig. 3. Proportion of vacancies requiring knowledge of data extraction on hh.ru

Although only about 1% of vacancies directly require data mining skills, up to 18% of developers have experience with or interest in them.

This indicates a high prevalence of the tool among specialists, but limited direct demand from employers.

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CORPORATE SOCIAL NETWORKS AS AN EFFECTIVE TOOL FOR HR MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. *This article assesses the potential of corporate social networks in the implementation of personnel management methods. It has been established that corporate social networks can enhance employee productivity and foster a favorable socio-psychological climate within the team. The establishment of a corporate network involves various limitations and risks, complicating the creation of such networks in certain companies.*

Keywords: *human resource management, personnel recruitment, personnel management, virtual social networks, corporate social networks.*

The relevance of the study is determined by the emergence of new technologies and algorithms for implementing personnel management methods through interaction with personnel via corporate social networks, as well as the necessity for a scientific analysis of the potentials and prospects of such technologies. The methodological foundation of the study comprises works by scholars addressing issues of transformation and novel combinations in the application of personnel management methods within companies amid active digitalization across all levels of the economy.

Contemporary business conditions, the active use of internet platforms to organize remote interactions, the rapid dynamics of external and internal environments, and the new generation of labor market candidates—all these necessitate revising traditional approaches and focusing on the implementation of current practices in personnel management. Modern globalization trends, the expansion of business into online channels, mobility, intense competition, and continuous business development require companies to align with new trends in the HR domain [1, p. 54].

Social Networks are a phenomenon that emerged at the turn of the 20th and 21st centuries. Currently, they are firmly embedded in human world perception, which in turn has led to the emergence of new models of social behavior and

personnel management strategies. Social Networks have evolved from simple information archives into tools for recruiting, influencing business processes, and employee training [2].

Today, innovative technologies such as social networks are employed to satisfy the company's personnel needs; due to their prevalence and functions, they have become a significant factor in personnel management practice. According to M.S. Bezbogova, a social network is 'a virtualized social environment in which an individual establishes, expands, and deepens social ties, forming a specific structure of relationships, socializes, self-realizes, generates, and consumes any information of interest through various communication channels in particular forms' [3, p. 7]. O.A. Grimov claims that social networks are '...one of the most crucial elements of modern sociocultural and information-communicative reality' [4 p. 3]. A.E. Volchina points out that a social network acts as '...a "conductor" of self-identification, offering users the opportunity to form the Self-Image — an idealized construction of a set of identification models, with which an individual seeks to associate and simultaneously receive a certain evaluation from others» [5, pp. 3-4]. D.V. Vynnyk, discussing the phenomenon of social networks, emphasizes that they represent «...a new form of social self-organization» [6, p. 110]. Furthermore, the author indicates that a social network is «an interactive multi-user website...» [6, p. 113]. The presented list of concepts allows us to assert that currently there is no single universally accepted definition of the stated phenomenon, as the concept of social networks remains insufficiently studied.

In general terms, social networks on the internet are understood as a platform (online service, website) designed for the construction, representation, and organization of social relationships within the online space [7, p. 24]. The principal characteristics of social networks are virtuality, interactivity, and multimedia functionality (Table 1).

Table 1. Properties of Social Networks

Property	Characteristic
Virtuality	In the online space, a personal profile is created, serving as the user's main page on the platform, thus enabling the transfer of the individual's personality, its attributes, and interests into the virtual environment.
Interactivity	The capacity for interaction among users of the social network, as well as between the user and the content, including in "real-time" mode
Multimedia	The presentation/transmission of information primarily through modes simplified for human perception—such as images, videos, animated graphics, etc.

Table – author's design

The above-mentioned key properties of virtual social networks, facilitated by the advancement of digital technologies, have contributed to their diverse applications, including in business.

The topic of applying social networks in the field of management is actively researched by both domestic and foreign authors. Particular attention is devoted to their use in the personnel selection process. Social networks are regarded as a powerful and effective tool for recruiting. For instance, D.N. Nazarova and A.S. Chabanov emphasize that integrating social networks into HR managers' work opens new prospects: it not only facilitates the search for highly qualified specialists but also enables the development of a promising database of candidates that can be utilized in the future [8, p. 18]. Employers increasingly utilize social networks for hiring decisions [9, p. 70; 10, p. 42]. The primary advantage of social networks is considered to be the ability to contact both candidates who are actively seeking employment and interesting professionals who are not currently looking for a job [11, p. 60].

The process of attracting applicants through social networks is schematically illustrated in Fig. 1. Each stage constitutes a comprehensive activity that must be conducted regularly. Recognizing the need for additional external personnel recruitment, companies can create a corporate group or community, the content of which should correspond to the company's activities [12, p. 1].

Fig. 1. Diagram of attracting candidates to the company through social networks (Author's development).

One of the relatively new directions in personnel recruiting is the implementation of innovative recruiting methods [13; 14], among which are the search for and interaction with candidates through social networks. Information about vacancies is posted on the relevant platforms, and recruiting specialists organize interactions with potential candidates. For many companies, social recruiting is not a mere fad but a deliberate practice that enhances the efficiency of personnel selection.

The conventional procedure for using social networks in personnel selection entails addressing two key tasks:

- searching for information about potential employees, verifying data, and evaluating the applicant by direct and indirect parameters — lifestyle, interests, friends, and so forth;
- posting vacancies to a specific target audience [15, p. 436].

Contemporary researchers note that when addressing the issue of digitalization of personnel recruitment and selection in companies, the following factors must be considered: company size; personnel headcount; employee turnover rate; categories of recruited employees; implemented personnel recruitment technologies; standard vacancy closing period; cost of digital tools and their technical maintenance.

In micro- (up to 15 employees) and small (up to 100 employees) companies, the need for personnel recruitment and selection arises episodically. Therefore, the use of expensive digital tools seems impractical; the task of personnel selection and recruitment can be carried out using traditional methods based on referral programs, social recruiting (searching within social networks), and job search websites [16].

Recruiting via social networks is a method of searching for candidates by utilizing social network platforms either as a talent database or for posting information about open vacancies and positions. Recruiting on social networks can involve advertising vacancies either through HR vendors or via crowdsourcing, where candidates share vacancies through their personal social profiles. This practice enables the identification, attraction, and hiring of both active and passive candidates through the social networks they inhabit.

Recruiting identifies the following methods/strategies: 1) building the company's reputation online; 2) using video to engage passive candidates; 3) employing a specialist to create posts on social networks (content creator); 4) regularly producing high-quality content; 5) supporting and increasing the engagement of potential candidates/creating communities; 6) leveraging innovations and new technologies.

Finally, it is recommended to use various neural networks to compose templates or pre-prepared texts for posts about employee recruitment on social networks. AI technologies assist in competently creating a ready-made template or text, which can then be edited. This is due to the fact that these technologies can reduce specialists' workload, save time, and do not require financial expenditures [17; 18; 19].

Significant attention in the scientific literature is also devoted to analyzing the application of corporate social networks in management. A. A. Petrova links this to numerous managerial tasks addressed through corporate social networks, including enhancing employee productivity [20, p. 124].

A Corporate Social Network is an internal portal designed for the company's target audience, constructed on the principles of a social network and incorporating extended functionalities for communication and interaction among participants in

the interests of the corporation. Essential social communication among employees in the workplace is organized and aligned with the company's mission, goals, and objectives. A Corporate Social Network can be developed both for the company's employees and for its external audience — partners and dealers. As a rule, access to the internal corporate social network is restricted to external users [21, p. 82]. Corporate Social Networks provide the company's top management with a powerful tool for creating and daily sustaining a unified corporate culture. The external level of artifacts is reflected in the overall design of the electronic portal, with the company's logos and attributes present daily on the employee's electronic desktop. Approaches to solving daily tasks, including the established logic of issuing instructions, adhering to regulations, and the necessity of identifying and documenting difficulties and problems in work, become a form of distance learning of the fundamentals of the production system adopted by the company and monitoring its implementation [21, p. 84].

The primary task of corporate social networks is to ensure the main flows of information: from 'top' to 'bottom.' In the first case, it refers to information originating from the company's top executives, which must be systematically conveyed to personnel. Equally important is the feedback flow from personnel to the manager. Moods, opinions, decisions, evaluations, attitudes, possible proposals, and initiatives — the manager can learn about all these only directly from the employees. Therefore, it is extremely important for the company's management to obtain such information [21, p. 84]. Corporate Social Networks, however, do not replace the existing systems in companies for electronic document management, task adoption, transfer, execution control, managerial, and financial accounting. They are aimed at addressing problems and tasks beyond those established and not specified in existing corporate electronic management systems.

The alignment between the services of corporate social networks and the business objectives they target is shown in Fig. 2.

Corporate Social Networks, as their operational logic and software development advance, alongside a reduction in implementation costs, can become a highly effective tool for optimizing organizational management processes in young innovative companies and, consequently, improving their survivability.

Corporate social networks can contribute to enhancing the effectiveness of personnel management methods. However, their implementation is often accompanied by various difficulties and challenges. Firstly, there are significant costs associated with the development, implementation, support organization, and advancement of corporate social networks projects. Secondly, the extended duration of such projects. They impact virtually all aspects of personnel management and require thorough analysis, strategic planning, and step-by-step elaboration of their implementation and development. Thirdly, difficulties arise in assessing the economic efficiency

of measures for implementing corporate social networks, as the effect of using the network often does not manifest in the short term, which undermines management's confidence in the feasibility of such investments.

Fig. 2. Corporate social network services within the company's business task system (Author's development)

These factors frequently lead companies to reject the use of corporate social networks, as managers do not always perceive a direct correlation between the costs incurred and the benefits gained. It should also be noted that the implementation of corporate social networks may involve risks such as employee resistance to change, leakage of confidential information, and insufficient user activity. The minimization of these risks is achievable through properly organized measures: employee training and enhancing their engagement; development of a clear policy for network usage; and ensuring data security [22, p. 38].

Thus, corporate social networks become an effective tool in the arsenal of HR management, enabling a significant increase in labor productivity.

This is achieved by reducing the time employees spend performing routine tasks such as processing emails, searching for information, and organizing collaborative work. At the same time, corporate networks provide managers with greater opportunities for flexible application of personnel management methods. Thanks to these networks, management gains a tool for deeper employee engagement in work processes, strengthening team cohesion, and fostering a positive climate within the collective.

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IMPORT SUBSTITUTION DIPLOMACY: CAN THE “COLLECTIVE WEST” BE REPLACED BY THE “GLOBAL SOUTH”?

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Abstract. *The article analyzes Russia’s import substitution policy and its success in the ongoing special military operation, which has de facto forced the national economy into a mobilization mode and consolidated the ongoing processes of modernization and industrialization within the framework of preparing a new innovative model of Russian industry. This model seeks to find its ‘own path’ between Western and Eastern technological solutions, the emerging robot-humanoid paradigm of Industry 4.0, and the accelerating energy transition.*

Keywords: *innovative diplomacy, fragmentation, GCSS, alter-globalization, network solutions, import substitution, brand substitution, international projects, sanctions, retaliations, reprisals, Industry 4.0, AI, Big Data.*

What kind of diplomacy must Russia be capable of conducting on both internal and external fronts under the conditions of the special military operation, and how can it minimize losses from severing ties with the real scientific achievements of the “collective West” while avoiding further declines in its own competitiveness by increasingly implementing technologies and technical solutions from the states and companies of the “Global South”?..

The basic understanding of import substitution policy, or partial autarky based on domestic resources (English: Import Substitution Industrialization, ISI), in contemporary economic thought tends toward a qualitative transformation of a range of concepts that enable the assessment of mechanisms for sustainable reproduction of all necessities through the use of previously established classical protectionist measures and their evolution into a comprehensive set of multilayered and multidirectional strategies for maintaining and restoring the critical foundations of technological sovereignty and industrial distinctiveness with the requisite degree of competitiveness and national security. At the same

time, the declared essence of the import substitution policy consists in implementing a comprehensive set of measures by the executive and legislative authorities to help the sovereign state ensure, without losses and in a timely manner, the targeted yet sufficiently comprehensive and large-scale development of the domestic market of necessary production chains, thereby providing painless and effective stimulation of national production of a critical range of goods and services, with the aim of substituting foreign-origin products (imported goods) on the domestic market with the achievements of domestic scientific and technological schools¹.

The fundamental basis of this strategy stems from Friedrich List's concept of 'educational protectionism,' who argued that developing countries cannot compete with industrial leaders without temporary protection of their 'infant industries' through tariffs and subsidies. In the mid-20th century, this idea was further developed by the structuralist theory of Raúl Prebisch and Hans Singer, who justified the necessity of import substitution as the only way to overcome the 'resource curse' caused by the long-term deterioration of terms of trade for natural resource-exporting countries².

Between 2020 and 2025, the essence of import substitution is being reconsidered in the context of global instability, the crisis of the classical division of labor model, increasing specialization in international economic relations, and the implementation of digital transformation across numerous innovative sectors. Contemporary researchers emphasize that today import substitution is not a feasible aim of achieving complete autarky in external markets for alternative product lines, but rather a risk minimization instrument amid the fragmentation of the global economy and the disruption of cross-border value chains. If the classical import substitution model of the 1950s-1980s focused on consumer goods, the modern phase is characterized by an emphasis on import substitution in the "capital" and "innovative" aspects. This entails a shift toward the production of high-tech equipment and software for the ICT sector at the level of digital solutions for AI and Big Data. Academic literature notes that the success of modern import substitution directly depends on the state's ability to integrate it with an export-oriented strategy, as demonstrated by the experiences of China and India, as well

¹ Import substitution definition [Electronic resource] // Fiveable: educational portal. — 2024. — URL: <https://fiveable.me/key-terms/international-economics/import-substitution>

² Chervinski, YA. Import substitution policy: CONCEPTS, METHODS OF ANALYSIS AND MAIN AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT [Electronic resource] // RRSociology: scientific journal. — 2012 (updated 2022). — URL: <https://rrsociology.ru/en/journal/article/358/>

as the Asian “tigers” and “tigrets,” where domestic market substitution became a “springboard” for the subsequent global expansion of national ICT giants^{1,2}

The objectives of import substitution policy in the modern economy are multifaceted and interdisciplinary, revealing the true state of labor resources, their possession of unique competencies, and their access to both materials and technologies that ensure breakthrough and sustainable self-sufficiency within the domestic industry, enabling the steady growth of essential sectors. At the macroeconomic level, the primary objective remains balancing the payment balance by reducing foreign currency expenditures on import purchases and stimulating domestic economic growth through the multiplier effect in industry. However, in recent years, strategic objectives of ensuring national security and the synthesis of solutions in the ICT sector have taken precedence, protecting critical digital infrastructure from hybrid impacts by competitors or adversaries. Global challenges, including the pandemic and geopolitical confrontation, have revealed the vulnerability of countries dependent on the import of critical technologies, as well as the difficulty of procuring various classes of semiconductors, pharmaceutical substances, and communication, encryption, and data transmission operating systems. In this regard, the key objective is to achieve technological autonomy, allowing the state to maintain resilience and uninterrupted governance and life support even under conditions of external isolation. The social objectives of the policy include not only the creation of new jobs but also a qualitative transformation of the labor market structure by fostering demand for highly qualified engineers and developers, which contributes to the preservation of human capital and prevents ‘brain drain.’^{3,4,5}

¹ Tyukavkin, N. M., Anisimova V. Yu. Processes of import substitution in Russian industry: theoretical and practical aspects [Electronic resource] // Scientific Journal “World of Science”. — 2023. — URL: <https://www.mir-nayka.com/jour/article/download/1412/978>

² Successful Import Substitution Policies [Electronic resource] // FasterCapital: analytical portal. — 2025. — URL: <https://fastercapital.com/topics/successful-import-substitution-policies.html>

³ Boyko I. V. Technological component of import substitution policy in Russia // Innovations. 2016. No. 1 (207). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/technologicheskaya-sostavlyayuschaya-politiki-importozamesheniya-v-rossii>

⁴ India’s Industrial Policies: Rejecting the Old Status Quo [Electronic resource] // Council on Foreign Relations (CFR). — 2025. — URL: <https://www.cfr.org/article/indias-industrial-policies-rejecting-old-status-quo-and-creating-new>

⁵ Yakushev N. O., Ustinova K. A., Kochnev A. A. (2024). Import substitution as a factor in the development of domestic digital technologies // Economic and Social Changes: Facts, Trends, Forecast. Vol. 17, No. 3, pp. 82-101. DOI: 10.15838/esc.2024.3.93.5 — URL: <http://esc.vscc.ac.ru/article/29993/full>

The toolkit for implementing the import substitution policy during 2020-2025. constitutes a complex synthesis of administrative, financial, and institutional mechanisms. Traditional tariff instruments include customs duties and quotas, which create artificial price barriers for foreign goods, making domestic counterparts more attractive to consumers. Nevertheless, in contemporary practice, non-tariff measures are deemed more effective, such as technical regulations, developed communication and switching protocols, certification systems, and sanitary standards, which often act as covert tools of market protection, embodying protectionism of national interests. Financial instruments play a special role: concessional lending through specialized development institutions, direct state subsidies to cover R&D expenses, and tax maneuvers (for example, reductions in profit tax and insurance contributions for the ICT sector); there are also subventions, as well as various grants and subsidy programs. These measures enable the reduction of financial risks for companies developing fundamentally new products for the national market^{1,2}

Institutional instruments have become the most dynamically developing component of import substitution policy in the 2020s. The most important among these is the public procurement mechanism, within which strict priorities are set for domestically produced goods. In addition, localization requirements for foreign investors are being actively implemented, compelling transnational corporations to relocate technological cycles within the country and transfer competencies to local specialists. In the most advanced models (for example, the ‘Self-Reliant India’ strategy or the Chinese ‘Made in China 2025’ plan), the state also assumes the role of coordinator in creating innovation clusters and technology parks, where small technology companies gain access to infrastructure and guaranteed demand from large state-owned corporations. Thus, modern import substitution policy instruments are aimed not at mechanically closing borders, but at creating a competitive environment that stimulates national businesses toward a technological breakthrough^{3,4}

¹ Examples of successful import substitution strategies [Electronic resource] // *FasterCapital*. — 2024. — URL: <https://fastercapital.com/topics/examples-of-successful-import-substitution-strategies-in-developing-countries.html>

² Abdikeev N.M. Import substitution in high-tech industries under external sanctions. *Management Sciences*. 2022;12(3):53-69. <https://doi.org/10.26794/2304-022X-2022-12-3-53-69>

³ Ustyuzhanina Elena Vladimirovna, Novikova Ekaterina Sergeevna Problems of import substitution and ways to solve them under sanctions pressure // *KE*. 2023. No. 5. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/problemny-importozamescheniya-i-puti-ih-resheniya-v-usloviyah-sanktsionnogo-davleniya>

⁴ Belykh S. IMPORT SUBSTITUTION AS A STRATEGY OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT // *Magyar Tudományos Journal*. 2020. № 41-2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/import-substitution-as-a-strategy-of-economic-development>

Therefore, the task of modern Russian diplomacy is to more actively and professionally engage the existing diplomatic attaché network abroad and to establish harmonization within the cooperation chains of economic entities under the execution of orders pursuant to Federal Laws 44-FZ, 223-FZ, and 225-FZ, the primary legislative acts aimed at closing vulnerabilities, thereby enabling a mergers and acquisitions policy on terms favorable to us within the international context. At the same time, it is necessary to continue striving to exchange both frozen assets with all potential foreign investors and to return to external markets the stocks of machine tools, screw-assembly equipment, or the incompletely realized network cooperation left with us by Western manufacturers in the form of fragmentation and an assessment of the further prospects of the GCSS. Here, it is precisely the «Global South» that becomes the starting point for developing efficiency and growing innovation due to ongoing regionalization through our enterprises and the processes of brand substitution for each product requested by enterprises, which becomes unique (as it is oriented towards existing scientific schools within the country), while at the same time capable of actively integrating into the international cooperation of accelerated projects in the fuel and energy complex, military-industrial complex, and space sectors. And it is precisely the extent of involvement of our specialists in the external networks of scientific research conglomerates that will evaluate our diplomatic capacity and demonstrate readiness for the next step — reindustrialization within the new energy transition.

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DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONNEL MARKETING IN THE HOTEL AND RESTAURANT SERVICES MARKET

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Abstract. *The article substantiates the role of personnel marketing in improving the quality of work in the hotel and restaurant business. It is proved that competence and expertise are the basic categories of personnel marketing necessary to ensure high-quality work, and the development of recommendations for improving the marketing policy of enterprises today cannot be carried out without defining, developing, and evaluating the key competencies and the level of expertise of each employee and the staff of the enterprise as a whole.*

Keywords: *hotel and restaurant business, personnel marketing, employer brand, competence-based approach.*

In modern conditions, the development of an enterprise requires certain competitive advantages: acquisition and utilization by personnel of new knowledge and skills that allow them to be leaders in their market segment; continuous development of personnel and investment in them; creation of high Brand value for the employer, ensuring an attractive position of the enterprise in the labor market.

Only activities based on these advantages provide an opportunity to create conditions for meaningful, creative, and spiritual work — work with high results for both the hired employee and the enterprise. Creating conditions at various levels (public, corporate, individual) for quality work — quality modern workplaces, reasonable employment, guarantees of job security, and opportunities for professional growth for each employee — also ensures the realization of decent labor. The quality of labor is significantly influenced by the scientific and technical level of production, the state of scientific organization of labor, socio-economic

conditions of production, the quality of the workforce, its organization, activity, and competence in its field.

Based on this, in order to ensure quality work and support the competitiveness of enterprises and the economy as a whole, it is necessary to create conditions for effective labor activity — at various levels, to ensure compliance of labor with certain standards of human behavior (levels of knowledge, skills, abilities, experience) in order to achieve the planned result. The results of qualitative labor demonstrate high labor productivity, the quality of products, services, and works, as well as the economic and social effectiveness of labor activity.

Personnel Marketing in this respect serves as a strategic tool of personnel policy, a mechanism for developing the employer Brand, a system of internal communications, and a value-oriented approach to personnel management.

Let us examine the objectives of Personnel Marketing as applied to the operation of enterprises in the hotel and restaurant sector (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Goals of Personnel Marketing in the Hotel and Restaurant Services Sector

In the hospitality and food service industry, the effectiveness of personnel marketing is inextricably linked to the customer experience. The perception of an enterprise's services by guests is largely determined by the quality of interaction with personnel, who are the primary service providers. A high level of personnel engagement and enthusiasm correlates with customer satisfaction, loyalty, repeat visits, and recommendations. At the same time, employee dissatisfaction leads to decreased productivity and the projection of negativity, which adversely affects client loyalty. [1].

Current realities require hotel and restaurant enterprises to seek effective solutions. Personnel Marketing, as shown in (Figure 2), offers a number of advantages that make it a valuable investment.

Figure 2. Advantages and results of personnel marketing

Establishing an attractive employer image. In scientific literature, the employer brand is defined as «...a set of organizational qualities associated by the target audience with a distinctly positive image and a unique combination of material and immaterial benefits» [2]. The organization’s reputation as an employer influences both potential candidates and current employees. It creates a specific image of the company, based on the emotional perception and subjective impressions of the personnel. Thus, for new employees, the attractiveness of the employer’s Brand becomes a key factor in their choice, while for existing employees, it plays a decisive role in maintaining or decreasing their motivation and loyalty to the company. A well-designed personnel marketing strategy contributes to the creation of a positive employer Brand, which enhances trust in the organization and its competitiveness in the labor market.

Attraction and retention of qualified personnel. In conditions of high competition in the labor market, a unique value proposition from the employer becomes the principal tool in shaping an attractive image of the company for specialists possessing rare competencies. Attraction and retention of qualified personnel through personnel marketing are not limited solely to the hiring process but constitute a systematic effort to create conditions under which employees view the organization not only as a workplace but also as a space for professional and personal development. Personnel Marketing in this context also contributes to reducing staff turnover, allowing «... to create new high-quality conditions for enhancing the motivation of existing employees toward better performance» [3].

Improving service quality. Personnel Marketing in the hotel and restaurant sector contributes to the formation of corporate service standards, ensures quality service based on customer orientation and emotional involvement of Personnel, and fosters the creation of positive client impressions that extend beyond the functional service. This directly influences guest satisfaction, encourages repeat visits, and fosters long-term loyalty to the enterprise Brand.

Sustainable customer experience. Personnel in the hotel and restaurant industry must strive to provide exemplary customer service by maintaining constant contact with clients. Personnel marketing, in turn, enables the standardization of these contacts, ensures consistent service quality, and fosters a positive experience of interaction with the Brand. Marketing initiatives for personnel help individuals understand the intricacies of what is happening at the enterprise, learn about the latest news and updates, newest products, offers, promotions, and much more. This, in turn, enables them to provide exceptional services to clients by possessing the necessary knowledge. Familiarity with the Brand's operations and its essence also provides an opportunity to establish certain service standards in the hospitality industry that truly reflect the Brand [4].

Efficiency of economic activity. Optimization of personnel management processes, enhancement of internal communications, implementation of diverse motivational systems, and the development of corporate culture within the team lead to increased productivity and rational use of human capital, ensuring a reduction in personnel turnover and a decrease in costs inevitably arising from recruitment, training, and adaptation of new employees.

Long-term competitive advantage. An effective personnel marketing policy enables hotel and restaurant service enterprises to create unique value propositions that are difficult for competitors to replicate, thereby ensuring complete customer satisfaction and sustainable competitive positions in the market.

For effective personnel management in the hotel and restaurant sector, it is advisable to consider it as a two-level system encompassing external and internal marketing. This division is manifested in strategic and operational approaches (see

Table 1). Strategic Personnel Marketing, as an integral part of personnel policy, aims at long-term planning and implementation of programs for attracting and retaining employees, based on the results of marketing research. In contrast, operational Personnel Marketing focuses on solving current personnel tasks, actively employing various marketing strategies (such as conversion marketing, innovative marketing, synchro-marketing, and remarketing) to influence both the external labor market and internal personnel. It is important to note that for enterprises in the hotel and restaurant sector, as well as for others, the development of modern, scientifically grounded approaches to assessing labor quality, utilizing advanced methods of economic analysis and mathematical modeling, remains relevant.

For an effective assessment of personnel labor quality in the hotel and restaurant industry, it is essential to develop a competence model. This model should be constructed based on the principles of the competency approach and adapted to the specific characteristics of each particular profession.

Research in this field examines labor quality through the prism of the competence-based approach, defining competence and competency as the ability of personnel to solve a particular class of production tasks, that is, the practical application of existing knowledge, skills, and abilities.

Table 1 — Content of strategic and operational personnel marketing in hotel and restaurant enterprises

Levels	Directions of personnel marketing	
	external	internal
strategic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — analysis of the regional and industry labor market; — analysis of the prospects for the development of productive forces in the region; — development of a strategy for attracting highly qualified personnel; — selection of external sources to cover personnel needs; — study of the social needs of the labor force carriers to create an optimal motivation system; — examination of changes in labor legislation; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — analysis of the overall enterprise development strategy; — analysis of the state of the corporate labor market; — analysis of personnel requirements; — development of personnel requirements; — analysis of job attractiveness; — analysis of the labor potential of an employee and the team; — selection of internal sources to meet personnel requirements; — calculation of planned expenses for forming and maintaining a highly effective team;

Levels	Directions of personnel marketing	
	external	internal
	— analysis of competitors' activities, i.e., studying forms and methods of personnel management, the specifics of personnel policy to choose one's own personnel management strategy	
operational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — advertising activities in the field of personnel marketing; — development of tactics for attracting highly qualified personnel; — search, selection, and recruitment of the required personnel; — establishment and maintenance of relations with external sources to fulfill personnel requirements; — maintenance of enterprise competitiveness in the labor market through modifications in the motivation system, labor organization, and production. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — comprehensive evaluation of employee competitiveness in the corporate labor market; — establishment of a correspondence between 'labor quality' and 'labor price'; — adaptation of personnel to production requirements; — personnel allocation; — conducting personnel surveys aimed at identifying negative trends in the staffing system and developing measures to eliminate them; — conceptualization of the professional trajectory.

At the same time, as practice shows, personnel with the same basic level of training may demonstrate varying production results. Analysis of the concept of competence and the determination of its quantitative indicators enable the identification of factors underlying the observed differences in personnel labor performance and the prediction of their success in fulfilling their functions. Within this approach, competence serves as an indicator of labor quality and a system-forming element, with respect to which the organization, optimization, and harmonization of all other components of the system are conducted.

From our point of view, these characteristics correspond to the concept of modern labor quality assessment, as they demonstrate the objectivity of the applied evaluation procedures, establish a relationship between personnel performance and the level of their material incentives, and create conditions for improving the productivity and efficiency of each employee's labor, which directly affects the achievement of the organization's strategic goals.

The competency-based approach entails extensive use of the concepts of "competence" and "competency," which replace the notion of "qualification." The integration of the presented categories into the personnel marketing system must

be conducted in accordance with their substantive characteristics, the study of which holds considerable scientific interest.

The analysis of the theoretical foundations and the interrelation between the concepts of “competency” and “competence” reveals their inseparable connection. Competence, as a fundamental concept, describes a set of personal and professional qualities of an employee, developed through education and experience, which confer competitive advantages. Competence, in turn, demonstrates how effectively these qualities are applied in work, thereby determining the quality of labor of a specific specialist.

Based on the results of previous studies, it can be asserted that competence and competency are fundamental categories of personnel marketing necessary to ensure high labor quality, and the development of recommendations for improving enterprise marketing policies today cannot be carried out without defining, developing, and evaluating the key competencies and the level of competence of each employee and the personnel of the enterprise as a whole.

It should be noted that in modern economic conditions, the importance of personnel marketing for organizational functioning is significantly increasing, with the key factor being their ability to respond to market demands. Under the influence of personnel marketing tools, a specific type of strategic thinking develops: managers at various levels make decisions based on analyzing their impact on the long-term development prospects of the enterprise. Such a market-oriented strategy becomes particularly relevant amid global economic upheavals, when even leading companies are compelled to reconsider their key competencies and competitive advantages.

In personnel marketing, competencies are regarded as a strategic resource through which the organization creates and sustains the employee value proposition (EVP) and actualizes the employer brand promise in interactions with internal and external audiences.

Marketing competence of an organization is understood as «...knowledge that ensures its effective operation by finding a correspondence between its capabilities to create a quality offer and consumer demand» [5]. Competence in the field of marketing is gradually developed through the systematic selection, interpretation, and accumulation of information, which is reflected both in the enhancement of marketing activities and in the optimization of the structure of specialized departments. Enhancing the level of marketing competence serves as a crucial prerequisite for the successful operation of enterprises in the market and represents a significant direction for improving the competitiveness of domestic organizations in the context of the emerging information society.

Figure 3. Conceptual Model for the Development of Personnel Marketing in Hotel and Restaurant Enterprises

The Competency-based approach in Personnel Marketing acts as a link between HR practices and the marketing policy of hotel and restaurant enterprises: through systematic description, development, and evaluation of competencies, the

organization ensures predictability of employee behavior, reproducibility of customer experience, and effectiveness of actions aimed at creating a valuable Brand in the context of 'service co-production'; it is precisely the individual with a set of competencies who is the primary bearer of the Brand promise, and the competent integration of competencies into Personnel Marketing is one of the key factors of competitive advantage in the industry.

The research enabled the formulation of a conceptual model for the development of personnel marketing in hotel and restaurant service enterprises (fig. 1.9), based on ensuring the improvement of workforce quality through the development of personnel competences and facilitating the formation of an attractive employer Brand.

The Employer Brand Concept originates from the marketing brand concept, developed from the perspective of human resource management. Considering that Personnel Marketing is a factor ensuring the effective operation of the entire enterprise, management seeks to improve Personnel quality by allocating funds for professional training.

The implementation of a conceptual model of Personnel Marketing enables the formation of a personalized approach to human resource management that ensures alignment of the interests of the organization and its employees, creates a foundation for targeted development of personnel potential and maintenance of a high level of professionalism, and also facilitates the formation of a long-term personnel reserve, minimizing turnover risks and contributing to organizational stability.

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MODERN URBAN ENVIRONMENT: SOLUTIONS FOR SMALL CITIES IN RUSSIA¹

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Abstract: *The article is devoted to the study of the impact of measures aimed at the development of urban infrastructure as part of the implementation of projects for the improvement of the territories in small Russian cities, on their development and increase of attractiveness for the population and tourists. The results of the All-Russian Competition of the Best Projects for Creating a Comfortable Urban Environment, held by the Ministry of Construction of Russia, are analyzed.*

Keywords: *urban environment, improvement, small cities, national program, All-Russian Competition, federal support, infrastructure.*

The Russian Ministry of Construction is holding a competition for the best projects for creating a comfortable urban environment within the framework of the national program «Housing and Urban Environment». This initiative was implemented on behalf of the head of state and is aimed at supporting municipalities that create high-quality public spaces. The events are regulated by a special procedure for the distribution of federal subsidies among the regions that have won the competition for projects to improve urban infrastructure.

The competition procedure was approved by Resolution of the Russian Federation № 237 (dated 07.03.2018, the latest version — amendments and additions dated March 24, 2025) [2]. This All-Russian competition has become an important arrangement for modernizing Russian cities. Thanks to the competition, thousands of localities have received additional funding for the development of the urban landscape. This program is not just a formal action, but an effective tool for interaction between government authorities, the professional community (architects, urbanists, economists, sociologists) and the population, aimed at creating comfortable living conditions. Over the years, the competition has allowed the implementation of hundreds of successful projects, significantly transforming

¹Funding: YarSU, project No. VIP-017.

small towns and historical settlements, improving the quality of life, attractiveness for investment and tourist activity.

The main directions of the development of a comfortable urban environment include the creation of attractive living conditions for residents and attracting tourists, among which it is necessary to highlight:

— development of auto-free zones: improvement of streets, parks and squares helps to generate interest in the territory among tourists and improve the quality of the local population;

— the creation of public spaces involves the construction of new cultural facilities, theaters and sports grounds attracts the attention of both citizens and visitors of the city;

— an increase in the level of landscaping is associated with an improvement in the appearance of buildings, facades, and street lighting, which has a positive effect on the perception of the city by guests.;

— the formation of tourist routes, in particular, the development of interesting excursion programs and drawing attention to historical sites stimulates the growth of tourism. The implemented projects create unique conditions for each specific city, emphasizing its individuality and attractiveness.

Table 1 illustrates the dynamics of the main indicators of the competition for the period from 2018 to 2025: changes in submitted applications, the number of finalists, the amount of allocated federal grants, as well as the number of completed facilities as of the end of 2025 are shown — about 74% of the total number of winning projects.

Table 1 [by 1]

Indicators of the results of the All-Russian competition of the best projects for creating a comfortable urban environment in cumulative terms for 2018-2025

Indicators	Contests/year of the contest									
	I	I-II	I-III	I-IV	I-V	I-VI	I-VII	I-VIII	I-IX	I-X
	2018 y.	2019 y.	2020 y.	2020 y.	2021y.	2022y.	2022y.	2023 y.	2024 y.	2025 y.
Number of applications submitted, pcs	451	781	1081	1382	1688	1968	2162	2557	2951	3375
Number of submitted applications for one competition, pcs	451	330	300	301	306	280	194	395	394	424
Number of winners, units	80	160	240	400	560	720	800	945	1185	1425
Number of winners in one competition, units	80	80	80	160	160	160	80	145	240	240

The amount of the Federal grant, million rubles	4900	9880	14880	24880	34880	47690	54880	70704	87080	107080
The average amount of the grant per winner, million rubles	61,25	61,75	62,00	62,20	62,29	66,24	68,60	74,82	73,49	75,14
Number of completed projects in total for the period, pcs										878

As follows from the table, the maximum number of applications was submitted in 2018 for the first competition. In recent years, after a decrease in this indicator, there has been growing interest in the competition. The amount of allocated federal funds is increasing annually, and the average grant amount for each winner is gradually increasing.

An All-Russian competition dedicated to selecting the best initiatives to create a comfortable urban environment in historical settlements and small Russian cities plays a key role in improving the comfort of citizens by creating attractive public areas and implementing successful urban planning solutions. This project promotes successful examples of innovation among small towns in the country, ensuring the dissemination of best practices throughout the state.

The expert commission conducts an assessment according to the established methodology, applying a matrix of criteria. The main parameters of the analysis are aspects such as social significance, which assesses the degree to which the project meets the current needs of the city's population and the potential of the standard of living. In terms of ensuring environmental sustainability, the impact of project activities on the ecology of the territory is being studied and measures are proposed to reduce possible negative consequences. When assessing economic efficiency, the estimated costs and potential benefits of the project are compared. Special attention is paid to the artistic qualities of the proposed solutions and the harmonious combination of new buildings with the surrounding urban environment, taking into account the unique ideas and modern approaches introduced into the projects. The winner of the competition is the participant who has demonstrated the best performance according to the specified criteria.

Among the key factors hindering the victory of the projects announced in the competition are insufficient depth of study of documents confirming the reality and achievability of the planned results; weak disclosure of the mechanisms of influence on the development of urban areas adjacent to the design area; lack of assessment of the needs of the target audience in the proposed activities and requests from it; incomplete justification for the coordination of planned actions with previously implemented measures for improvement of adjacent areas of the city.

To increase the chances of successful participation, it is recommended to take into account the following principles of preparing applications:

1. Approach the development of the project consciously, focusing on the real needs and goals of the city's development.
2. Rely on qualified expertise and accumulated experience of successful initiatives of the past years.
3. Formulate tasks that go beyond simple landscaping and cover the strategy of integrated development of the city.
4. Regularly interact with local authorities, residents and business representatives.

The tasks of the project team are not only to prepare an application according to a standard package of documents, but also to fully and truly display all the real events taking place on the territory of a particular small town or historical settlement. Thus, the structure and requirements for the application are only a basic guide, which should not limit the creative approach of team members and prevent the disclosure of the essence of the submitted project. It is important to remember that each city has unique features: if significant information is missing from the established criteria, it should not be ignored, but should be given more attention, as this may highlight the strengths of the project. The competition should be interpreted not only as a source of financial support for landscaping, but also as a chance to start the processes of positive changes in the city, using an integrated approach and involving the maximum number of participants to create a comfortable and harmonious urban environment.

The events of the All-Russian Competition contribute to improving the skills of specialists from regions and architectural organizations, creating attractive conditions for tourists and small businesses through the transformation of urban spaces. Due to the reconstruction and modernization of public areas, parks and walking areas, various services are comfortably accessible to residents. These measures stimulate the use of innovative approaches to the development of urban infrastructure, increasing the level of convenience and attractiveness of small settlements by attracting investments for the implementation of infrastructure projects, including private and public funds [by 3].

The analysis of table 2 shows the dynamics of the number of winners of the All-Russian Competition for the best projects for creating a comfortable urban environment in various federal districts of Russia from 2018 to 2025. A total of 1,425 winning projects were identified during this period. The Central Federal District is the leader in terms of the number of winning projects, reaching the largest number in 2025 (63 projects, 397 in just 8 years), which indicates a high level of activity and development of the region's infrastructure. According to the results of ten competitions, the share of the winning projects of the Central Federal District in the total number of winners was almost 28% (that is, about a third). The Volga Federal District is slightly inferior, demonstrating stable growth and interest in improving the urban environment (361 projects over the entire period is a quarter of the total number).

Table 2 [by 1]
 Winners of the All-Russian Competition of the best projects for creating
 a comfortable urban environment in the Federal Districts (FD)

Indicators	FD*	Competitions/year										By FD
		I 2018	II 2019	III 2020	IV 2020	V 2021	VI 2022	VII 2022	VIII 2023	IX 2024	X 2025	
Number of winning projects in competitions, units	CFD	25	20	26	43	47	48	25	40	60	63	397
	NWFD	13	15	10	22	24	13	5	20	23	36	181
	SFD	4	7	3	11	11	8	2	21	23	30	120
	NCFD	5	4	1	5	6	9	5	13	18	15	81
	VFD	26	17	24	45	39	46	23	24	63	54	361
	UFD	1	8	4	12	11	9	4	10	20	19	98
	SFD	4	4	5	13	15	18	6	17	33	23	138
	FEFD	2	5	7	9	7	9	10	separate competition			49
	Total	80	80	80	160	160	160	80	145	240	240	1425

* Explanations to the table:

- CFD (Central Federal District)
- NWFD (Northwestern Federal District)
- SFD (Southern Federal District)
- NCFD (North Caucasian Federal District)
- VFD (Volga Federal District)
- UFD (Ural Federal District)
- SFD (Siberian Federal District)
- FEFD (Far Eastern Federal District)

The North-Western Federal District showed moderate growth, but significant increases occurred in 2020 and 2021, which highlights the increased attention to urban improvement in the region. The Southern and North Caucasus Federal Districts have less activity, but both show a positive trend of increasing participation and the number of winning projects. The Ural and Siberian Federal districts show a steady level of activity, second only to the Central Federal District in terms of the number of victories. The Far Eastern Federal District has significantly increased the number of wins in individual competitions, reflecting the state’s attention to the development of the eastern regions, and starting in 2023, a separate competition has been allocated for small towns in the district.

Currently, landscaping includes not only traditional methods of landscaping and park development, but also the introduction of modern technologies. These include the use of energy-saving solutions, the creation of bike paths and pedestrian zones, and the introduction of interactive elements into public spaces.

Despite significant achievements, there are difficulties associated with the need to attract significant resources to implement large projects, take into account environmental, social and economic factors at the same time, and maintain long-term efficiency to ensure a sustainable effect after completion of construction and landscaping. In addition, public participation is necessary, as it is important to support and actively involve residents in the decision-making process regarding future changes in the city.

The Federal competition is an effective device for supporting positive transformations in Russian cities, providing the basis for further growth and prosperity of municipalities. The competition helps to draw the attention of the public and the authorities to the problems of small towns, for which there are opportunities for development, increasing the attractiveness and quality of life of their residents through the creation of new modern recreational areas.

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AN ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK FOR IMPROVING CADASTRAL VALUATION IN TRANSITIONAL ECONOMIES

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Abstract: *cadastral valuation systems constitute a fundamental component of land administration and property taxation frameworks. In transitional economies, such systems frequently experience structural distortions due to institutional instability, limited market transparency, inconsistent data infrastructure, and methodological deficiencies in mass appraisal procedures [4], [5]. This study proposes an integrated economic framework for improving cadastral valuation systems without reliance on complex econometric modeling. The framework combines four interrelated dimensions: market alignment, fiscal stability, institutional reliability, and data quality assurance. Unlike purely technical valuation approaches, the proposed model emphasizes gradual convergence mechanisms, governance capacity, and transparency safeguards to ensure socially and fiscally sustainable implementation. The framework is adaptable to transitional economies undergoing modernization of land administration systems and digital transformation processes [1].*

Keywords: *cadastral valuation; land taxation; transitional economies; mass appraisal; institutional reform; valuation zoning; land administration.*

1. Introduction

Cadastral valuation plays a central role in value-based property taxation systems and directly influences municipal revenue stability and investment attractiveness [5]. In transitional economies, the transition from administratively determined values to market-oriented cadastral valuation has often led to discrepancies between cadastral and observed market values [4]. Such discrepancies may generate fiscal imbalances and social resistance to tax reforms.

Research demonstrates that successful implementation of mass appraisal systems requires reliable valuation infrastructure, access to representative market data, and institutional transparency [4], [5]. In small or thin markets, typical for many transitional regions, mass valuation models may become unstable due to

insufficient transaction observations [4]. This instability increases the probability of systematic valuation bias.

Moreover, inaccuracies in cadastral attributes — particularly parcel area discrepancies and incomplete land-use information — can significantly distort valuation outcomes [2]. Therefore, improving cadastral valuation requires not only methodological refinement but also systemic enhancement of data quality and institutional reliability.

The purpose of this study is to develop a comprehensive economic framework for improving cadastral valuation systems in transitional economies through integrated market, fiscal, institutional, and data-quality mechanisms.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Mass appraisal challenges in transitional economies

Mass appraisal methods are widely used to determine cadastral values for taxation purposes. However, their effectiveness depends on data sufficiency and methodological consistency [4]. In transitional economies, weak market transparency and uneven transaction coverage limit model accuracy.

Comparative analysis of European property taxation systems indicates that fiscal sustainability depends on transparent valuation standards and coherent institutional arrangements [5]. Without such foundations, large-scale revaluation may produce volatility and undermine trust.

2.2 Digital valuation systems and institutional integration

Digital integration of cadastral systems and valuation information models improves administrative consistency and transparency. The development of valuation information models compatible with LADM demonstrates how structured data architecture can strengthen institutional reliability [1].

Integration of cadastre, land registry, and geospatial systems enhances procedural clarity and reduces information asymmetry. In forestry and land management contexts, the use of cadastral datasets for integrated planning further confirms the importance of coordinated land information systems [7].

2.3 Data reliability and valuation accuracy

Empirical evidence confirms that unreliability of cadastral data — particularly parcel area inconsistencies — directly affects valuation precision [2]. Transitional economies often inherit heterogeneous datasets formed during rapid institutional reforms, which increases systemic risk in valuation outputs.

Addressing these issues requires systematic auditing of cadastral records and gradual correction mechanisms before implementing revaluation cycles.

2.4 Spatial diagnostics and zoning methodology

Spatial analysis techniques have proven effective in identifying methodological errors in cadastral valuation processes [8]. By detecting clusters of systematic deviation, authorities can prioritize recalibration of valuation zones and parameters.

Research on valuation zoning theory also highlights discrepancies between theoretical zoning frameworks and their practical implementation [10]. Inconsistent zoning logic may create structural valuation distortions across regions.

2.5 Agricultural land valuation specifics

Agricultural land valuation introduces additional uncertainty due to income-based projections and crop price assumptions [3], [6]. Transitional economies frequently require methodological revision to adapt cadastral systems to evolving agricultural and market conditions [6].

3. Methodological Approach

The study adopts a conceptual and institutional-economic approach. Rather than focusing on econometric estimation, the framework emphasizes systemic coherence and practical implementability.

The proposed structure integrates four components:

1. Market Alignment Mechanism
2. Fiscal Stability Mechanism
3. Institutional Reliability Mechanism
4. Data Quality and Spatial Control Mechanism

Each component addresses a specific source of distortion identified in the literature [2], [4], [8].

4. Proposed Economic Framework

4.1 Market Alignment Mechanism

The framework recommends periodic comparison of observed market transaction levels with existing cadastral values at the valuation-zone level. Such comparison enables identification of systematic underestimation or overestimation trends.

In small markets, methodological caution is necessary due to limited transaction samples [4]. Gradual recalibration based on aggregated transaction monitoring reduces volatility and improves alignment with real economic conditions.

4.2 Fiscal Stability Mechanism

Abrupt increases in cadastral values may produce excessive tax burden shifts. Comparative fiscal research indicates that stable taxation systems require gradual implementation and smoothing mechanisms [5]. Therefore, transitional adjustment periods and caps on annual increases are recommended.

4.3 Institutional Reliability Mechanism

Institutional reliability encompasses transparency of valuation methodology, accessibility of appeal procedures, and digital integration of land administration systems. Implementation of structured valuation information models improves procedural clarity and supports governance stability [1].

Digital interoperability between cadastral databases and registry systems reduces administrative fragmentation and strengthens institutional coherence [7].

4.4 Data Quality and Spatial Control Mechanism

Given documented effects of unreliable cadastral attributes on valuation outcomes [2], systematic data-quality audits are essential. Spatial diagnostics can identify clusters of methodological inconsistencies and zoning errors [8], while theoretical and practical refinement of valuation zoning enhances systemic fairness [10].

5. Policy Implications

The proposed framework suggests that transitional economies should prioritize:

- strengthening cadastral data reliability before large-scale revaluation [2];
- implementing gradual fiscal adjustment mechanisms [5];
- enhancing digital integration and valuation information modeling [1];
- applying spatial diagnostics to monitor methodological consistency [8].

Such measures increase valuation credibility and reduce dispute frequency.

6. Discussion

Unlike purely technical mass appraisal upgrades, the proposed framework integrates economic, institutional, and spatial dimensions. Transitional economies are characterized by uneven development of land markets and governance structures. Therefore, a comprehensive and adaptive approach is necessary.

By combining market monitoring, fiscal safeguards, institutional transparency, and spatial diagnostics, the framework addresses systemic weaknesses identified in contemporary research [4], [5], [8].

7. Conclusions

Cadastral valuation reform in transitional economies requires coordinated improvement of methodological, fiscal, and institutional components. The proposed economic framework offers a structured and adaptable pathway for enhancing valuation accuracy and legitimacy without reliance on complex mathematical modeling.

Future empirical research should test this framework within specific national contexts and evaluate its impact on valuation dispersion, dispute rates, and tax revenue stability.

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ANALYSIS OF THE STATE AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF THE PUBLIC CATERING MARKET IN RUSSIA

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Abstract. *This article presents the results of an analysis of the state and development trends of the Russian catering market for 2025. The study was based on statistical data and analytical reports reflecting the growth dynamics of key segments of the catering market, changes in the structure of consumer demand, and the impact of macroeconomic, legislative, and regulatory factors. Summarizing the results of the study, the article develops a SWOT matrix describing the Russian catering market in 2025 and highlights the need for market participants to flexibly respond to the changing environment, implement innovative technologies, and focus on the quality of products and services.*

Keywords: *catering industry, trends in the development of the catering market, key indicators.*

At the present stage, the Russian public catering market is characterized by dynamic transformation due to a combination of macro- and microeconomic factors.

The Russian public catering market continues to show positive dynamics despite economic challenges. The total number of public catering establishments in Russia increased by 8% in 2025, reaching over 240,000 units. Fast-service restaurants grew the fastest in 2025. Their number exceeded 95,000 units, which is 8.7% more than in the corresponding period of the previous year. The Grab&-Go segment, offering ready meals and snacks in individual packaging that can be eaten on the go, also experienced active growth. The number of such outlets grew

by 8.4% (to more than 59,000 units), while the number of bars increased by 7.2%, reaching almost 20,000 units. Restaurants (traditional full-service type) grew by only 6.5%, to 68 thousand units.

Overall, according to INFOLine's estimate, in 2025 the turnover of public catering enterprises increased by 8% compared to 2024, reaching 4.3-4.4 trillion. rubles (in 2024, it increased by 14%). According to data from the analytical center 'Check Index' of the company 'Platform OFD,' the average check in cafés, restaurants, and fast food chains (including both chain and non-chain outlets) in 2025 amounted to 1492 rubles, 11% higher than the previous year. At the same time, the number of purchases increased by only 2% when comparing 2025 to 2024. The average check increased across all categories: at fast food outlets by 10% annually (523 rubles), in cafés and canteens by 9% (up to 758 rubles), and in restaurants and cafés by 13% (2710 rubles). However, in terms of the number of visits, restaurants and bars exhibited a negative trend (-1%), cafés and canteens showed stagnation (+1%), while traffic at fast food outlets increased by 7% [1].

The increase in the average check is attributable to the rise in dish prices and is linked to several factors. Firstly, an increase in the costs of raw materials and ingredients is observed due to overall economic instability and inflation. Official inflation in Russia for 2025 amounted to 5.6%, the lowest over the past five years (according to data from the Central Bank of the Russian Federation). At the same time, there was a significant increase in prices for certain goods and services. For example, within the food products segment, the price of potatoes rose by 62%, white cabbage by 45%, butter by 30%, natural coffee by 24%, fermented dairy products by 19%, and live and chilled fish by 17% [2]. The level of inflation and price growth directly impact the profitability of public catering establishments, as they increase the cost of finished products and reduce profitability.

Another factor driving price increases in the public catering sector is the rise in rental fees for premises, which increases the financial burden on establishments. Thus, the rental rate in 2025 increased on average by 6% (for premises up to 300 m²) and by 18% (for premises over 300 m²) compared to 2024.

Thus, restaurants and cafés are compelled to raise prices to offset costs while maintaining quality, with the increase in the average check being a natural consequence of changes in the cost price of products and services.

Alongside the influence of economic factors, the public catering market in 2025 encountered a series of regulatory and legal changes that substantially impacted the development and operational activities of its participants. The main directions of legislative changes and their characteristics are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 — Key Directions of Legislative Changes in the Russian Public Catering Sector in 2025 and Their Description [3]

Directions	Essence and Description
1. Sanitary and Hygienic Requirements	
Updating SanPiN to Minimize the Risks of Infectious Disease Transmission and to Protect Consumer Health	By the Resolution of the Chief State Sanitary Doctor of the Russian Federation dated August 22, 2024, No. 9, significant amendments were introduced to SanPiN 2.3/2.4.3590-20 (“Sanitary and Epidemiological Requirements for the Organization of Public Catering for the Population”), including the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The obligation to provide complete documentation confirming product compliance with safety and quality standards; • Increased requirements for quality control of raw materials and finished products; • The necessity of regularly updating equipment and maintaining premises in accordance with established hygiene standards.
Introduction of a risk-oriented inspection system for public catering enterprises within the framework of supervision reform.	The frequency and depth of inspections directly depend on the level of potential risk associated with the activities of each specific establishment. Preventive visits and warnings instead of traditional fines are introduced, which contributes to reducing the administrative burden on conscientious entrepreneurs (Key changes in SanPiN for public catering enterprises effective from March 1, 2025).
2. Regulation of taxation and accounting	
Exemption from VAT under the simplified taxation system (STS) to support the development of small and medium-sized businesses in the public catering sector, reducing the financial burden on entrepreneurs	Tax incentives have been introduced for individual entrepreneurs and legal entities operating in the public catering sector and utilizing the simplified taxation system (STS). Provided that the annual income does not exceed 450 million rubles, such entities are exempt from the obligation to pay VAT (Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation dated 02.09.2025 No. 1351).
Introduction of a new procedure for settlements with clients aimed at increasing the transparency of financial operations and reducing the likelihood of tax evasion.	As of March 1, 2025, a law came into effect establishing a new payment procedure in public catering establishments and the mandatory issuance of an official cash receipt to clients prior to payment. The previously common practice of issuing preliminary bills (“pre-checks”) was abolished (New payment rules for guests in public catering from March 1, 2025). Violation of the new procedure exposes entrepreneurs to fines of up to 30,000 rubles.

Directions	Essence and Description
3. Product labeling and electronic documents	
Introduction of a mandatory labeling system aimed at strengthening control over product circulation.	Mandatory labeling is required for goods used in public catering: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vegetable oil (mandatory labeling using Data Matrix codes); • Caviar of sturgeon and salmon species (mandatory withdrawal from circulation through the ‘Chestny Znak’ system); • Non-alcoholic beverages with high sugar content (subject to excise duty and requiring individual accounting).
Implementation of electronic document management to enhance supply transparency and facilitate tax control.	Public catering establishments are required to record incoming products via electronic invoices and promptly transmit this information to state information systems.

The presented changes necessitate the adaptation of public catering enterprises to new business conditions, create certain risks, and increase the complexity of management in a volatile external environment.

It is also important to note the high level of competition intensity in the Russian public catering market, which intensifies both the traditional rivalry among establishments and the pressure from large retailers offering own-produced ‘ready meals,’ thus providing an alternative to restaurants and cafés.

One of the serious problems remains the shortage of qualified personnel. Despite the increase in wages for public catering employees, the issue of specialist shortage remains relevant. In 2025, the average salary of public catering workers increased by 24%, yet the demand for personnel exceeds supply, creating challenges for employers.

The results of the structural analysis of the Russian public catering market in 2025 made it possible to identify key development indicators, the characteristics of which are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 — Key Indicators of the Development of the Russian Public Catering Market for 2025

Indicators	Characteristics of Consumer Behavior
Market Volume	The total volume of the public catering market in Russia for 2025 increased but did not reach the 2024 levels. The primary contribution was made by café establishments, surpassing restaurants and bars.
Number of Establishments	The number of public catering establishments increased, with restaurants, cafés, and bars prevailing. This reflects the overall trend of consumers shifting toward more affordable dining formats.

Indicators	Characteristics of Consumer Behavior
Average check	Average spending on dining out has increased. Price increases, rather than higher visit frequency, played the primary role.
Fast food growth	Fast food has become the market's growth leader. Accessibility and speed make it an attractive alternative to classic restaurants and cafés.
Predominance of cafés	Cafés are growing faster than other market segments. They attract customers by convenience, ease of business launch, and lower requirements for licenses and premises.
Change in the structure of visits	The share of expensive restaurants is decreasing, while the share of inexpensive establishments such as fast food and cafés is increasing.
Market geography:	The leaders in the number of establishments are located in the Central part of Russia, confirming the high concentration of business in metropolitan areas.
Increasing competition	Numerous food delivery services have emerged, intensifying competition among public catering establishments.
Rising costs	Food prices have risen sharply, increasing the cost of dishes and reducing business profitability.
Inflation	High inflation rates compel restaurants to raise prices, diminishing the attractiveness of their offers to consumers.
Labor shortage	The shortage of professional cooks and waiters hampers industry development.
Strengthening of regulators	Government authorities are tightening control over the quality and working conditions of establishments, thereby adding administrative challenges for business owners.

Consumer behavior in the Russian public catering market in 2025 is likewise characterized by several pronounced trends.

One of the key aspects is the differentiation of consumer preferences based on socio-demographic characteristics. Thus, young people aged 18 to 25 exhibit a greater tendency to visit fast-food establishments and coffee shops. Analysis of the presented data indicates that the share of this age group in the total volume of fast-food visits is approximately 45%. The older generation, in turn, demonstrates a stronger preference for traditional formats of establishments, such as full-service restaurants and cafés specializing in national cuisine.

Meeting and communication venues are becoming important criteria when selecting an establishment. All consumers are attracted by the atmosphere of the establishment, the sense of belonging to a community, and comfortable conditions of stay.

The income level of the population exerts a significant influence on consumer behavior. In regions with above-average incomes, there is demand for the premium segment of the public catering market: restaurants with authorial cuisine, specialized

bars, and establishments. In regions with lower income levels, demand predominates for more affordable formats of establishments: canteens, bistros, and cafés.

The growth of digitalization and the development of online delivery platforms significantly influence the structure of consumer demand. Consumers increasingly use mobile applications and websites to order ready-to-eat meals for home or office, resulting in a decline in visits to traditional establishments — restaurants and cafés.

One of the trends in consumer behavior is a shift in value orientations. Thus, the growing trend towards a healthy lifestyle leads to increased demand for dishes made from natural and organic ingredients. Vegetarian and vegan dishes are becoming increasingly popular, prompting many restaurants and cafés to expand their menus by offering alternatives for health-conscious consumers [4].

The results of the conducted studies have identified key indicators of consumer behavior in the Russian public catering market in 2025 (Table 3).

Analyzing the current processes and dynamics of the Russian public catering market for 2025, several key trends and directions can be identified that determine the further development of the industry [5]:

1. *Active implementation of digital technologies.* One of the most important aspects of the modern market is the active use of digital tools and technologies in various sectors of the restaurant business — from administrative systems to loyalty and promotion systems. CRM and ERP systems are particularly relevant, characterized by the highest degree of adoption owing to their ability to enable detailed analysis of consumer patterns and optimization of internal processes. Furthermore, there is active development of mobile applications and online services that facilitate convenient booking, order placement, and online payment for services. The implementation and use of these technologies contribute to enhancing service quality and consumer loyalty, as well as strengthening the competitive position of establishments.

Table 3 — Key Indicators of Consumer Behavior in the Russian Public Catering Market in 2025

Indicators	Characteristics of Consumer Behavior
Increase in Expenditure	Russian consumers have increased their spending on public catering. However, the reason for this growth is linked to an increase in the average check, rather than to the frequency of visits, which has remained nearly unchanged.
Market Structure	Fast food dominates in terms of transaction share (80%), leaving a minor share to other categories (cafés and restaurants — 16%, bars — 4%). This situation reflects consumer preferences for affordable prices and fast service.

Type of establishment	Consumers prefer small and convenient dining formats (café, fast food), indicating a shift from traditional restaurants and large establishments towards small businesses and on-the-go services.
Quality of dishes	Quality plays a key role, but economic factors drive the desire to gain maximum satisfaction for minimal expenditure, which is reflected in the preference for affordable formats.
Price Influence	People have increasingly chosen establishments with affordable prices, reflecting a desire to minimize expenses on leisure and entertainment.
Changes in Habits	Alongside selecting establishments, consumers focus on healthy and functional dishes, emphasizing the importance of food quality and composition.
Turn to Simple Products	Russian cuisine is gaining popularity; people are returning to national culinary traditions, experiencing nostalgia and a yearning for traditional flavors.
Conscious attitude towards health	Diets based on high-quality ingredients and a proper balance of proteins, fats, and carbohydrates are becoming widespread. Consumers prefer establishments that offer fresh, homemade dishes.
Broadening the perception of gastronomy	Consumers are willing to experiment with new presentation styles, eclectic flavors, and unusual recipes, enhancing their consumption experience.
Interest in the unique atmosphere of establishments	Customers are more inclined to visit venues with unique interiors, atmospheres, and histories, paying attention to the creativity of design and service.
Information influence	Decisions regarding the choice of an establishment often depend on reviews, ratings, and recommendations from friends and acquaintances.
Service requirements	Consumers expect a professional approach, high-quality service, and pleasant experiences when visiting an establishment.

2. Expansion of the delivery segment and proliferation of virtual kitchens. A stable trend in public catering is the growing role of food delivery and the emergence of specialized virtual kitchens, which operate exclusively for preparing dishes for takeaway or delivery. Such business formats minimize expenses related to premises maintenance and service staff, concentrating on optimizing production and logistics processes. This model has become popular due to changes in consumers' lifestyles, with a preference for ordering food to their homes or offices rather than visiting a traditional restaurant. As a result, the share of establishments offering delivery services has increased significantly, reaching 64% of the total number of public catering enterprises in Russia.

3. *Regional expansion and diversification of offerings.* Major chain operators are redirecting their activities from central regions to small and medium-sized cities. Moreover, establishments are starting to open in small settlements where public catering infrastructure was previously absent. The primary drivers of regional expansion are the growth of the population’s purchasing power and the development of domestic tourism. As a consequence, local markets of diversified formats and types of establishments with adapted offerings tailored to regional preferences and consumer demands are formed.

4. *Focus on product quality and safety.* Consumer requirements concerning the quality of prepared dishes and their ingredient composition have become significantly more stringent. Furthermore, the trend towards a healthy lifestyle drives the growing demand for environmentally friendly and natural products. These circumstances encourage enterprises to minimize the use of various synthetic additives and preservatives. Simultaneously, measures to enforce compliance with sanitary and hygienic requirements and quality standards by regulatory authorities are being intensified, and government bodies are introducing additional rules to enhance the social responsibility of economic entities.

5. *Market consolidation and expansion of business units.* Consolidation in the public catering market is achieved through mergers and acquisitions of small competitors by large network operators, the establishment of strategic alliances, and joint ventures. This enlargement allows for the expansion of geographic presence, reduction of costs, and optimization of supply chains. Under these conditions, small and medium-sized entrepreneurs are compelled to seek market niches by specializing in unique products, cuisines, or services, as well as integrating into the networks of large operators through franchising.

The synthesis of the conducted research results enabled the identification of key opportunities and threats, strengths and weaknesses, aimed at determining the potential and risks, as well as the advantages and limitations inherent in the Russian public catering market in 2025 (Fig. 1).

Opportunities	Threats
<p>1. <i>Digitalization:</i> the automation of processes and the implementation of digital technologies will enhance the operational efficiency of establishments and attract more customers.</p> <p>2. <i>Growth in delivery popularity:</i> virtual kitchens provide effective models for cost reduction and focusing on the production of high-quality food.</p> <p>3. <i>Formation of regional markets:</i> regions</p>	<p>1. <i>High inflation rate and price increases:</i> rising food product costs cause higher dish production expenses and reduce establishment profitability.</p> <p>2. <i>Strengthening regulation and control:</i> tightening sanitary and epidemiological supervision, labeling rules, and quality standards leads to increased burdens and operating costs for enterprises.</p> <p>3. <i>Intensification of competitive pressure:</i></p>

<p>are developing faster, with new establishments catering to local tastes and needs emerging.</p> <p>4. <i>Increased attention to product quality</i>: eco-friendly and healthy dishes attract a larger share of customers, opening new niches for restaurateurs.</p> <p>5. <i>Market consolidation</i>: major players absorb smaller chains, reducing costs and improving service.</p>	<p>the dominance and expansion of large chain operators create conditions that displace small local enterprises, forcing them to develop diversified offerings.</p> <p>4. <i>Labor shortage</i>: a lack of qualified personnel reduces operational efficiency and creates barriers to business expansion.</p> <p>5. <i>High level of recession</i>: decline in population income, reduction in solvent demand for public catering products and services.</p>
Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>1. <i>Exclusivity of consumer experiences</i>: differentiation through a unique menu and gastronomic offerings, a distinctive atmosphere, and a premium level of service.</p> <p>2. <i>Adaptability to innovations and changes</i>: swift adoption of digital services, new technologies, and adjustment to shifts in customer preferences strengthen competitive advantages.</p> <p>3. <i>Marketing activity</i>: brand promotion and loyalty programs guarantee a stable customer flow.</p> <p>4. <i>Cost management and expense control</i>: effective resource allocation and procurement policy ensure business profitability.</p> <p>5. <i>Development of the digital environment</i>: integration with delivery aggregators and social networks ensures omnichannel interaction with the target market.</p>	<p>1. <i>High level of expenses</i>: continuous cost monitoring is necessary to avoid unprofitable operations.</p> <p>2. <i>Dependence on suppliers</i>: instability of supplies and price fluctuations reduce the predictability and profitability of the business.</p> <p>3. <i>Lack of a clear crisis response plan</i>: insufficient resilience and absence of reserves hinder business operations.</p> <p>4. <i>Inefficient management practices</i>: outdated planning and accounting methods result in loss of efficiency and profit.</p> <p>5. <i>Vulnerability to administrative barriers</i>: bureaucratic obstacles slow business development, increasing costs, including financial and time expenditures.</p>

Figure 1 — SWOT analysis of the Russian public catering market in 2025

Thus, the developed SWOT matrix confirms that the Russian public catering market in 2025 is in a phase of active restructuring, which requires market participants to respond flexibly to the changing environment, implement innovative technologies, and maintain a steady focus on the quality of products and services offered.

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FACTORS INFLUENCING CHANGES IN THE INVESTMENT CLIMATE IN THE KOMI REPUBLIC AND AREAS FOR THEIR IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract. *Based on the analysis of the investment climate in the region, the authors have identified the main reasons for its change in 2025. Key factors influencing the improvement of the investment climate have been identified to promote the effective socio-economic development of the Komi Republic, which holds considerable potential for this purpose.*

Keywords: *national projects, private investments, investment climate, development of the forest industry complex*

The Komi Republic is a vast territory with unique northern nature and extensive opportunities. The area of the region is 416 thousand km², comparable to the territory of France and twice the size of the United Kingdom.

The economy is based on the fuel and energy sector and the forest industry complex. Vast raw material wealth includes oil, gas, coal, gold, bauxite, forests and construction materials, as well as mineral and fresh groundwater.

The Komi Republic possesses significant unrealized potential, primarily in the field of natural resource development.

Annually, approximately 14 million tonnes of oil (including gas condensate), 3.4 billion m³ of gas (both natural and associated), and 7.6 million tonnes of coal are extracted within the region.

The volumes of reserves and extraction of combustible mineral resources define the Komi Republic as the primary fuel base of the European North of Russia.

The share of all-Russian reserves amounts to approximately: 3% of oil, 4.5% of coal, 13% of barite, 30% of bauxite, 50% of titanium, and 80% of vein-quartz raw materials.

The mineral resource potential of the republic is represented by a complex of diverse fuel, metallic, and non-metallic mineral deposits and holds significant importance for the Russian economy. [1]

Fuel mineral resources are represented by oil and gas fields in the southern part of the Timan-Pechora province, major coal deposits of the Pechora Basin, two slate-bearing basins, as well as peat deposits and numerous occurrences.

Oil reserves are accounted for at 154 fields. Half of the remaining recoverable oil reserves are concentrated in the large oil fields of Vostochno-Lambeishorskoye, Yaregskoe, Usinskoe, and Nizhnechutinskoe.

Fuel gas reserves are accounted for at 42 hydrocarbon fields. Approximately one-third of the free gas reserves are contained in the large Vuktyl oil and gas condensate field.

The Pechora coal basin is the second largest in Russia in terms of resources and contains the full range of coals that underpin the development of the raw material base for energy and coking chemistry. Hard coal reserves are accounted for across 11 deposits. Eighty percent of the balance coal reserves are concentrated in four deposits: Inta (26%), Vorgashor (22%), Usinsk (21%), and Vorkuta (11%). [1]

Metallic minerals are represented by industrial deposits of titanium, bauxite, and manganese ores, as well as placer gold, located on the western slope of the Urals and in the Middle and Southern Timan regions.

The Komi Republic is the largest and most promising bauxite ore resource base in Russia, hosting about one-third of the Russian balance reserves of this type of raw material. In the Timan bauxite-bearing province, six deposits have been explored, located in the Middle Timan and South Timan bauxite-bearing districts. Industrial mining of bauxites in Middle Timan has been conducted since 1998.

The gold raw material base comprises 36 industrial placer deposits situated in the Kozhim River basin in the Polar Urals.

The raw material base of ferrous metals comprises titanium, manganese, chromium, and vanadium ores, which are located in the Middle and Southern Timan, as well as in the Polar Urals. The Yareg and Pizhem titanium ore deposits are among the largest in Russia and the near abroad. Manganese ore reserves are represented by the Parnok iron-manganese deposit (Polar Urals).

Non-metallic minerals are represented by large industrial deposits of quartz raw materials, barite, rock salt, and numerous deposits of mineral construction materials. Deposits of brick clays and building stone are being developed, with deposits of construction sand and sand-gravel mixtures undergoing the most intensive exploitation.

The Komi Republic is one of the leading forestry-industrial regions of Russia and possesses the capacity to increase production volumes. The total forest area amounts to 36.3 million hectares, approximately 50% of the forested area in the European North of Russia, and 4% of the country's total forest area.

Structurally, forest industry production is represented by organizations involved in logging, wood processing, and pulp and paper industries. Forest industry activities are conducted by approximately 600 organizations employing over 13,000 people.

In 2024, the production index for wood processing and wood product manufacturing reached 95.1% relative to the corresponding level of 2023. Production volumes of particle board increased by 1.3%, and plywood by 4.3%.

The main flagship of the pulp and paper industry is the Syktyvkar Forestry Industrial Complex. JSC 'SFIC' is included in the federal list of strategically important enterprises, with a workforce exceeding

4.5 thousand employees. The company develops infrastructure for settlements and industry and is one of the largest taxpayers contributing to the revenue side of the regional budget. JSC 'SFIC' constitutes the foundation of the forestry industrial complex, uniting operations from logging and forest management to advanced wood processing.[1]

For the socio-economic development of any constituent entity of the Russian Federation, a significant factor is the state of the investment climate, which constitutes a set of conditions determining the attractiveness of investments in the economy and social sphere both at the national level and within a specific territory. These conditions include political stability, the legislative framework, and the economic and financial environment.

In the Komi Republic, the current state of the investment climate can be characterized as stagnant, with a slight tendency towards improvement. This situation is explained by a range of objective and subjective factors, including the change of regional leadership, shifts in strategic priorities both at the national and regional levels, as well as changes in economic and financial conditions resulting from events occurring in the country. A distinctive feature of the economic component of the investment climate in our republic is the dominant share of public investments in regional projects and the funding of national projects implemented within our territory.

It should be noted that one of the most significant socio-economic development programs of the region, shaping the investment climate, is the State Program of the Komi Republic 'Development of the Economy and Industry,' within which six objectives have been established:

Objective 1 — improving the strategic management of the Komi Republic's development.

Objective 2 — increasing the volume of investments in fixed capital from all sources of financing to 133,980.0 million rubles by 2030.

Goal 3 — to increase the satisfaction of residents of the Komi Republic with the quality of outbound and domestic tourism services to 39% by 2030.

Goal 4 — to establish a high-tech, competitive, sustainable, and balanced industry with corporate social responsibility.

Goal 5 — to enhance labor productivity, including in state and municipal organizations within the social sector.

Goal 6 — to develop and implement the scientific and innovative potential of the Komi Republic.

Goal 7 — Growth of income per employee in small and medium-sized enterprises within the region.

The total volume of financial resources, including federal budget funds, allocated for the implementation of this program in 2025 amounted to 1.8 billion rubles. (1.67 billion rubles were utilized in 2024).

Within the framework of the first goal, strategic management of regional development is based on a close interconnection between scientifically substantiated forecasting and flexible implementation mechanisms. Key instruments for the realization of strategic objectives are state programs, which translate strategic priorities into concrete projects, resources, and measurable outcomes.

Sanctions and geopolitical instability have significantly affected investments in leading industrial sectors, particularly in the manufacturing sector. Nevertheless, the republic maintained a certain level of employment and ensured growth in real incomes of the population (by 2020) as well as wages.

The primary priorities of the regional strategy remain unchanged: efforts continue to accelerate economic diversification, develop support institutions, and enhance the quality of human capital. These directions fully align with national objectives, including the provisions of the Decree of the President of Russia No. 309 dated May 7, 2024, concerning the country's national development goals.

The investment portfolio of projects in the Komi Republic comprises approximately 80 investment projects with a total investment volume of 900 billion rubles, with implementation timelines for certain projects extending until 2054, including projects in mineral extraction, manufacturing, tourism, the agro-industrial complex, energy, and other sectors. [4]

The Komi Republic is making every effort to attract private investment through the development of key economic sectors:

— Oil industry: development of oil fields and increase in extraction volumes, enhancement of its economic efficiency (Usinskoye, Yaregskoe, Vostochno-Lambeishorskoye fields, etc.).

— Timber processing sector: establishment of OSB panel production facilities, modernization of existing enterprises, and organization of production of high value-added products. [2]

In 2026, the launch of two significant projects is planned:

- the construction of a calcium carbide production plant in Inta (at a cost of 0.5 billion rubles);
- the modernization of the woodworking enterprise in Syktyvkar (at a cost of 4 billion rubles).

Under the directive of the Ministry of Economic Development of Russia, the republic has formulated an investment plan for 2025-2030, comprising 30 major projects with a total cost exceeding 300 million rubles, impacting the socio-economic development of the republic.

The largest and most significant investment project aimed at diversifying the economy of the single-industry town of Vorkuta is the “Creation of the Vorkuta Chemical Complex,” with an investment volume exceeding 200 billion rubles and the creation of approximately 1,500 jobs. [3]

To improve the investment climate in the Komi Republic concerning business conditions, systemic measures are being implemented to enhance the regulatory framework, ensure access to various forms of state support, develop infrastructure, and provide preferences for residents of the Arctic territory, such as tax incentives, concessional loans from the regional industrial development fund, the conclusion of a special investment contract (SPIC), the conclusion of an agreement on the protection and promotion of capital investments (APPCI), and the provision of land plots for lease without tender for the implementation of large-scale investment projects; federal mechanisms are also actively utilized (Arctic subsidies, infrastructure budget loans, treasury credits).

It can be assumed that the created conditions facilitate business development and the attraction of investments; however, at the initial stage of project launch, investors in northern territories face difficulties in securing credit funds as well as resources from regional and federal development institutions for the implementation of new investment projects.

Consequently, many enterprises reconsider the implementation of investment programs, postponing project implementation deadlines to a later period. Among the main factors that create additional challenges for potential investors and necessitate a comprehensive approach to addressing existing problems are:

- high interest rates on credit resources;
- disruptions in transport and logistics chains;
- increases in tariffs of natural monopolies (including Russian Railways tariffs), which negatively impact production costs and the company’s net profit;
- high logistics costs due to the region’s geographical remoteness from key sales markets;
- absence or closure of sales markets that the enterprise targeted when launching production lines;

— disruptions and suspensions of deliveries of raw materials, materials, spare parts, and components, as well as their significant price increases;

— difficulties with import substitution in a number of high-tech categories.

Currently, our region is among six pilot regions with which the Agency for Strategic Initiatives for Promoting New Projects will thoroughly develop measures aimed at improving target indicators, including by using effective practices from constituent entities of the Russian Federation.

In the forest processing industry, significant emphasis is placed on the implementation of four priority investment projects with a total volume of investments amounting to 11.3 billion rubles and plans to create 1,065 new jobs.

These projects include:

1) Modernization and expansion of production capacities of LLC ‘Luzales,’ with a planned investment volume exceeding 3 billion rubles;

2) Modernization and expansion of the infrastructure facilities of the Syktyvkar Sawing and Woodworking Plant;

3) “Modernization of the existing wood-processing production at LLC Promtekh-Invest for processing low-grade wood and manufacturing OSB boards in the Komi Republic,” with investments exceeding 2 billion rubles;

4) “Modernization of wood-processing production and organization of comprehensive wood processing with the manufacture of high value-added finished products at LLC Pechora Sever Les.” The planned investment volume is 2 billion rubles. [3]

By the end of 2025, companies will have invested 8 billion rubles, creating more than 370 new jobs with high wages.

Successful implementation of investment projects involves rational forest management, the creation of new jobs with safe working conditions and high wages, an increase in the revenue portion of the Komi Republic’s budget, as well as the establishment of new manufacturing facilities for producing high value-added wood products.

The current situation in the forestry sector, associated with the closure of the European market and external restrictions, has impacted the operations of enterprises investing in the creation and modernization of wood processing production facilities. Investors encountered difficulties in sourcing and supplying equipment equivalents produced in unfriendly countries.

These circumstances were the primary cause of the gradual delays in the implementation schedules of the investment projects of LLC ‘Luzales’ and LLC ‘Promtekh-invest’.

One of the key current issues in the forestry sector is the disruption of trade flows and the logistics of timber product distribution.

To address logistical challenges, the Ministry of Economic Development, Industry and Transport of the Komi Republic established the ‘Logistics Center,’

which facilitates the resolution of problems related to freight transportation for the republic's industrial enterprises.

Currently, issues are being addressed promptly in cooperation with the Operational Situation Center of the Ministry of Transport of the Russian Federation to ensure transport logistics. In 2025, 28 requests from enterprises for approval of freight transportation applications were processed.

Following the meeting of the Operational Headquarters for ensuring sustainable passenger and freight logistics, enterprises of the forestry complex were recommended to use alternative logistics routes through the Republic of Kazakhstan (Dostyk station) or the port of [city]. Saint Petersburg (Northern Sea Route).

Moreover, enterprises of the Timber Industry Complex of the Komi Republic have been included in the Unified Register of Shippers — producers of timber industry complex products, which ensures the priority of timber products on the railway.

At present, due to a shortage of operating cash flow caused by an increase in working capital (increased payment terms with buyers, extended logistics periods, payments by buyers upon product delivery, increased volume of goods in transit, changed payment terms in export contracts to post-payment) a difficult financial situation has developed in many enterprises of the timber industry complex.

Sustainable development of enterprises requires investments and additional resources, as well as the resolution of several social issues.

Key directions for the development of the Timber Industry Complex of the Komi Republic are as follows:

1. Investment development. The attraction of financial resources creates new opportunities for technological advancement of production and ensures stable growth of enterprises over the long term.

(For example, the Syktyvkar Timber Industry Complex plans to construct a fluff pulp production plant with a capacity of 60 thousand tons per year, with an investment volume of 3.4 billion rubles. An industrial park focused on the timber industry is being developed near Syktyvkar.)

2. Development of Wooden Housing Construction. Wooden housing construction in the Komi Republic has significant potential and will enable the activation of substantial domestic demand reserves for timber.

Within the framework of the regional development concept for wooden housing construction until 2030, certain enterprises are already constructing socio-cultural facilities; in Vorkuta, Kortkerossky, and Koygorodsky districts, houses are being built using prefabricated wooden housing kits for the purpose of resettlement from emergency and dilapidated housing; in Sysolsky, Priluzsky, and Izhemsky districts, houses are being constructed for medical personnel to attract staff to work in rural areas. A standard project has been developed for district forestry units.

3. Infrastructure development. The development of transport and production infrastructure, as well as changes in the logistics of finished product deliveries, will largely determine the prospects for export growth.

For the republic's forest industry, the project to construct a deep-water seaport in Arkhangelsk with the capability to transship containerized forest cargo is highly relevant. Collaboration with the Government of the Arkhangelsk Region will help ease the burden on the eastern route, modernize the existing railway, and leverage the opportunities offered by the new port. It should be noted that specialists in the field of strategic planning, engaged in adjusting the regional strategy, anticipate the resumption of the Northern Latitudinal Railway project, which will increase the utilization of the Northern Railway in the Komi Republic.

Therefore, it is critically important to continue and expand state support measures for priority projects aimed at stimulating investment activity and creating conditions for the sustainable development of the republic's forest industry complex. The prospects of the industry as a whole, as well as of each enterprise individually, will depend on the dynamism of ongoing changes and on the speed and timeliness of the decisions made.

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INDICATOR ANALYSIS AS A TOOL FOR ASSESSING RUSSIA'S INFORMATION AND ECONOMIC SECURITY IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract. *This article examines indicator analysis as a tool for a comprehensive assessment of the information and economic security of the state amid accelerated digital transformation of the economy and public administration. The authors demonstrate that traditional economic security monitoring systems, predominantly based on macroeconomic indicators, inadequately reflect digital and informational risks associated with cyber threats, vulnerability of digital infrastructure, and dependence on external ICT technologies. The existence of a methodological gap between systems of economic security indicators, digital transformation metrics, and cybersecurity indices is substantiated, complicating the formation of a holistic understanding of the state's information and economic security. A conceptual model of information and economic security and a system of indicators are proposed, integrating macroeconomic, digital, and information-technical indicators, including international cybersecurity indices and digital maturity measures. The methodological foundation utilizes indicator and index analysis, expert assessments (Delphi method), and cross-country benchmarking, enabling the development of an integrated index of information and economic security and facilitating cross-country comparisons. It is anticipated that the application of the proposed approach will improve the comprehensiveness and predictive capacity of the assessment, enhance the early warning function concerning threats, and provide a more justified basis for decision-making in the field of state policy on digital transformation and security assurance.*

Keywords: *indicator analysis, information and economic security, economic security, digital transformation, digital economy, cybersecurity, digital infrastructure, composite index, state and municipal governance*

The active digital transformation of public administration, the economy, and the social sphere is institutionalized in Russia at the level of the national project ‘Data Economy and Digital Transformation of the State,’ which sets goals for the digitalization of key management processes, the development of the data market, and digital infrastructure. According to monitoring data [1], by the end of 2025, the planned targets for several key indicators (data market maturity index, level of digital maturity across industries, etc.) will have been met or exceeded, indicating a rapid increase in the state’s dependence on digital technologies.

Studies on the impact of digital transformation on economic security reveal a dual effect: on one hand, digitalization fosters GDP growth, enhances productivity, and reduces transaction costs; On the other hand, it intensifies vulnerabilities related to cyber threats, dependence on external technologies, and risks of disruption to critical digital infrastructure. Certain studies highlight that information security is becoming a key component of the country’s economic security system and necessitates systematic consideration in strategic planning and monitoring [2]. In international practice, indices and rankings evaluating the cybersecurity status of countries are widely used, particularly the Global Cybersecurity Index (GCI) by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), which aggregates data across five areas: legal, technical, and organizational measures, capacity building, and international cooperation. In the latest GCI report, Russia is classified at the second level (‘progressing’), reflecting the existence of a developed regulatory and organizational framework, while challenges persist regarding technical measures and practical implementation // Global Cybersecurity Index 2024 [3].

Domestic studies in the field of economic security emphasize the increasing role of information technology as a factor in national economic security and propose indicator systems that account for the impact of IT on financial stability, innovative activity, international competitiveness, and information security. At the same time, it is emphasized that the statistical evaluation of actual digital economy security indicators under conditions of high uncertainty and rapid technological change remains a methodologically challenging task [4].

Against this background, there is an increasing need to develop indicator analysis as a tool for the comprehensive assessment of the state’s RIS — at the intersection of economic, informational, and institutional parameters — in the context of accelerated digital transformation.

Existing approaches to assessing the economic security of the state traditionally rely on an indicator-based approach employing a system of threshold values

of macroeconomic indicators (GDP growth rates, inflation levels, external debt, investment activity, etc.). This approach enables the identification of threats to the stability of the economic system but insufficiently reflects the specific risks of the digital economy: cyber threats, data leaks and distortions, dependence on foreign ICT solutions, shortages of digital competencies, and vulnerabilities of digital infrastructure [5]. Simultaneously, indicator systems for the digital economy and digital maturity (such as communication infrastructure, big data usage, the level of digitization of public services, the share of online transactions, etc.) are being developed; however, they are rarely integrated into the economic security indicator system and are generally used to assess the effectiveness of digital transformation rather than to diagnose security threats [1].

As a result, a methodological gap arises between:

- statistical and indicator systems for assessing economic security;
- metrics of digital transformation and data market development;
- indicators of cybersecurity and information protection.

The research problem lies in the absence of a comprehensive, formalized system of indicator analysis specifically designed to assess the information-economic security of the state as an integral condition that accounts for the impact of digital transformation.

In domestic literature, economic security of the state is understood as the ability of the national economy to resist internal and external threats, ensuring sustainable growth and competitiveness; within this framework, the following security subsystems are distinguished: macroeconomic, financial, investment, innovation, social, foreign economic, and others. Several authors emphasize the necessity of supplementing this structure with components related to the digital economy and information infrastructure [6]. Research on information security within the economic security system focuses on threats related to unauthorized data access, disruption of information system operations, cyberattacks on critical infrastructure, and informational influence capable of distorting economic decisions. It is noted that in most existing systems for monitoring economic security, the information component is presented fragmentarily and does not fully reflect digital risks [6].

Research focused on the economic security of organizations and enterprises in the context of digitalization demonstrates the necessity of integrating economic, information, and innovation security into a unified model aimed at proactive risk management. However, scaling these approaches to the state level requires adapting indicators, data sources, and aggregation methods [5].

The indicator-based approach to assessing economic security relies on a system of indicators and their threshold values, which define the boundaries of the safe functioning of the economy. Exceeding or not reaching thresholds is interpreted as a signal of emerging threats, while the aggregation of indicators allows for the

formation of integral indices that characterize the overall security level [7]. Contemporary studies propose multidimensional indicator systems that include the dimensions ‘Financial Stability and IT Sector Development,’ ‘Innovative Activity,’ ‘International Competitiveness,’ ‘Human Resources Potential,’ ‘Information Security,’ ‘Infrastructure and Access to Digital Services,’ and ‘E-Government and Digitalization of Public Services.’ This approach allows the use of index methods to build composite indicators, assess dynamics, and forecast the attainment of threshold values [8].

In international practice, indicator and index approaches are implemented in cybersecurity indices (GCI), where the state of national cybersecurity is aggregated from indicators across five key areas using score evaluations and weights. Similarly, statistical studies of the digital economy emphasize the role of statistical methods and indicators in assessing the security of the digital economy and the risks associated with digitalization [9].

Taking into account the specified approaches and gaps, the research question is formulated as follows: ‘How does the use of indicator analysis integrating economic, informational, and digital indicators affect the quality of assessing the state’s information and economic security in the context of digital transformation?’

Based on the reviewed literature, the following hypothesis is proposed: The integration into the indicator analysis system of a set of digital and informational indicators (level of digital infrastructure development, data market maturity, cybersecurity metrics, level of digital skills, degree of digitalization of public services), alongside traditional macroeconomic indicators, enhances the completeness, sensitivity, and predictive capacity of the assessment of the state’s information and economic security compared to systems predominantly based on macroeconomic indicators.

The study proposes employing a combination of three complementary methods.

1. Indicator and index analysis

Indicator and index analysis, including:

- selection of a system of indicators reflecting the economic, informational, and digital components of security (based on existing approaches to economic security, the digital economy, and cybersecurity);
- normalization of indicators (for example, scaling from 0 to 1, taking into account threshold values and target benchmarks);
- aggregation of indicators into sub-indices (economic, information-technical, institutional-legal, personnel-competence, etc.);
- calculation of the integral index of information and economic security (RIS) as a weighted sum of sub-indices.

This approach enables the quantitative assessment of the current state of RIS, the monitoring of dynamics, the identification of ‘weak links’ (sub-indices with

the poorest values), and the comparison of results with threshold values and target benchmarks.

2. Expert assessments and the Delphi method

The expert assessment method using a modified Delphi method can be applied to:

- determining the weights of indicators and subindices in the integrated assessment;
- refining threshold values and interpreting critical levels of indicators;
- validating the structure of the indicator system (the composition of groups and specific indicators).

Experience in applying expert surveys in research on the impact of digital transformation on economic security demonstrates their effectiveness in identifying the most significant factors (for example, infrastructure, integration into the global digital space, and the effectiveness of government policy in the fields of information security and the digital economy). Multi-round surveys enable reaching a consensus among expert groups and enhance the reliability of the adopted weights and thresholds [2].

3. Cross-country analysis (benchmarking)

Cross-country analysis (benchmarking), based on:

- comparison of key indicators and subindices of Russia's RIS with data from other countries for which comparable metrics are available;
- use of international indices (e.g., GCI) and open statistical data on the digital economy and economic security.itu+2

This analysis allows for:

- identifying the delays and advantages of Russia in specific areas (legal regulation, technical measures, capacity building, international cooperation, etc.);
- refining the target values of the RIS indicators based on the practices of leading countries;
- assessing the impact of various digital transformation models on the state of information and economic security.

Within the framework of the proposed methodology, the following results are expected.

1. Development of a conceptual model of the state's information and economic security as an integrated state encompassing interconnected economic, information-technical, institutional-legal, and personnel-competency components.

2. Formation of the RIS indicator system, incorporating both traditional macroeconomic indicators (growth stability, investment activity, financial stability) and digital transformation indicators (level of digital infrastructure development, data market maturity, digital maturity of public administration, cybersecurity indicators).

3. Construction of an integrated RIS index based on the index method, enabling monitoring, cross-country comparisons, and detection of risk dynamics.

4. Development of methodological recommendations for state and municipal authorities on the application of RIS indicator analysis in the formulation of digital transformation strategies, economic and information security programs, as well as in assessing the effectiveness of implemented measures.

5. Identification of key factors determining the state of RIS and early detection of risk areas (for example, underinvested digital infrastructure, low digital skills, weak law enforcement in information security), which should enhance the quality of management decisions.

An example of a system of indicators for the state’s information and economic security is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 — Example of a system of indicators for the state’s information and economic security

Indicator group	Examples of indicators	Possible data sources
Economic	GDP growth rate, inflation, investment in fixed capital, export of ICT services	Rosstat, Bank of Russia, international statistics
Digital infrastructure	Share of population with broadband access, mobile coverage, data centers	Roskomnadzor, industry reports, national project
Information Security	Scores and levels according to GCI, number of cyber incidents, share of protected resources	ITU reports, national centers
Electronic Government	Level of digitalization of public services, share of citizens’ online requests	Ministry of Digital Development, reports on digital maturity
Institutional and legal environment	Availability of fundamental laws and strategies in the field of IS and the digital economy, and their implementation	Regulatory legal acts, state programs
Personnel competency	Level of digital skills among the population, number of information security specialists per 100,000 employed	Educational statistics, surveys

Source: compiled by the authors

The proposed approach to indicator analysis of information and economic security builds upon and develops existing models of economic security indicator assessment but introduces closer integration with digital and informational indicators. Unlike traditional systems, where digital aspects are either absent or represented by isolated indicators, digital transformation is regarded here as a fundamental source of both opportunities and risks for security [7].

The inclusion of international cybersecurity indices (such as the GCI) and digital maturity metrics into the indicator system enables the comparison of national results with global trends, as well as the adjustment of threshold values in accordance with the practices of leading countries. At the same time, it is important to consider the limitations of these indices (data lag, methodological discrepancies, incomplete representation of the actual security level); therefore, they should be used in conjunction with national statistical and administrative data.

From the standpoint of state and municipal governance, indicator analysis of RIS can serve as:

- a tool for early warning (early diagnosis of emerging threats);
- a mechanism for prioritizing state policy measures (identifying areas where indicator deviations from threshold values are greatest);
- a basis for assessing the effectiveness of implemented digital transformation and security assurance programs.

At the same time, the implementation of this approach encounters several limitations:

- incompleteness and heterogeneity of data, especially in terms of cyber incident statistics and the assessment of system security levels;
- the risk of ‘formalization’ of policy, where achieving target indicator values replaces the real enhancement of security;
- the necessity of regularly updating the set of indicators in light of emerging technologies and threats.

In the national security hierarchy, information and economic security can be represented as a subsystem located at the intersection of:

- economic security (stability and development of the economy);
- information security (protection of information and infrastructure);
- digital development (digital infrastructure, data, digital services).

This positioning underscores the necessity for interagency cooperation and policy coordination in the areas of economic development, digital transformation, and information security.

The analysis showed that, in the context of accelerated digital transformation, traditional approaches to assessing the state’s economic security insufficiently capture the specific risks related to the information sphere and digital infrastructure. At the same time, existing indicator systems for the digital economy and cybersecurity are generally not integrated into the overall economic security monitoring system. A research question aimed at evaluating the impact of indicator analysis on the quality of information and economic security assessment has been proposed, and a hypothesis formulated that integrating digital and information indicators with traditional macroeconomic metrics enhances both the comprehensiveness and predictive qualities of the assessment. A methodological research

framework has been developed, encompassing indicator and index analysis, expert assessments, and cross-national benchmarking. The practical implementation of the proposed approach is expected to:

- enhance the justification of decisions in the field of state policy on digital transformation and security assurance;
- strengthen the early warning function regarding emerging RIS threats;
- ensure the comparability of Russia's results with international practices and best global standards.

Further research should focus on the empirical validation of the proposed hypothesis using specific data sets, the development of software tools for calculating the RIS index, and testing various weighting schemes and threshold values.

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PARTNERSHIP RELATIONS OF COMMERCIAL BANKS: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND TARGET ORIENTATION

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Abstract. *The article examines the theoretical aspects of forming partnership relations of a commercial bank in the context of the digital transformation of the financial market; the conceptual apparatus used in describing the bank's interaction with counterparties is clarified. Based on etymological and terminological analysis, the categories of 'business partner,' 'partnership ties,' and 'partnership relations' are distinguished, and authorial definitions of these concepts are proposed with reference to the banking sector. Specific characteristics of partnership relations in banking activities have been identified, determined by a high level of regulatory oversight, the significance of reputational components, and the critical role of banking infrastructure. The target orientation of building partnership ties is revealed, encompassing market, product, financial, technological, and ecosystem aspects. It is concluded that partnership ties have transformed from an auxiliary sales tool into a strategic resource for creating the bank's long-term competitive advantages.*

Keywords: *bank, banking ecosystem, business partner, commercial bank, partnership relations, partnership ties, conceptual framework, partnership objectives.*

The current stage of development of the banking system is characterized by a fundamental transformation of the interaction models between credit institutions and clients and counterparties. In the context of the digitalization of the economy, increased competition from fintech companies, and changes in consumer behavior, the classical understanding of the bank solely as a financial intermediary is giving way to a broader concept: the bank as a platform integrated into the client's daily life.

Commercial banks are increasingly moving away from the model of a closed financial organization aiming to independently meet the widest possible range of client needs. This is being replaced by the paradigm of open architecture, which involves active interaction with diverse counterparties – from insurance companies and investment intermediaries to IT developers and retail enterprises.

The theoretical comprehension of the phenomenon of partnership relations has a solid scientific tradition and is reflected in the works of numerous researchers. such as: Aaker D., Ambler T., Antipina E., Arkhipova O., Bos N., Bono E., Braert E., Buznya A., Wulf V., Doyle P., Drucker P., Zelinsky A., Zernova L., Inshakova O., Korobkina Yu., Kotler F., Koshurnikova Yu., Lambin J., Levitt T., Morozova N., Neal R., Olson G., Omelchenko M., Rubtsova N., Ruglova V., Ruglova L., Semiryaga M., Smorodinskaya N., Tikhomirova O., Hansen M., Yakunaeva S., et al.

The key role in this paradigm is played by partnership ties [1, p. 47], which cease to be a peripheral marketing tool and become one of the main mechanisms for expanding the client base, increasing commission income, and enhancing competitiveness. It is natural that the phenomenon of partnership ties in the banking sector attracts increasing attention from researchers: whereas initially this issue was developed primarily in the context of marketing communications, there is now a clear trend towards rethinking the role and position of partnerships within the structure of banking business.

It should be noted that within the existing research tradition, several approaches have been developed for understanding the partnership relations of a commercial bank. Within the institutional approach, partnerships are regarded as a hybrid form of coordination of economic activity, enabling the reduction of transaction costs and the compensation of market mechanism imperfections. The resource-based approach emphasizes the opportunity to access the unique competences and assets of a counterparty, which constitutes the basis for achieving a synergistic effect. The ecosystem approach, which has evolved in recent years, interprets partnership ties as the foundation for constructing integrated platforms that unite financial and non-financial services. At the same time, each of these approaches illuminates only certain facets of the phenomenon under study, while its comprehensive theoretical model remains insufficiently developed.

This transformation inevitably poses a number of questions for the scientific community regarding the nature of the emerging relationships between banks and counterparties, their typological characteristics, as well as the functional roles they perform in the modern banking system. The need for such conceptualization is driven not only by the logic of economic theory development but also by the demands of banking practice, which encounters diverse forms of partnership interaction and the necessity to establish criteria for assessing their effectiveness and strategic importance.

Before proceeding directly to the analysis of partnership relations, it is necessary to make a terminological clarification concerning the key subject of the study. The term ‘bank’ denotes a commercial bank as a special type of credit institution possessing the exclusive right to perform, collectively, the banking operations prescribed by current legislation (attracting monetary funds from individuals and legal entities as deposits, placing these funds on its own behalf and at its own risk, opening and maintaining bank accounts)[2]. It is important to emphasize that the primary object of consideration is predominantly universal commercial banks focused on serving a broad range of clients – both individuals and legal entities. This particular category of banks is most extensively involved in the processes of building partnership ecosystems and developing interorganizational interactions, whereas specialized credit institutions may exhibit a different model of partnership relations, shaped by their narrow functional specialization.

One of the significant factors ensuring the growth of a bank’s competitiveness, expansion of its market presence, and improvement of financial performance is the formation of a stable system of partnership relations with entities involved in the activities of the credit institution. The very nature of a bank as a financial intermediary implies its multiple partnership identity: on the one hand, it acts as a business partner for its own clients, maintaining long-term relationships through account management and transaction execution; on the other hand, it is an element of the centralized financial system, entering into transactions with other participants of that system [3, p.21].

The etymology of the term ‘partner’ dates back to the mid-19th century, when this term was predominantly used to denote a participant in a dance, game, or theatrical performance. In the second half of the 20th century, under the influence of increasingly complex economic relations, it undergoes economization: expressions such as ‘business partner,’ ‘trade partner,’ and ‘partner in joint activity’ firmly enter the lexicon. In relation to the banking sphere, in our view, the category of business partner assumes key significance, encapsulating the specifics of economic relations formed between a credit institution and other entities.

A review of contemporary economic literature reveals multiple interpretations of the concept of a “business partner.”

GOST R 53662-2015: Supply Chain Security Management System. Best practices for ensuring supply chain security clarify the essence of the concept of a “business partner” as a contractor or supplier with whom the organization concludes a contract to assist in fulfilling its role as an entity participating in the supply chain[4].

G. Borisov defines a “business partner” as a person who is a co-owner of the company or occupies a senior position, possessing significant influence over its activities[5].

L. Zernova defines the term «business partner» as an entrepreneur (company) with whom another organization initiates a certain alliance or has concluded a

cooperation agreement, the relations of which are formalized by a contract specifying specific rules or standards of conduct for the parties [3, p.21].

The definitions encountered differ in terms of completeness, emphasis on organizational-legal form, the nature of relationships, and the documentation of the interaction. Summarizing existing approaches, key characteristics present in most definitions can be identified: the presence of two or more entities (legal or natural persons); entering into business relationships that imply mutual interest; legal formalization of relations through a contract or agreement; focus on achieving commercial objectives.

At the same time, the analysis shows that a universal definition fully accounting for the specifics of banking activities is absent in the literature. Many interpretations tend either toward excessive generality, which obscures sector-specific characteristics, or, conversely, narrow the concept to one of its potential roles. This necessitates clarifying the category of ‘business partner’ as applied to the commercial bank, taking into account the diversity of its interaction forms with counterparties.

In our view, a business partner of a commercial bank should be understood as a legal or natural person entering into contractual economic relations with the bank that are long-term, based on mutual benefit, and aimed at achieving common or related commercial objectives. Partners of the bank may include clients (both existing and prospective), suppliers of goods and services, contractors, financial intermediaries, other credit institutions, as well as technology companies that ensure service integration. A fundamental characteristic of partnership relations in the banking sector is their complexity: the same entity can simultaneously fulfill multiple roles (for example, a bank client who is also an IT service provider), which generates a multiplicity of connections and strengthens their stability.

If the category ‘business partner’ identifies the subject composition of interaction, then the concepts of ‘partnership ties’ and ‘partnership relations’ allow for revealing the substantive aspect of this phenomenon and the nature of interdependencies arising between the subjects. These terms are often used as synonyms; however, in our view, there is a certain semantic distinction between them that is important for understanding the nature of the phenomenon under study.

Partnership ties of a commercial bank should be understood as a set of stable interactions between the bank and counterparties, mediated by the flow of resources (financial, informational, technological, client-related) and ensuring the implementation of banking products and services, as well as access to new markets and competencies. Partnership ties constitute a structural framework, a network of communications and contracts connecting the bank with other economic entities. They may vary in density, intensity, duration, and formalization, but in any case constitute the immediate external environment in which the bank operates.

Partnership relations constitute a broader and more substantively enriched category. While connections record the mere existence of interaction and its channels,

relations imply a specific quality of this interaction, developed over time and encompassing a value-normative component. Partnership relations of a commercial bank constitute a historically developed system of mutual expectations, obligations, and behavioral patterns that regulate the interaction of the bank with counterparties based on the principles of trust, mutual benefit, and long-term orientation. Unlike one-time transactions, partnership relations are characterized by the accumulation of so-called relational capital – a non-material asset arising during joint activities that enables the reduction of transaction costs, minimizes risks of opportunistic behavior by partners, and creates additional value for the participants.

Within the structure of partnership relations of a commercial bank, several levels can be distinguished (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Levels of partnership relations of a commercial bank

The levels of partnership relations of a commercial bank include:

- economic, encompassing resource exchange and income distribution from joint activities;
- organizational, including mechanisms for coordination, decision-making alignment, and conflict resolution;
- social-psychological, pertaining to the formation of interpersonal trust, business reputation, and informal norms of interaction between representatives of the bank and partner organizations;
- institutional, reflecting the impact of the external environment on the nature of developing relationships.

It is important to emphasize that partnership relations in the banking sector possess certain specific characteristics that differentiate them from interorganizational interactions in other industries:

- a high level of regulatory supervision imposes restrictions on forms of cooperation and requires compliance with stringent requirements for information protection and anti-money laundering measures;
- the reputational component acquires particular importance: the bank is accountable to its clients for the actions of its partners, which entails heightened demands for their selection and monitoring;
- the critical role of banking infrastructure in the economy renders issues of reliability and continuity of partnership interactions a matter of close scrutiny not only by the management of credit institutions but also by regulatory authorities.

Partnership ties and partnership relations correspond to form and content, as well as to the structural and procedural aspects of a commercial bank's interaction with counterparties. The formation of an effective system of partnership ties implies not only the quantitative expansion of the counterparty network but also the qualitative deepening of relations with the most significant counterparties, shifting interactions from situational transactions to the realm of long-term strategic partnership based on mutual trust and resource integration.

The identification of essential characteristics of partnership relations inevitably leads to the question of their target orientation in formation. In the broadest sense, the goal of establishing partnership relations of a commercial bank can be defined as the creation of a stable configuration of interaction with counterparties that provides a synergistic effect unattainable through autonomous functioning [6, p. 783]. The decomposition of this key goal allows for the distinction of several interrelated target objectives that specify the bank's motivation when entering into partnership relations.

From the perspective of market strategy, the primary objective is to expand the client base and penetrate new market segments. Partnerships with companies that already have a loyal audience enable the bank to overcome entry barriers to saturated markets and attract clients at lower marketing costs compared to traditional promotion channels [7]. Simultaneously, the objective of increasing the frequency and volume of banking service consumption by existing clients is achieved through their integration into a broader ecosystem of partner services.

From the perspective of product strategy, establishing partnership relations aims to enrich the product line without the need to develop proprietary competencies in non-financial sectors. The bank gains the opportunity to offer clients comprehensive solutions that include both banking and related services, thereby increasing the value of the bank's offering in the eyes of the consumer.

From a financial perspective, the objectives of partnership interactions are associated with diversifying income sources and optimizing costs. Commission fees for client acquisition to partners, participation in profit distribution from joint products, and savings on investments in non-core assets – all these form the financial

basis of partnership relations. Equally significant is the technological component: through partnerships, the bank gains access to modern technological solutions and digital platforms developed by specialized companies, enabling it to accelerate the market launch of new products and reduce costs associated with in-house development [1, p.57].

In the long term, building an extensive network of partnership ties contributes to achieving the strategic goal of forming a banking ecosystem – creating a sustainable community of interconnected services around the bank, enhancing client loyalty and establishing additional barriers to their switching to competitors.

Thus, the partnership ties of a commercial bank, in our opinion, represent a complex phenomenon, the essence of which transforms under the influence of digitalization. Whereas partnerships were previously regarded as an auxiliary marketing tool, under current conditions they acquire strategic significance, becoming the foundation for the formation of banking ecosystems.

Further research may focus on classifying types of partnerships, systematizing their functions, and empirically evaluating the effectiveness of various partnership models.

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THE FUNCTIONAL STRUCTURE OF CLUSTER RELATIONS IN AGRO-INDUSTRIAL REGIONS (USING THE EXAMPLE OF A COTTON CLUSTER)

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Annotation. *This article presents the functional structure of cluster relations in agro-industrial regions, taking into account the specific features of the cotton cluster in the region. It was also noted that regional clustering is one of the most important ways to increase the competitiveness of the national economy in modern conditions.*

In the course of globalization, the development of the agro-industrial complex plays an important role in shaping the integration process in the economy of the Republic of Tajikistan. The article discusses the possibilities of formation, methods and barriers to the formation of a cotton cluster in the studied area.

Keywords: *economic relations, agro-industrial sectors, digital economy, functional structure, agro-industrial complex, integration relations, economic efficiency, development of agro-industrial sectors, cluster formation, production, supply, storage and marketing.*

The development of the agro-industrial complex and the formation of the process of cooperation and integration continue in the direction of globalization, and the economy of the Republic of Tajikistan benefits from this process. This process has played a special role in the formation of agro-industrial clusters, in particular, cotton clusters in the regions, and has not lost its application from a methodological and stylistic point of view. Cotton clustering in the region does not contradict the goals and objectives of integration and cooperation, but collectively contributes to the development of entrepreneurship in the agro-industrial system.

Regardless of the process of forming cotton clusters in the agro-industrial complex, it goes through complex and lengthy stages, but all the problems in the context of the organization of agricultural production, technological and innovation chains are considered very acutely. It is important and will serve the socio-economic

situation of the country's regions in the near future. At the same time, domestic experience does not have a single point of view on the mechanism, principles and functions of cotton clusters. The concept of the formation of cotton clusters in the regions of the Republic of Tajikistan shows that the main basis for the development of cotton clusters is the collective method of activity of the agro-industrial complex, ensuring the efficient use of natural resources and the competitiveness of products. domestic goods and products in the country's regions. [8]

In modern conditions in the field of agriculture and other areas of the agro-industrial system, these clusters do not function properly. An analysis and study of the cotton clustering process in the regions of the republic shows that an attempt to form these clusters on the basis of Soviet-era agro-industrial enterprises without using the experience of economically developed countries and the global economic system, in particular, from a scientifically sound point of view, does not give the desired results. Hence, there is an objective need for the collective development of the agro-industrial complex based on clusterization, including the cotton cluster, ensuring the competitiveness of its participants and the efficient use of economic resources.

There are different views of domestic and foreign scientists on the theoretical and methodological aspects of the formation of agro-industrial cotton clusters. Some of them are of the opinion that "... there are two options for the operation of cotton clusters. First, it is the organization of cotton clusters "from above", initiated by the state, the government and state and local authorities, and the organization of participants in these clusters "from below". Another part of the scientists is of the opinion that "... the organization of agro-industrial cotton clusters will give the desired results when integration begins from below, and its participants unite independently to increase the competitiveness of domestic products and solve the issues of cluster formation ...". From this point of view, the sectoral organization of cotton-growing clusters of the agro-industrial system provides ample opportunities to ensure the effective use of the region's potential., and its development in modern conditions should naturally accelerate. [6]

According to Tereshin E. N., "...in conditions of not very good development of the agro-industrial complex and trust between subjects of the agri-food market, the formation of cotton clusters requires a priority role of coordination with local government agencies, greater efficiency in the formation of cotton clusters through the efforts of the state and the support of the state "from above" will be brought ...". Or: "... using their capabilities, these clusters can transfer new knowledge, scientific discoveries and inventions, as well as quickly and effectively adapt them to innovations demanded by the market...". This, in turn, requires science and practice to solve a number of new tasks for the further development of agriculture, especially the agricultural sector. [7]

It is important to note that cotton clusters ensure the integration of economic activity and the competitiveness of regional, international and regional markets, and also consider the study of methodological aspects, principles and special functions of their functioning necessary for the development of the country's regions. . Therefore, "... the formation and development of the cotton industry as a system of economic relations in the agricultural sector is a complex and lengthy process and its application to the state of the material possibilities of society, the development of industrial infrastructure." and the cotton market, as well as the availability of special laws for its development, state regulation and the development of the regional market depends on ..." [5]

From a scientific and practical point of view, the formation and development of cotton clusters in the agro-industrial system also requires the mental (psychological) state of its participants, mutual trust, cultural development and the level of financial literacy. These factors contribute to the centralization of the resource and natural potential of the region and the development of agro-industrial enterprises and mutual relations of participants, and attract more investments into the country's economy.

The cotton cluster plays a central role for the region's economy, promotes the development of domestic markets and the emergence of new participants in its chain, and ensures the pricing and abundance of the region's agri-food market. Taking into account the cluster approach in the development of agriculture has a number of advantages and is very important for local and regional governments and business development and the participants of these clusters. [9]

Thus, according to the functional structure, there are three groups or types of cotton clusters.:

- a regional structure with the dynamics of the economy of its branches, stimulating the involvement of more scientific institutions (research, universities and institutes, etc.);

- the production chain of vertical integration, which plays a major role in the production process (supplier, manufacturer, seller and consumer), that is, the circulation of goods and products;

- an industry with a high level of integration (for example, agro-industrial cotton clusters), in which the integration of industries and a very high level of activity is achieved.

Over time, cotton clusters will attract more foreign capital, large investments and efficient production management, increase the number of taxpayers and a special tax base, increase new jobs, create good funds for joint business and lead to further restructuring of the country's economy. area. Agriculture and large companies are the central elements of the cotton cluster, and healthy competition is maintained between them, which differs significantly from cartels or financial and industrial groups. The system of organization of competitiveness of enterprises and organizations of the agro-industrial system attracts more and more producers, suppliers

and buyers for the organization of specialization of production, cooperation and integration. [4]

The organization of cotton clusters promotes a special form of development of agro-industrial innovations, new innovative products and the use of modern technologies are also observed, which is aimed at further mastering new knowledge and new goods and products of the agro-industrial complex. the food market. It is thanks to the initiative of the mutual relations of the participants of the cotton cluster that they produce and implement effective new innovative developments, high-quality products that meet market requirements. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account, first of all, several main factors, namely the state policy in the regions of the country on the formation of cotton clusters and the development of agro-industrial sectors, as well as emergency situations that, for various reasons, the company's management is unable to manage its management, etc.[3]

In general, cotton clusters act as a new organizational and economic object in the agro-industrial complex, the ultimate goal of which is to ensure the competitiveness of the economy, the region or its individual industries. Here, "... the goal of cluster policy is to improve the quality of socio-economic development of the region by creating favorable conditions for the competitiveness of economic entities forming cotton clusters in the region ...". Supporting its development in the region by reducing production costs, providing financial support and access to the regional market, increasing investment attraction, and forming and developing market infrastructure are important parts of cluster policy in the regions. [2]

Along with political, financial and economic institutions, ensuring effective macroeconomic policy is also considered an important factor in the formation of agro-industrial cotton clusters in the region, which contributes to the formation of a regional end product at the microeconomic level. At the same time, "... the effectiveness of clustering at the meso-level in agriculture and the cotton processing industry, achieved as a result of vertical integration, eliminates sectoral and technological innovation barriers between them ...". It also depends on the ability of enterprises and organizations in the process of organizing goods and services, stable demand, and effective use of advanced production, distribution, and consumption methods.

At the same time, cluster policy is an important tool for the development of the national and regional economy, the process of local entrepreneurship and the environment of small and medium-sized businesses, the potential of companies and the professionalism of employees. effective production management, the development of market infrastructure, the participation of research institutions, suppliers ensures raw materials and fair competition for its participants.

The formation of cotton clusters in regional conditions depends on a number of factors and conditions, the most important of which are: geographical integration and the relationship of its participants, the size and share of small and medium-sized

businesses, competition between cluster participants in regional markets and the development of agricultural industries, etc. In addition, "... public authorities play an important role in the implementation of clusterization policy and play an important role in improving regional and national competitiveness as a priority area of public policy ...". Cluster policy is the quality of support for the integration process and the effective functioning of its participants, the quality of initiative and creativity in the activities of agricultural and agro-industrial enterprises. [1]

As the experience of regional economic development shows, the most effective economic system is one that ensures pure competition among domestic producers. The effect of competition in these cases is due to "... direct competition between companies and the distribution of profits between them, competing with each other, ambitions and the desire to take an active position in their localities make it possible to ensure a strategy of passing each other ...". At the same time, competition between the participants of the cotton cluster is considered one of the important elements of the clustering concept and distinguishes the cluster from other forms of development of the agro-industrial system, such as cooperation and integration, which contributes to increasing the competitiveness of the country's regions as a whole.

Interdependence and competition in cotton clusters are conducted in several directions. The internal competition of clusters contributes to the development and improvement of production efficiency, motivation of its participants, improvement and search for new ways of innovative development, territorial and geographical convergence, and also contributes to ensuring fair competition of enterprises and organizations of the agro-industrial complex. industrial clusters. Industrial competition in these clusters is a necessary and obligatory condition that helps not only to acquire the end user, but also to attract more resources, political and public support.

The methods of government intervention in the development of the region's economy, which is traditionally caused by the failure of market mechanisms (in particular, the social situation and the unfavorable environmental situation due to the impact of the financial and economic crisis), are based on the failures of the state. These and other factors will not affect the formation and further development of cotton clusters in the regions of the republic.

Thus, cluster policy is a mixed form of economic policy of the state, consisting of the integration of industrial and agrarian policies, regional policies, policies to support business development, attracting more domestic and external capital, innovation, scientific, technical, educational policies and policies. for the effective activities of its participants and aimed at the sustainable development of the region. Local government agencies take a special position on the development of clusterization, considering government policy mandatory for the formation and development of cotton clusters, as well as assessing the development of market infrastructure in the activities of these clusters as an important factor in the competitiveness of domestic production. goods and economic incentives.

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RUSSIA'S ENERGY DIPLOMACY: THE CHALLENGES OF GLOBAL LEADERSHIP IN NUCLEAR PROJECTS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the development of Russia's energy diplomacy in the nuclear energy sector as a key instrument of its foreign energy policy. It demonstrates that, unlike hydrocarbon-based industries, nuclear energy fosters long-term institutional ties based on intergovernmental agreements, export financing, and participation in the full life cycle of nuclear facilities. The article examines the geography and mechanisms for implementing Russia's international nuclear projects, as well as the specifics of a model that combines technological leadership and government support. Particular attention is paid to the limitations and transformation of Russia's nuclear energy diplomacy in the face of sanctions pressure and increased international competition in the nuclear technology market. It concludes that nuclear energy retains its strategic importance for Russia's foreign energy presence, while the financial and institutional risks associated with this model are simultaneously increasing.*

Keywords: *energy diplomacy; nuclear energy; foreign energy policy; Rosatom; nuclear technology; international energy projects; sanctions.*

The world of Trumpism accelerates the transformation of the global energy sector and leads to intensified competition for technological and infrastructural leadership, where nuclear energy retains particular significance as an instrument of long-term foreign economic and foreign policy influence. Unlike hydrocarbon markets, nuclear energy is characterized by high capital intensity, prolonged

investment cycles, and a strong linkage to state institutions, making it a domain of strategic energy diplomacy.

For Russia, nuclear energy has become one of the key directions of foreign economic activity, within which a stable system of international relations is formed, going beyond the mere trade of technologies and services. The implementation of overseas nuclear projects entails a long-term presence that includes construction, financing, fuel supply, maintenance services, and spent nuclear fuel management. This turns nuclear energy into a comprehensive instrument of energy diplomacy, combining economic, technological, and political components.

The relevance of this research is determined by the fact that, under conditions of sanctions pressure and fragmentation of global markets, nuclear energy remains one of the few sectors in which Russia maintains a systemic international presence. Simultaneously, the development of nuclear energy diplomacy is accompanied both by the expansion of project geography and by the growth of institutional and financial risks.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the development of Russia's energy diplomacy in nuclear energy, to identify the main instruments of its implementation, and to assess the structural constraints of this direction in foreign energy policy.

Nuclear energy as a specific instrument of Russia's energy diplomacy

Unlike traditional forms of energy diplomacy based on hydrocarbon exports, nuclear energy entails a fundamentally different model of interaction between the supplier state and the partner country. Nuclear projects establish long-term institutional ties that endure for several decades and encompass not only economic but also regulatory, technological, and personnel domains.

The key actor of Russian energy diplomacy in the nuclear sector is the state corporation Rosatom, which consolidates the functions of technology developer, contractor, fuel supplier, and operator throughout the life cycle of nuclear power plants. According to data from the state corporation, as of 2023, Russia was involved in the construction of 34 power units abroad across 10 countries, accounting for approximately 40% of the global nuclear power plant construction market [1]. This indicator significantly surpasses the positions of other leading actors in the nuclear market.

A distinctive feature of the Russian model is the active utilization of intergovernmental agreements, which formalize the terms of cooperation at the state level and mitigate commercial and political risks. Within the framework of such agreements, Russia generally offers partner countries a comprehensive package encompassing design, construction, financing, and nuclear fuel supplies. This enhances the receiving party's dependence on Russian technological and institutional support.

A key element of Russia's energy diplomacy in the nuclear sphere is the financial component. In several projects, the BOO (build–own–operate) model is employed, which entails retaining ownership of the facility by the Russian party or providing

state export credits. According to the International Energy Agency's estimates, the volume of Russian state financing for overseas nuclear projects from 2010 to 2020 exceeded 70 billion US dollars [2]. This allows Russia to compete in the markets of developing countries, where access to capital remains limited.

Thus, nuclear energy constitutes a distinct form of Russia's energy diplomacy, based not on short-term resource deliveries but on long-term institutional presence. However, this model simultaneously amplifies the strategic impact and increases vulnerability to external restrictions, necessitating a dedicated analysis of its sustainability in the current international context.

Geography and Mechanisms for the Implementation of Russia's Energy Diplomacy in the Nuclear Sphere

The development of Russia's energy diplomacy in nuclear energy is characterized by a distinct geographical differentiation and the use of a unified set of institutional and financial mechanisms. Unlike hydrocarbon exports, which are primarily focused on existing markets, Russia's nuclear energy diplomacy aims to establish new long-term partnerships, primarily in countries with increasing electricity demand and limited capacity for independent development of nuclear technologies.

The key regions for the implementation of Russian nuclear projects are Eastern Europe, the Middle East, South Asia, and Africa. In Eastern Europe, the most indicative example is Hungary, where the Paks-2 NPP project is being implemented on the basis of an intergovernmental agreement and envisages the construction of two VVER-1200 power units with a total capacity of 2400 MW. The financing of the project is predominantly secured through a Russian state loan amounting to up to 10 billion euros, covering approximately 80% of the construction costs [3]. This format of cooperation exemplifies the utilization of nuclear energy as a tool for deepening bilateral relations within the EU framework.

In the Middle East, the Akkuyu NPP project in Turkey occupies a central position — the world's first large-scale nuclear facility implemented under the BOO model. Russia not only constructs the plant but also retains control over its operation, thereby ensuring a long-term presence in the country's energy sector. The total cost of the project is estimated at 20-22 billion USD. The United States, and its operational lifespan is no less than 60 years [4]. In this case, atomic energy diplomacy goes beyond economic interaction and acquires a strategic dimension.

In South Asia, cooperation with India remains a key area, where Russia participates in the construction of the Kudankulam NPP. As of 2023, four power units have been commissioned, with two more under construction. Russia maintains its status as a key technological partner of India in the nuclear sector, providing not only construction but also fuel supply and maintenance services [1]. This enables the maintenance of stable relations even amid India's multi-vector foreign policy.

Africa holds a special place in the geography of Russian nuclear diplomacy. Projects in Egypt (El Dabaa NPP) and preliminary agreements with several other countries in the region reflect Russia's aspiration to secure a position in promising energy markets. The El-Dabaa project envisages the construction of four VVER-1200 power units with a total capacity of 4800 MW and is financed by a Russian loan of up to 25 billion USD [5]. For the host country, this format lowers financial barriers to entry into nuclear energy, while for Russia, it ensures long-term institutional presence.

From the standpoint of the mechanisms for implementing Russia's energy diplomacy in the nuclear sector, several stable components can be identified. Firstly, it relies on intergovernmental agreements that establish cooperation parameters for decades ahead and minimize the risks of unilateral contract revisions. Secondly, the utilization of export financing and state guarantees, enabling compensation for the high capital intensity of nuclear projects. Thirdly, the provision of comprehensive life-cycle services — from design to spent nuclear fuel management — which strengthens partners' technological dependence.

According to the World Nuclear Association, Russia remains the world leader in the number of simultaneously implemented foreign nuclear projects, surpassing France, the United States, and China [6]. This confirms that nuclear energy is among the most institutionally established areas of Russia's energy diplomacy.

At the same time, the high concentration of projects in specific regions and reliance on state financing increase the vulnerability of this model to external constraints. The long-term nature of nuclear contracts renders Russia's energy diplomacy in this domain both a source of strategic influence and a factor contributing to risk accumulation, thereby requiring an analysis of its resilience amidst evolving international conditions.

Constraints and Transformation of Russia's Energy Diplomacy in Nuclear Power under Sanctions and Heightened Competition

Since the late 2010s, the development of Russia's energy diplomacy in nuclear power has occurred under mounting external constraints related to sanctions pressure, the transformation of global supply chains, and intensified competition in the international nuclear technology market. These factors substantially adjust both the tools and the geographical priorities of Russian nuclear policy, without diminishing its strategic significance.

Sanction pressure has exerted an ambiguous impact on the Russian nuclear industry. On the one hand, nuclear energy has been affected by direct restrictions to a lesser degree than the hydrocarbon sector. As of 2023-2024, nuclear fuel supplies, uranium enrichment services, and the operation of reactors of Russian design have continued, including to countries in the EU. Thus, Russia's share in the global uranium enrichment services market is estimated at approximately 35-40%, while

in the supply of nuclear fuel for VVER reactors it is significantly higher [6]. This preserves Russia's structurally strong positions in international nuclear energy.

Conversely, sanctions risks have intensified the financial and institutional burdens on foreign nuclear projects. Restrictions on access to Western financial markets increase the role of state funding and export credits, thereby raising budgetary costs and extending project payback periods. Given the high capital intensity of nuclear energy, this circumstance increases the vulnerability of the energy diplomacy model based on long-term lending to foreign partners.

An additional factor in the transformation of Russian nuclear diplomacy is the increasing competition from alternative suppliers of nuclear technologies. China actively promotes its own reactor technologies, offering more flexible financial terms and leveraging the scale of its domestic market. France and South Korea concentrate on projects in countries with high institutional stability, relying on political support from allies. As a result, the nuclear energy market is gradually fragmenting, and competition is acquiring not only a technological but also a geopolitical dimension [1;7].

Under these conditions, the geography of Russian nuclear energy diplomacy is increasingly shifting towards countries focused on pragmatic economic cooperation and willing to enter into long-term interstate agreements. Projects in Turkey, Egypt, India, and several countries in Asia and Africa demonstrate that the Russian model remains in demand where priority is given to energy security and access to financing rather than political conditions. Simultaneously, opportunities to expand presence in countries highly dependent on Western regulatory and financial institutions are diminishing. [8]

A key direction in the adaptation of Russia's energy diplomacy in the nuclear sphere is the emphasis on technological autonomy and the development of a closed fuel cycle. The promotion of fast reactors and spent nuclear fuel reprocessing technologies allows Russia to position itself not only as a supplier of power units but also as a participant in shaping the long-term architecture of nuclear energy. This reinforces the strategic dimension of nuclear diplomacy and partially offsets external constraints.[9]

Thus, Russia's energy diplomacy in nuclear energy is entering a phase of structural transformation. While maintaining a high degree of international presence, it becomes more geographically selective, more financially costly, and more sensitive to geopolitical changes. [10]

In these circumstances, nuclear energy continues to be one of the key instruments of Russia's foreign energy policy; however, its application requires adaptation to new conditions of global competition and sanction pressure.

Conclusion

The analysis has demonstrated that nuclear energy holds a special position within Russia's energy diplomacy framework, functioning as one of the most

institutionally resilient and long-term instruments of foreign energy influence. Unlike the hydrocarbon sectors, nuclear diplomacy relies not only on the export of products but also on the establishment of comprehensive interstate relations, including financing, technological support, and participation throughout the entire life cycle of nuclear facilities.

The Russian model of energy diplomacy in the nuclear sector is characterized by a high degree of centralization and dependence on state mechanisms. The use of intergovernmental agreements, export credits, and long-term presence models allows Russia to secure its position in strategically important energy markets, primarily in countries with growing electricity demand and limited access to indigenous nuclear technologies. This ensures the stability of cooperation and reduces the dependence of projects on short-term political fluctuations.

At the same time, an analysis of the geography and mechanisms of implementing foreign nuclear projects reveals structural limitations of this model. High capital intensity, long investment cycles, and the growing role of state financing exacerbate the financial burden and increase the sensitivity of nuclear energy diplomacy to external constraints. Sanction pressure and the transformation of the global nuclear technology market necessitate adapting instruments and revising regional priorities.

Amid intensifying international competition and fragmentation of global energy markets, nuclear energy remains significant for Russia as one of the few sectors ensuring a systemic international presence and successful dominance within the structure of the global energy balance, where it, as 'green energy' and the most advanced industry, can continue to implicitly assert its distinctive advantages. However, the further development of energy diplomacy in the nuclear sector will depend on the ability to combine technological leadership with financial resilience and flexibility in foreign policy approaches, especially under the continuing sanction pressure from the 'collective West.' This underscores the necessity of transforming Russian nuclear diplomacy in accordance with new geopolitical and economic realities, the 'Anchorage spirit,' and Russia's maintenance of its unique position within the global energy infrastructure.

The world is exhausted by energy deficits and crises of heat and capacity shortages; consequently, it anticipates the increasingly extensive involvement of Russia in the nuclear infrastructure of digital breakthrough solutions that enhance the wealth and security of countries.

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ASPECTS OF THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES ON DIGITAL WELLBEING AND QUALITY OF LIFE

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Abstract. *This scientific article is devoted to studying the impact of digital technologies, particularly e-commerce, on digital wellbeing and quality of life. The relevance of this topic stems from the ongoing process of digitization that affects all spheres of human activity. The author conducted an empirical study by interviewing clients of a food online store across different age groups. The aim was to determine how e-commerce influences satisfaction with life needs and improves the overall quality of life. Key findings confirm the positive influence of e-commerce on digital wellbeing. The study has practical significance as its results help better understand consumer interactions with digital technologies and develop measures to enhance comfort and security in the context of the digital economy.*

Keywords: *population's quality of life, digital wellbeing, e-commerce, digitization, digital economy, indicators of population's quality of life.*

In light of the rapid development of digital technologies and globalization, issues related to quality of life and digital wellbeing have become increasingly important both for national governments and international organizations. These aspects not only affect social and economic development but also form a solid foundation for sustainable societal growth. Therefore, research and knowledge exchange in this area are crucial for achieving balanced global progress.

Quality of life is a multifaceted concept encompassing various dimensions of human existence. It refers to the degree of fulfillment of material, spiritual, and social needs. Components include health level, access to education, availability of essential services, and income levels. Thus, quality of life reflects not just objective metrics but also subjective perceptions of individual welfare. In this context, quality of life can be seen as a scientific category defined by specific indicators, methods of measurement and comparison, along with social norms regarding qualitative characteristics of living conditions and features at the individual, group, or societal

level [1]. Core components of quality of life include health, which serves as the basis for physical and mental well-being; education, providing opportunities for personal development and self-realization; income level ensuring access to material goods; safety — both physical and social; environmental conditions influencing residential comfort; and accessibility to cultural and social resources contributing to full participation in public life.

The concept of quality of life began taking shape in mid-twentieth century when the international community started paying attention not only to economic indicators but also to socio-economic prosperity. A significant step forward was the introduction of the Human Development Index (HDI) by the United Nations, incorporating such factors as life expectancy, educational level, and per capita income. This allowed for more comprehensive evaluation of living standards across countries. Additionally, there exists another index developed by “Economist Intelligence Unit” based on methodology linking subjective evaluations of life in different countries with objective determinants of quality of life [2]. Both indices complement each other, offering a holistic approach to assessing citizen well-being.

Evaluating quality of life serves as a critical tool for designing and implementing social programs and state policies. It helps identify key challenges and needs among citizens, enabling efficient measures aimed at improving their lives. Analyzing quality of life guides resource allocation toward areas requiring most urgent attention, thereby promoting sustainable societal development. Amidst increasing digitization, creating healthy work environments and adopting practices enhancing wellness becomes even more relevant [3].

Digital wellbeing represents a condition where digital technologies contribute positively to people’s quality of life [4][5]. It encompasses several core elements: Internet access, digital literacy, safe technology usage, and the impact of digital tools on physical and mental health [6]. These elements serve as a framework for understanding how digital tools can improve diverse facets of daily life, ranging from education to healthcare.

In contemporary society, digital wellbeing plays a pivotal role since it underpins sustainable development. According to UN reports from 2021, digital wellbeing is recognized as a vital factor affecting access to education, medical care, and economic opportunities [4]. It contributes to bridging the digital divide by ensuring equal access to critical resources and services for all segments of the population.

A high level of digital wellbeing exerts a beneficial effect on the quality of life through increased remote working possibilities, expanded educational resources, and enhanced medical services. For instance, distance learning enables people in remote regions to obtain quality education while telemedicine makes healthcare accessible for those far away from major medical centers.

Internationally, varied approaches exist for evaluating digital wellbeing [8]. In particular, Britain has introduced a digital inclusion index analyzing accessibility, skills, and utilization of digital technologies within the population. This index identifies areas needing improvement and informs strategies for boosting digital inclusiveness. Consequently, leveraging digital technologies globally underscores their importance for maintaining social and economic stability.

In today's world, digital technologies play a crucial and invaluable role in enhancing quality of life and digital wellbeing, significantly impacting everyday activities [9]. Specifically, in Russia, according to Rosstat data from 2022, the penetration rate of the Internet reached 83%. This creates favorable conditions for developing essential sectors like education, healthcare, and e-commerce.

To further clarify these impacts, especially concerning socially-oriented digital technologies like e-commerce, the author conducted an empirical study involving interviews with customers of an online grocery store. Two hundred respondents aged between 24 and 78 years participated. They were asked open-ended questions about how e-commerce affects their lives. Responses were analyzed and categorized by the author, with results presented in the text of the article.

According to Russian Association of Electronic Communications (RAEC), the volume of the e-commerce market in 2021 amounted to 4.1 trillion rubles, rising to 11.5 trillion rubles by 2025 [10]. This increase indicates dynamic sector expansion and substantial improvements in product/service accessibility for consumers, allowing them to make purchases without leaving home. During the COVID-19 pandemic, many brick-and-mortar stores closed down, making e-commerce indispensable for meeting basic necessities.

Furthermore, the National Project "Digital Economy of the Russian Federation" actively implements advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence and big data, leading to noticeable improvements in healthcare quality in some Russian regions [11]. For example, telemedicine and electronic medical records enable doctors to diagnose patients faster and more accurately, facilitating timely medical assistance. E-commerce also profoundly enhances the quality of life by giving users broader options compared to traditional retail outlets. Users can compare prices, read reviews, and gain access to a wider range of products and services. This benefits individuals with limited mobility or residing in distant locations. Moreover, e-commerce fosters small business development by enabling entrepreneurs to enter markets without large initial investments. As a result, it increases accessibility to goods/services, stimulates economic growth, and generates new job opportunities.

However, considering anticipated mobile internet restrictions in Russia by 2025, vulnerabilities in e-commerce services could adversely affect the quality of life.

Limitations in mobile connectivity may lead to slower speeds and unstable connections, hindering access to online shopping platforms. Furthermore, reliance

on less secure networks might expose users to cyber threats, compromising sensitive information and financial losses. Under restricted internet access, residents may face difficulties obtaining necessary goods and services, negatively impacting livelihoods, particularly vulnerable populations and rural dwellers who already struggle accessing physical shops.

Thus, combining vulnerabilities in e-commerce services and limitations in mobile internet presents serious challenges for Russians' quality of life, jeopardizing economic stability and access to essential resources.

Additionally, e-commerce influences family relationships in multiple ways. On one hand, online shopping and services simplify daily tasks, saving time and effort spent on routine chores like groceries or travel planning. This frees up more time for family bonding and communication enhancement. However, constant exposure to online commerce introduces potential problems. Excessive spending habits and dependence on shopping may cause internal conflicts over finances. Screen-time use reduces interpersonal interaction, harming emotional bonds within families.

Therefore, the impact of e-commerce on familial dynamics appears dualistic: while it may improve life quality and interactions, it simultaneously poses new challenges demanding attention and resolution.

For instance, uncoordinated purchases made independently by family members often trigger disputes, particularly when funds come from shared budgets. Online retailers' wide assortment sometimes leads to impulsive and ill-conceived expenditures causing dissatisfaction and stress. Nonetheless, e-commerce mitigates tensions arising from household duties associated with purchasing items.

Firstly, online shopping empowers every family member to select and order required items autonomously, minimizing disagreements about responsibilities. Secondly, electronic platforms offer convenient collaborative purchase planning tools. Features like joint shopping lists or budget-sharing apps allow collective decision-making processes. Such transparency promotes constructive dialogue on fiscal matters, reducing conflict probability. Also, comparing prices and finding deals online encourages rational expenditure management, alleviating purchase-related stress and encouraging cooperative efforts towards savings goals.

E-commerce also contributes to user safety by simplifying transactions and reducing risks linked to physical shopping trips. Injuries sustained during visits to brick-and-mortar stores — such as falls, collisions, muscle strains, or heavy lifting — are avoided through online alternatives. Hence, modern technologies ensure safer shopping experiences, benefitting urbanites facing heightened injury risks.

Consequently, families now enjoy safe and hassle-free shopping from home. Not only does this save time but allows focused discussions and alignment of financial decisions in relaxed settings. E-commerce elevates customer satisfaction by granting independence in sourcing essential goods and services.

Online platforms empower buyers to choose freely, free from external opinions or aid. Access to extensive catalogues, price comparisons, and reviews equips users with informed decision-making capabilities. Ultimately, they derive greater satisfaction knowing their choices align perfectly with their preferences and expectations.

Moreover, online shopping provides unique opportunities for exploring diverse options and discovering optimal deals without pressure from sales personnel. This fosters a comfortable environment conducive to thoughtful decision-making, particularly valuable amid rapidly evolving markets. Overall, this mode of trade simplifies buying processes while encouraging responsible consumption patterns central to households' financial sustainability.

Additionally, e-commerce supports social initiatives, enhancing trust in brands and client satisfaction. Many online stores engage in charitable projects, letting shoppers feel good about supporting worthy causes alongside purchasing essentials. Participation in philanthropic campaigns or local producer support adds value for consumers, strengthening brand loyalty. Beyond convenience, e-commerce nurtures deeper engagement and corporate responsibility.

It also offers unique opportunities for skill acquisition and first-hand experience in the digital realm. Engaging in e-commerce helps individuals master skills like managing online stores, using analytical tools, marketing via social media, etc. — all highly relevant in today's digital landscape. Skill-building enhances personal competencies while opening career paths in fast-growing industries.

Through empirical research, additional insights into e-commerce's effects on digital wellbeing and quality of life emerged. Findings indicate improved satisfaction due to broad service/product variety available online, lower risk of spontaneous purchases, reduced tension in domestic relations, fewer injuries caused by physical shopping, and higher satisfaction derived from autonomy in securing needed supplies.

Despite these advantages, certain limitations persist. Sample representativeness remains an issue as not all demographic strata were adequately covered. Future studies should assess the precise influence of e-commerce on key indicators of digital wellbeing and quality of life.

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SHIKAKEOLOGY AND BEHAVIORAL ECONOMICS: DESIGNING FOR ETHICAL ENGAGEMENT IN VIDEO GAMES

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Abstract. *This paper proposes a theoretical synthesis of Shikakeology — the Japanese science of designing behavioral triggers — and behavioral economics to develop an ethical framework for video game design. While Shikakeology provides a taxonomy of physical and psychological triggers that subtly influence behavior, behavioral economics explains the cognitive biases and decision-making mechanisms underlying player engagement. By bridging these two traditions, we analyze how game mechanics such as battle passes, loot boxes, and social features function as complex shikake, activating psychological triggers that can either foster sustainable engagement or exploit player vulnerabilities. The paper introduces the concept of «ethical engagement» as a design principle that distinguishes win-win shikake from dark patterns. Finally, we outline the Shikake Atlas — a proposed analytical tool for classifying game mechanics by their behavioral triggers and economic effects — as a practical resource for developers seeking to adapt Japanese engagement strategies ethically.*

Keywords: *shikakeology, shikake, behavioral economics, behavioral design, video game design, engagement economy.*

The digital economy has created unprecedented opportunities for scaling cultural products, yet it has also generated a fundamental challenge: the struggle for user attention in an environment of near-zero marginal costs. Nowhere is this more evident than in the video game industry, where business models increasingly depend not on one-time sales but on long-term user engagement and retention. As Mariko Koizumi (Ph.D. in Media Environmental Studies, Kyoto Seika University) documents in her comprehensive historical analysis, the Japanese market has witnessed a dramatic shift from packaged software to service-based models, with online games — including social games and smartphone applications — surpassing traditional console software sales by 2012 [Koizumi, 2016, pp. 46-48].

In this competitive landscape, traditional strategies of price competition and aggressive marketing show diminishing returns. What becomes crucial is the ability to design experiences that foster sustainable engagement — to create environments where users want to return, not because they are trapped, but because they find intrinsic value in the interaction. This is precisely where the Japanese tradition of shikake offers a unique perspective.

Shikakeology, as developed by Professor Naohiro Matsumura of Osaka University and his colleagues, studies how deliberately designed triggers in physical or digital environments can gently, often unconsciously, nudge people toward desired behaviors [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 420]. From a staircase painted like a piano that encourages people to walk instead of taking the escalator, to a trash bin shaped like a basketball hoop that makes disposing of litter playful, shikake operate through a combination of physical and psychological triggers [Matsumura et al., 2015, pp. 422-424]. Crucially, a shikake is defined by three characteristics: it is an embodied trigger for behavior change, it is designed to induce specific behavior, and it aims to solve a social or personal problem [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 420]. This last point is essential: shikake is not about manipulation, but about creating win-win situations.

The success of Japanese video game companies — Nintendo, Capcom, From-Software, and others — can be partly attributed to their mastery of such behavioral design, even if intuitively rather than systematically. As Hiro Izushi, Professor in the Business Department at Aston University, and Yuko Aoyama, Professor of Economic Geography at Clark University, demonstrate, the Japanese game industry drew on rich creative talent from comic books (manga) and animated films (anime), which provided the narrative and visual foundations for character-driven game design [Izushi, Aoyama, 2006, pp. 1850-1851]. This cultural foundation enabled Japanese developers to create games with strong storylines and relatable characters at a time when technological limitations made photorealistic graphics impossible [Izushi, Aoyama, 2006, p. 1855]. In shikake terms, they excelled at creating analogy-based triggers and positive expectation through narrative.

However, Shikakeology alone, while providing a powerful descriptive framework, does not fully explain why certain triggers work. This is where behavioral economics becomes indispensable. Behavioral economics, drawing on the work of Daniel Kahneman, Amos Tversky, Richard Thaler, and others, offers insights into the cognitive biases and heuristics that shape human decision-making. Key concepts such as hyperbolic discounting — the tendency to overvalue immediate rewards and undervalue future consequences — help explain why players are drawn to daily login bonuses or battle passes [Takahashi, 2018, p. 120]. Mental accounting and payment isolation illuminate why minors may overspend using parental accounts without experiencing the «pain of payment». Reference dependence and

social comparison clarify the power of leaderboards and rare cosmetic items [Qu, Luo, 2025, pp. 927-928].

The convergence of these two fields — Shikakeology and behavioral economics — opens a productive space for inquiry. If Shikakeology provides the vocabulary of triggers, behavioral economics provides the grammar of cognitive mechanisms. Together, they can help us understand not only how game mechanics engage players, but also when such engagement crosses the line into exploitation. The growing scholarly and public concern over «dark patterns» — interfaces designed to trick users into actions they did not intend [Luguri, Strahilevitz, 2021, p. 46] — makes this ethical dimension particularly urgent.

This paper aims to synthesize these two traditions into a coherent framework for analyzing and designing ethical engagement in video games. We argue that:

1. Video game mechanics can be understood as complex shikake, combining multiple physical and psychological triggers to shape player behavior.
2. Behavioral economics provides the explanatory mechanism for why these triggers work, grounding them in established theories of decision-making.
3. The ethical distinction between shikake and dark patterns lies in whether the design solves a genuine problem for the user/community or merely exploits cognitive vulnerabilities for corporate gain.
4. This synthesis can inform a practical tool — the Shikake Atlas — for developers seeking to adapt Japanese engagement strategies ethically.

The concept of shikake originates from a Japanese word with multifaceted meanings, encompassing «device», «mechanism», «contrivance», and even «challenge». Within the academic framework of Shikakeology, Professor Matsumura and his colleagues define a shikake more precisely as «an embodied trigger for behavior change» designed to solve social or personal problems. This definition rests on three essential characteristics: first, a shikake must be an embodied trigger — a perceivable artifact or feature in the environment; second, it must be deliberately designed to induce specific behavior; and third, the intended behavior should address a genuine problem, whether social or personal [Matsumura et al., 2015, pp. 419-420].

A key distinction in Shikakeology is the interplay between physical and psychological triggers. Physical triggers operate through direct sensory channels — visual, auditory, haptic, olfactory, or taste feedback — while also serving as feedforward mechanisms that signal how an object might be used. Psychological triggers, by contrast, work through individual and social cognitive mechanisms, including challenge, curiosity, reward, self-esteem, social proof, and the feeling of being watched [Matsumura et al., 2015, pp. 424-426]. The power of a shikake lies in the synergy between these two levels: a physical trigger ignites a psychological trigger, and the psychological trigger then drives behavioral change [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 422].

Matsumura and colleagues illustrate this mechanism through several canonical examples. A cylinder installed at Tennouji Zoo in Japan, shaped like a telescope with a hole at eye level for children, uses its physical form (analogy to a telescope) and placement to trigger curiosity — a psychological trigger — leading children to look inside and discover a replica of elephant excrement, transforming a walkway into an exploratory experience. A tiny replica of a Shinto shrine gate placed in a litter-prone area works as a physical analogy that evokes the psychological trigger of social norm, discouraging littering by creating an association with sacred space [Matsumura et al., 2015, pp. 422-423]. A fake fly etched into urinals triggers an instinctive aim response, combining visual feedback with the psychological challenge of «hitting the target» to reduce spillage. The famous «Piano Stairs» installation transforms a staircase into a musical instrument, using auditory and visual feedback to make stair-climbing playful, thereby triggering positive expectation and voluntary behavior change [Matsumura et al., 2015, pp. 424-425].

Importantly, Matsumura and his colleagues emphasize that shikake are not traps or tricks designed to force or deceive. Rather, they «encourage people to change their behavior by presenting them with possible alternative behaviors, either explicitly or implicitly». The objectives of the designer and the target user need not align perfectly; what matters is that the shikake facilitates a behavior that solves a problem, creating a win-win outcome [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 420].

To systematize the design of such triggers, Matsumura and colleagues developed a hierarchical taxonomy of shikake trigger categories [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 426]. At the top level, triggers are divided into physical and psychological. Physical triggers encompass Feedback (Auditory, Haptic, Olfactory, Taste, Visual) and Feedforward (Analogy, Perceived Affordance). Psychological triggers branch into Individual context (Challenge, Dissonance, Negative Expectation, Positive Expectation, Reward, Self-esteem) and Social context (Being Watched, Social Norm, Social Proof). Based on an analysis of 120 shikake cases, they further constructed a «shikake trigger matrix» revealing patterns of frequently co-occurring triggers — for instance, the combination of Analogy and Positive Expectation appeared in 13 cases, while Auditory and Positive Expectation appeared in 11 [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 428]. These patterns offer «rules of thumb» for designing new shikake, suggesting which physical-psychological pairings are most likely to prove effective.

While Shikakeology provides a rich descriptive vocabulary for how triggers operate, it does not fully explain the underlying cognitive mechanisms that make these triggers effective. This is where behavioral economics — the study of how psychological factors shape economic decision-making — offers crucial explanatory power. Behavioral economics emerged from a sustained critique of the neo-classical assumption of *homo economicus*, the perfectly rational agent with stable

preferences and unlimited computational capacity. Drawing on empirical research in psychology, scholars such as Daniel Kahneman, Amos Tversky, and Richard Thaler demonstrated that human decision-making is systematically shaped by cognitive biases, heuristics, and framing effects.

One of the foundational theories in behavioral economics is Prospect Theory, developed by Kahneman and Tversky. Prospect Theory shows that individuals evaluate outcomes not in absolute terms but relative to a reference point, and that they experience losses more intensely than equivalent gains — a phenomenon known as loss aversion. This has profound implications for understanding player behavior in games: losing a rare item or falling in a leaderboard ranking can feel more impactful than gaining an equivalent reward, motivating players to invest further to avoid loss.

Another key concept is Mental Accounting, introduced by Richard Thaler. Mental accounting refers to the cognitive operations individuals use to organize, evaluate, and track financial activities. People mentally segregate money into different «accounts» (e.g., «savings», «entertainment budget») and treat these accounts as non-fungible, even when rationally they should be interchangeable. A particularly relevant extension of this is payment isolation — the phenomenon whereby the psychological link between payment and consumption is weakened, reducing the «pain of paying». As Jiakang Qu (Beijing Haidian Foreign Language Shi Yan School) and Xin Luo (Zhejiang University) demonstrate in their analysis of minors' gaming addiction, when children use parental accounts to make in-game purchases, they do not directly experience the financial transaction, leading to payment isolation and diminished resistance to impulse spending [Qu, Luo, 2025, p. 927].

Intertemporal choice — decisions involving trade-offs between costs and benefits occurring at different times — is another critical domain. Neoclassical economics assumes that individuals discount future rewards exponentially, implying consistent preferences over time. However, empirical research reveals that humans exhibit hyperbolic discounting: they disproportionately prefer smaller, immediate rewards over larger, delayed rewards, and this preference can reverse over time — a phenomenon known as dynamic inconsistency. Taiki Takahashi, Professor at Hokkaido University, applies this framework to addiction in the digital age. He explains that individuals with Internet Gaming Disorder show impaired ability to evaluate trade-offs between delayed rewards (e.g., long-term well-being from abstinence) and immediate gratification (e.g., continuing to play), with neuroimaging studies revealing dysfunction in the prefrontal cortex and altered activation in the nucleus accumbens, a key reward region [Takahashi, 2018, pp. 120-121]. Hyperbolic discounting helps explain why players are drawn to daily login bonuses (immediate small rewards) and battle passes (structured sequences of rewards that exploit present bias).

Reference dependence further illuminates social dynamics in games. As Qu and Luo note, players often use rare virtual items or rankings obtained by others as reference points, and this social comparison generates stronger consumer demand. When a player sees a peer acquire a rare cosmetic item, they perceive their own status as diminished relative to this reference point, motivating them to spend to restore their position [Qu, Luo, 2025, p. 928]. Game mechanics such as leaderboards, rare item displays, and social feeds actively cultivate such reference dependence, transforming social comparison into an economic driver.

Finally, the gambling effect — or infatuation with small probability events — explains the appeal of loot boxes and gacha mechanics. When faced with a low-probability but high-value reward, individuals tend to develop excessive expectations, leading to repeated impulsive decisions. This is compounded by the «near-miss» effect, where failing to win but coming close intensifies the urge to continue. Minors, whose prefrontal cortex is not fully mature, are particularly susceptible to this mechanism.

Having reviewed both Shikakeology and behavioral economics, we can now articulate their complementary relationship and why their synthesis is theoretically productive.

Shikakeology excels at describing the design features that trigger behavioral change. Its taxonomy of physical and psychological triggers provides a systematic language for analyzing how artifacts — whether physical objects like a piano staircase or digital interfaces like a battle pass — are structured to influence action. Moreover, by emphasizing that shikake are embodied and designed, it grounds analysis in concrete, observable features of the environment.

However, Shikakeology is primarily a descriptive and taxonomic enterprise. It tells us what triggers exist and how they are combined, but it offers limited explanation of why they work — that is, the cognitive and neural mechanisms that make certain triggers effective. Why does a visual analogy (e. g., a shrine gate) activate a social norm? Why does auditory feedback (e. g., the sound of a coin in Mario) motivate repeated action? Why do challenge-based triggers (e. g., hitting a fly in a urinal) feel intrinsically rewarding?

Behavioral economics provides the missing explanatory layer. It offers well-established theories of cognitive biases, heuristics, and decision-making processes that explain the psychological mechanisms underlying shikake triggers. The physical trigger of a shrine gate works because it activates a reference-dependent social norm; the auditory feedback of a coin works because it provides immediate positive reinforcement that appeals to our hyperbolically discounting brains; the challenge of hitting a fly works because it taps into intrinsic motivation for mastery and the positive affect associated with reward prediction error.

Conversely, behavioral economics often remains at the level of describing biases without offering concrete design principles for intervention. It tells us that

people are loss-averse, but not how to design an environment that harnesses loss aversion for positive ends. Shikakeology provides that design vocabulary. As Matsumura and colleagues envision, their trigger categories and matrix are intended to be used in practice — to enable «anyone to create new shikakes» [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 428]. The synthesis we propose thus completes a theoretical circuit: Shikakeology supplies the design patterns, behavioral economics supplies the explanatory mechanisms, and together they form a framework for intentional, theory-driven intervention.

This synthesis also illuminates why the Japanese video game industry has been particularly successful in creating engaging experiences. As Izushi and Aoyama demonstrate, Japan's game developers drew on creative talent from manga and anime — industries that had already mastered the art of creating compelling characters and narratives with limited technological resources [Izushi, Aoyama, 2006, pp. 1850-1851]. At a time when technological constraints made photorealistic graphics impossible, Japanese developers excelled at designing analogy-based triggers and positive expectation through storytelling. This was, in effect, an intuitive application of shikake principles — creating engagement not through computational power, but through carefully designed psychological triggers. Behavioral economics now allows us to understand why those triggers worked: they tapped into fundamental human motivations for competence, autonomy, and relatedness (Self-Determination Theory), while exploiting cognitive biases in ways that felt rewarding rather than manipulative.

Matsumura and colleagues' taxonomy of physical triggers distinguishes between Feedback (auditory, haptic, olfactory, taste, visual) and Feedforward (analogy, perceived affordance) [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 424]. In digital games, these physical triggers are translated into interface elements, sound design, haptic feedback through controllers, and visual effects that serve the same functions: providing real-time responses to player actions and signaling possible interactions.

Table 1 presents a systematic mapping of physical shikake triggers to their manifestations in video game mechanics, with examples drawn from both Japanese and Western game design traditions.

As Koizumi notes, Japanese game developers have historically excelled at visual design that emphasizes clarity and character expression over photorealism, with Japanese consumers consistently preferring 2D graphics to hyper-realistic 3D rendering. This aesthetic preference aligns with shikake principles: clear visual feedback and intuitive analogies are more readily achieved when graphics prioritize communication over verisimilitude. The success of Nintendo's DS series and Wii, which expanded gaming demographics to middle-aged and senior players [Koizumi, 2016, p. 20], can be partly attributed to their emphasis on intuitive perceived affordance — designing interfaces that signaled their use without requiring technical expertise.

Table 1. Physical Shikake Triggers and Their Manifestations in Video Game Mechanics

Shikake Trigger (Physical)	Game Mechanic	Example	Behavioral-Economic Mechanism
Auditory Feedback	Sound effects for actions, level-ups, rewards	Coin collection sound in <i>Super Mario</i> series (Nintendo); «level up» fanfare in <i>Dragon Quest</i> (Square Enix)	Immediate positive reinforcement; dopamine release
Visual Feedback	Progress bars, experience points, damage numbers, particle effects	Health bars in <i>Dark Souls</i> (FromSoftware); combo counters in <i>Devil May Cry</i> (Capcom)	Goal gradient effect; visualization of progress toward completion
Haptic Feedback	Controller vibration, rumble effects	Controller shake when taking damage in <i>The Legend of Zelda</i> (Nintendo); haptic feedback for different surfaces in <i>Astro's Playroom</i> (Sony)	Embodied reinforcement; somatic marker for events
Analogy	Interface metaphors, familiar game patterns	«Battle pass» as digital analog of season ticket; «loot box» as analog of physical mystery box	Reduced cognitive load; transfer of learned expectations
Perceived Affordance	Intuitive UI elements, button prompts	«Press X to open» prompts; glowing interactable objects	Reduced friction; lowered barriers to action

If physical triggers constitute the «interface» of shikake, psychological triggers constitute the «engine» — the cognitive and motivational mechanisms that translate perception into action. Matsumura and colleagues identify psychological triggers operating at both individual (Challenge, Dissonance, Negative/Positive Expectation, Reward, Self-esteem) and social levels (Being Watched, Social Norm, Social Proof) [Matsumura et al., 2015, pp. 425-426]. Behavioral economics provides the explanatory framework for understanding why these triggers are effective by linking them to specific cognitive biases and heuristics.

Table 2 maps psychological shikake triggers onto their corresponding behavioral-economic mechanisms and illustrates their manifestation in game design.

Table 2. Psychological Shikake Triggers, Behavioral-Economic Mechanisms, and Game Design Manifestations

Shikake Trigger (Psychological)	Behavioral-Economic Mechanism	Game Mechanic	Example
Challenge	Intrinsic motivation for competence; goal-gradient effect	Achievements, trophies, difficulty levels, time trials	<i>Sekiro: Shadows Die Twice</i> (FromSoftware) mastery-based progression
Positive Expectation	Dopamine anticipation; reward prediction error	Loot boxes, gacha mechanics, randomized rewards	<i>Genshin Impact</i> (miHoYo) wish system; <i>Pokémon</i> trading card packs
Reward	Hyperbolic discounting; present bias	Daily login bonuses, time-limited events	<i>Fate/Grand Order</i> login streaks (DELIGHTWORKS)
Self-esteem	Self-determination theory; competence need	Character customization, player housing, profile customization	<i>Animal Crossing</i> (Nintendo) island personalization
Social Proof	Reference dependence; social comparison	Leaderboards, friend activity feeds, «friends who play» notifications	<i>PlayStation Network</i> activity feed; <i>Xbox</i> friends leaderboards
Being Watched	Social facilitation; accountability	Public profiles, streaming integration, spectator modes	<i>Twitch</i> integration in games; visible online status
Social Norm	Conformity; descriptive norms	Guilds, clans, community guidelines, shared goals	<i>Monster Hunter</i> (Capcom) cooperative hunting culture

The effectiveness of these mechanisms is not merely theoretical. Takahashi notes that neuroimaging studies have identified specific neural correlates of gaming-related decision-making: the nucleus accumbens, a key region in reward processing, shows altered activation patterns in individuals with Internet Gaming Disorder, while prefrontal cortex dysfunction impairs response inhibition and cognitive control [Takahashi, 2018, pp. 120-121]. These findings suggest that game mechanics exploiting psychological triggers are not merely «engaging» in a metaphorical sense — they literally reshape neural processing of reward and impulse control over time.

To illustrate the integrated framework, we now analyze the battle pass — a monetization model pioneered by *Dota 2* (Valve) in 2013 and subsequently adopted widely across the industry, particularly in Japan by companies such as Nintendo (*Splatoon 2*, *Mario Kart Tour*), Capcom (*Monster Hunter* series), and

mobile developers like GungHo (*Puzzle & Dragons*). The battle pass is an exemplary case of a complex digital shikake — a multi-component system combining multiple physical and psychological triggers into a coherent engagement architecture.

A typical battle pass employs several physical triggers simultaneously:

- **Visual Feedback:** a progress bar displays the player's current level, remaining levels, and rewards at each tier. As Koizumi notes regarding Nintendo's quality-control philosophy, clear visual communication of progress and reward structure reduces cognitive friction and encourages continued engagement [Koizumi, 2016, p. 25].

- **Auditory Feedback:** leveling up the battle pass triggers distinctive sound effects that signal achievement. Matsumura and colleagues emphasize that auditory feedback «attracts immediate attention» and can make interactions more salient [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 424].

- **Analogy:** the term «battle pass» itself functions as an analogy, drawing on familiar concepts from transportation (season tickets) and entertainment (season passes). This reduces the learning curve and transfers positive associations from existing mental models.

- **Perceived Affordance:** the interface clearly signals that clicking on locked rewards reveals their contents and that progressing through levels unlocks them. This transparency of function is essential to effective shikake design.

The battle pass activates multiple psychological triggers simultaneously, creating synergistic effects:

- **Challenge:** the multi-level structure presents an unwritten goal — completing all tiers before the season ends. Matsumura and colleagues note that challenge triggers «set an unwritten goal in people's minds» and «urge people to become involved, although they do not have to» [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 426].

- **Reward:** rewards are distributed at every level, with premium tiers offering more valuable items. This frequent reinforcement schedule maintains engagement through variable ratio reinforcement — a mechanism known to be highly effective in shaping behavior.

- **Positive Expectation:** locked rewards create anticipation about future content. The combination of visual concealment (what's in the next tier?) and temporal delay (I'll get it when I level up) generates positive expectation, which Matsumura and colleagues identify as a trigger that «arouses people's curiosity... making people excited by imagining what might happen» [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 426].

- **Social Proof:** many battle passes display friends' progress or allow players to see which rewards others have earned. This activates social comparison, which Qu and Luo identify as a key driver of consumption: «minors often use rare virtual items or game rankings obtained by others as reference points, and this social comparison leads to stronger consumer demand» [Qu, Luo, 2025, p. 928].

From a behavioral-economic perspective, the battle pass exploits several well-documented cognitive biases:

- **Hyperbolic discounting:** players pay upfront (or commit to playing) for rewards distributed over time, systematically overvaluing the future rewards relative to their actual value.
- **Sunk cost fallacy:** once players have invested time (or money) in the battle pass, they become more likely to continue investing to «get their money's worth» or avoid wasting prior effort.
- **Endowment effect:** as players unlock rewards, they come to feel ownership over them, making the prospect of losing access to future rewards (by not completing the pass) feel like a loss.
- **Goal-gradient effect:** players accelerate their play as they approach the final tier, a phenomenon well-documented in loyalty program research.

The battle pass thus exemplifies how shikake principles, when systematically applied, create self-reinforcing engagement loops. Importantly, as Izushi and Aoyama [Izushi, Aoyama, 2006, p. 1855] note regarding the historical evolution of game design, such mechanics succeed not merely through technological sophistication but through deep understanding of player psychology — a understanding that Japanese developers cultivated through their roots in manga and anime storytelling traditions.

The same psychological mechanisms that make shikake effective for positive behavior change can, when deployed without ethical restraint, create harmful patterns of addiction and exploitation. This is particularly concerning when the targets are minors, whose developing brains are more susceptible to impulse-control failures and reward-seeking behavior.

Qu and Luo provide a detailed behavioral-economic analysis of minors' addiction to game top-ups in China, identifying three key mechanisms that parallel the shikake framework:

Payment isolation occurs when minors use parental accounts to make purchases, severing the psychological link between payment and consumption. As Qu and Luo explain: «Minors often top up through their parents' payment accounts, and the separation between payment and actual consumption enhances their demand for virtual rewards and reduces the psychological burden of consumption» [Qu, Luo, 2025, p. 927]. In shikake terms, the physical trigger of «one-click purchase» (perceived affordance) activates a psychological trigger (reward anticipation) without the countervailing «pain of payment» that would normally inhibit excessive spending.

Infatuation with small probability events describes the gambling-like attraction to loot boxes and gacha mechanics. Qu and Luo observe: «When faced with a low probability but high-value reward, individuals tend to develop excessive

expectations, which in turn lead to frequent impulsive decision-making» [Qu, Luo, 2025, p. 928]. This maps directly onto Matsumura and colleagues' category of positive expectation, but in this context the expectation is systematically exploited rather than satisfied. The «near-miss» effect — where players almost win but fall short — intensifies the urge to continue, creating a behavioral pattern indistinguishable from pathological gambling.

Reference dependence drives social comparison and status anxiety. As Qu and Luo note: «Minors often use rare virtual items or game rankings obtained by others as reference points, and this social comparison leads to stronger consumer demand» [Qu, Luo, 2025, p. 928]. This activates the social proof and social norm triggers identified by Matsumura and colleagues, but in ways that can generate anxiety, envy, and compulsive spending rather than positive social engagement.

Takahashi provides the neurobiological context for understanding these phenomena. He notes that Internet Gaming Disorder involves «poorer response-inhibition and emotion regulation, impaired prefrontal cortex functioning and cognitive control, poorer working memory and decision-making capabilities». Crucially, «time-discount rate, an economic parameter indicating impulsivity, has been shown to mediate the relationship between posterior insular cortex volume and social media addiction symptoms» [Takahashi, 2018, p. 120]. This suggests that individuals differ in their baseline vulnerability to shikake-like triggers — a fact that ethical designers must take into account.

The distinction between ethical shikake and harmful dark patterns thus hinges on three criteria:

1. Intent: Does the design aim to solve a genuine problem for the user/community, or merely to extract maximum revenue regardless of user welfare? Matsumura and colleagues emphasize that shikake should address «social or personal problems» [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 420].

2. Transparency: Are the mechanics and their likely effects transparent to users, or are they deliberately obscured? Dark patterns thrive on deception and confusion [Luguri, Strahilevitz, 2021, p. 46].

3. Proportionality: Do the engagement mechanisms respect users' autonomy and cognitive limitations, or do they exploit vulnerabilities (particularly those of minors and other vulnerable populations)?

As Izushi and Aoyama observe in their comparative analysis, «the sociocultural cohesiveness between old and new industries further lowers the sectoral barrier for skill transfers» [Izushi, Aoyama, 2006, p. 1857]. We might extend this insight: the sociocultural responsibility of an industry — its embeddedness in norms of care and ethical practice — determines whether its skill in designing engagement is deployed for good or for ill. Japanese game companies, drawing on cultural traditions that emphasize harmony and social responsibility, may be better positioned

to develop shikake that respect user welfare, but this is not automatic; it requires conscious ethical reflection and design discipline.

The preceding analysis has demonstrated that video game mechanics can be understood as complex digital shikake — deliberately designed triggers that shape player behavior through the same basic mechanisms identified by Matsumura and colleagues, translated into the unique affordances of digital media. However, this very effectiveness raises profound ethical questions. The same psychological mechanisms that make shikake powerful tools for positive behavior change can, when deployed without ethical restraint, create harmful patterns of addiction, exploitation, and compromised autonomy.

A crucial but often overlooked aspect of Matsumura and colleagues' definition of shikake is its teleological dimension: a shikake must be designed to solve a «social or personal problem». This is not merely a descriptive observation but a normative constraint — a shikake that fails to address a genuine problem, or that creates problems while purporting to solve them, is not a shikake in the full sense intended by Shikakeology.

Matsumura and colleagues elaborate this point by distinguishing shikake from mere manipulation or deception: «a shikake is not a trap to force or trick people, but a way to encourage people to change their behavior by presenting them with possible alternative behaviors, either explicitly or implicitly». Importantly, they note that «the objectives of target people and shikake designers do not necessarily align» [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 420]. What matters is that the shikake facilitates behavior that solves a problem, creating a win-win outcome where both parties benefit, even if for different reasons.

The canonical examples of shikake illustrate this win-win principle. The fly etched into urinals solves the facility's problem of spillage and cleaning costs while offering users a playful challenge; the users are not harmed or exploited, and they may even derive minor satisfaction from hitting the target. The piano staircase encourages physical activity (solving a public health problem) while providing users with a moment of playful delight. The transparent trash improves recycling accuracy while appealing to users' self-esteem and social awareness — users feel good about doing the right thing.

In each case, the shikake operates not by coercing or deceiving, but by aligning desirable outcomes with intrinsic motivations. The win-win principle thus provides the ethical foundation for Shikakeology: a well-designed shikake creates value for all parties involved, respecting users' autonomy while gently guiding behavior toward beneficial ends.

The concept of «dark patterns» emerged in user experience design to describe interfaces that deliberately trick users into actions they did not intend. Jamie Lugi (Law Clerk to the Honorable Amy St. Eve) and Lior Jacob Strahilevitz (Sidley

Austin Professor of Law) define dark patterns as «user interface designs that trick users into doing things they might otherwise not do», noting that they «exploit cognitive biases and decision-making vulnerabilities to steer users toward choices that benefit the platform» [Luguri, Strahilevitz, 2021, p. 46]. This definition precisely inverts the win-win principle of shikake: dark patterns create win-lose outcomes where the platform gains at the user’s expense.

Luguri and Strahilevitz identify several categories of dark patterns relevant to game design [Luguri, Strahilevitz, 2021, p. 48]:

- Forced action: requiring users to do something they wouldn’t otherwise do to access a desired feature
 - Interface interference: highlighting certain options while hiding others
 - Obstruction: making it difficult for users to cancel subscriptions or opt out of unwanted features
 - Sneaking: hiding costs or automatically enrolling users in recurring payments
 - Social proof manipulation: fabricating or exaggerating social endorsements
- In gaming contexts, dark patterns manifest in mechanics such as:
 - Loot boxes with hidden or misleading odds, particularly when targeted at minors who cannot accurately assess probabilities
 - Aggressive «nudge» mechanics that repeatedly prompt users to spend, exploiting present bias and hyperbolic discounting
 - Deliberately confusing cancellation flows for subscriptions, making it difficult for users to stop spending
 - Artificial scarcity and FOMO (fear of missing out) tactics that pressure users into impulse decisions
 - Payment isolation exploitation, where systems are designed to minimize the psychological «pain of paying», particularly problematic when minors use parental accounts

The harm caused by such patterns is not trivial. Qu and Luo document cases where minors accumulated thousands of dollars in charges without parental knowledge or consent [Qu, Luo, 2025, p. 926]. Beyond financial harm, these mechanics can contribute to gaming disorder, anxiety, and compromised autonomy. As Takahashi notes, neuroimaging studies reveal those individuals with Internet Gaming Disorder show «poorer response-inhibition and emotion regulation, impaired prefrontal cortex functioning and cognitive control» [Takahashi, 2018, p. 120] — suggesting that prolonged exposure to exploitative engagement mechanics may have lasting neurological effects.

Drawing on the theoretical framework, we can propose criteria for distinguishing ethical shikake from harmful dark patterns. These criteria operate at multiple levels: designer intent, mechanism transparency, user autonomy, and outcome proportionality.

Table 3 presents a comparative framework for distinguishing ethical shikake from dark patterns across key dimensions.

Table 3. Ethical Shikake vs. Dark Patterns: A Comparative Framework

Dimension	Ethical Shikake	Dark Pattern
Primary Intent	Solve a genuine problem for user/community	Maximize platform revenue regardless of user welfare
Problem Definition	Problem is defined with user/community interests in mind	Problem is defined from platform perspective (e.g., «low engagement», «insufficient spending»)
Transparency	Mechanics and their effects are transparent and understandable	Mechanics are deliberately obscured; true costs/consequences hidden
User Autonomy	Preserves meaningful choice; exit is straightforward	Manipulates choice architecture; exit is made difficult
Cognitive Vulnerability	Respects cognitive limitations; does not exploit known vulnerabilities	Exploits cognitive biases and vulnerabilities (especially in minors)
Outcome Distribution	Win-win: both parties benefit	Win-lose: platform gains at user's expense
Long-term Effect	Supports sustainable engagement and user well-being	May generate short-term revenue but undermines trust and well-being
Cultural Embedding	Reflects sociocultural norms of care and responsibility	Ignores or exploits cultural context for extraction

The distinction is not always sharp in practice. A mechanic that begins as an ethical shikake can degrade into a dark pattern through aggressive optimization. For example, daily login bonuses — which can be a harmless way to reward regular players — become problematic when they employ variable ratio schedules designed to maximize compulsion, or when they pressure players to log in at disruptive times. The difference lies not in the mechanic itself but in how it is implemented and whether it respects the criteria above.

Qu and Luo propose a similar distinction in their policy recommendations, arguing for «optimizing ‘choice architecture’» to encourage rational decisions while preserving freedom. They emphasize that design should «reduce the negative impact of game consumption behavior» on minors, suggesting that ethical design requires proactive attention to vulnerable populations [Qu, Luo, 2025, p. 929].

Building on the theoretical synthesis and the distinction criteria above, we propose a practical checklist for game designers and publishers seeking to implement shikake-informed mechanics ethically. This checklist operationalizes the win-win principle and the distinction criteria into concrete questions that can guide design decisions.

Intent and Problem Definition:

1. Whose problem are we solving? Is this a problem experienced by players/community, or merely a business metric problem (e.g., low retention)?
2. How would we explain the mechanic's purpose to a player? Can we articulate its value in terms of player benefit?
3. Would we be comfortable with our children (or vulnerable users) engaging with this mechanic?

Transparency and Autonomy:

4. Are the mechanics and their likely effects transparent? Can players easily understand how the system works and what it will cost them (time, money, attention)?
5. Is exit straightforward? Can players opt out, cancel, or discontinue without navigating deliberately confusing interfaces?
6. Are default settings in players' interest? Do defaults protect rather than exploit? (following the «nudge» principle of Richard Thaler and Cass Sunstein)

Vulnerability and Proportionality:

7. Does this mechanic disproportionately affect vulnerable populations? Minors, individuals with impulse control difficulties, or those in financial stress require special consideration.
8. Is the reinforcement schedule proportionate? Are rewards frequent enough to be engaging but not so addictive as to create compulsion?
9. Does the mechanic respect cognitive limitations? Does it exploit known biases (hyperbolic discounting, gambling effect) or work with them toward beneficial ends?

Outcome and Accountability:

10. Who benefits, and how? Is the outcome genuinely win-win, or does one party gain disproportionately at another's expense?
11. Would we be comfortable with this mechanic being publicly documented? If the mechanic were featured in a news story about «how games manipulate players», would we feel defensive or confident?
12. Does the mechanic align with our company's stated values and ethical commitments?

This checklist is not intended as a rigid compliance tool but as a reflective framework for design practice. As Matsumura and colleagues envision, the ultimate goal of Shikakeology is to enable «anyone to create new shikakes» [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 428] — but this creative power must be exercised responsibly. The checklist provides guidance for responsible creativity.

Izushi and Aoyama's comparative analysis of the video game industry in Japan, the United States, and the United Kingdom offers an important insight for ethical design: the sociocultural context in which an industry develops shapes its understanding of

what constitutes acceptable practice. They argue that «the sociocultural cohesiveness between old and new industries further lowers the sectoral barrier for skill transfers» [Izushi, Aoyama, 2006, p. 1857]. Extending this insight, we might suggest that socio-cultural cohesiveness also shapes an industry's ethical sensibilities.

Japanese game companies developed in a context where manga and anime had already established strong traditions of character-driven storytelling and emotional engagement. These traditions carry implicit ethical commitments — to characters, to audiences, to the integrity of the narrative world. When Nintendo's Shigeru Miyamoto created *Donkey Kong* as «a game with a story — just as in cartoons or animated films» [Izushi, Aoyama, 2006, p. 1851], he was not merely borrowing techniques but inheriting a cultural framework that emphasized care for the player's experience.

This cultural embedding does not guarantee ethical outcomes — Japanese game companies have also faced criticism over addictive mechanics and exploitative monetization. However, it suggests that ethical design is not merely a matter of abstract principles but of culturally situated practice. The challenge for global game designers is to cultivate similar ethical sensibilities within their own cultural contexts, adapting the win-win principle to local norms and expectations.

Koizumi's documentation of Nintendo's historical quality-control philosophy is instructive here. By limiting the number of software titles each developer could release and maintaining strict quality standards, Nintendo created a system that prioritized sustainable quality over short-term quantity [Koizumi, 2016, pp. 25-26]. This institutionalized an ethic of care that shaped the entire Japanese console ecosystem. While the digital transition has eroded some of these controls, the underlying principle — that engagement should be built on quality and respect for players — remains relevant.

The synthesis of Shikakeology and behavioral economics opens the possibility for a practical tool that could systematically support ethical game design. We propose the development of the Shikake Atlas: a taxonomic knowledge base that would classify game mechanics by their underlying shikake triggers, behavioral-economic mechanisms, and associated engagement outcomes.

The need for such a tool emerges from three observations. First, game mechanics increasingly function as complex behavioral systems whose effects are not always transparent even to their designers. The battle pass analyzed above demonstrates how multiple triggers and biases interact synergistically; understanding these interactions requires systematic analysis that goes beyond intuition.

Second, while the Japanese video game industry has developed deep intuitive mastery of engagement design — drawing on cultural resources from manga and anime and institutionalized quality-control philosophies — this knowledge

remains largely tacit and embedded in specific organizational contexts. There is no common language for describing, comparing, and transferring engagement design patterns across studios, let alone across cultural boundaries.

Third, the growing ethical concern over dark patterns and gaming addiction creates urgent demand for design tools that can distinguish ethical engagement from exploitation. A systematic taxonomy could help developers, publishers, and regulators identify potential risks before mechanics are deployed at scale.

Matsumura and colleagues themselves envisioned such systematization. Their shikake trigger categories [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 426] and the accompanying trigger matrix [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 428] represent an initial effort to identify «rules of thumb» for designing new shikake. The Shikake Atlas would extend this vision from physical objects to digital games, creating a living knowledge base that captures and organizes engagement design patterns.

The Shikake Atlas is conceived as a multi-dimensional classification system that would allow designers to navigate the space of engagement mechanics along several orthogonal axes.

Drawing on Matsumura and colleagues' taxonomy [Matsumura et al., 2015, pp. 424-426], each mechanic would be classified by the physical and psychological triggers it employs:

- Physical triggers: feedback modalities employed (visual, auditory, haptic) and feedforward mechanisms (analogy, perceived affordance)
- Psychological triggers: individual triggers activated (challenge, positive expectation, reward, self-esteem) and social triggers engaged (social proof, social norm, being watched)

Cognitive Mechanism Profile. Each mechanic would be mapped to the cognitive biases and heuristics it primarily engages:

- Intertemporal choice mechanisms: hyperbolic discounting, present bias, future reward valuation
- Reference-dependent mechanisms: loss aversion, endowment effect, social comparison
- Probability assessment mechanisms: gambling effect, near-miss effect, probability neglect
- Mental accounting mechanisms: payment isolation, sunk cost fallacy, transaction utility

Engagement Outcome Profile. Mechanics would be characterized by their typical engagement signatures:

- Retention patterns: daily active users (DAU), monthly active users (MAU), session length, return frequency
 - Monetization patterns: average revenue per paying user (ARPPU), purchase frequency, spending distribution
-

- Social engagement patterns: community formation, user-generated content, social sharing

Ethical Risk Profile. Each mechanic would be assessed for potential ethical concerns:

- Vulnerable population impact: differential effects on minors, impulse-vulnerable individuals

- Transparency level: ease of understanding mechanics and consequences

- Exit friction: difficulty of discontinuing or opting out

- Exploitation potential: likelihood of mechanism being used as dark pattern

The Shikake Atlas is intended to serve multiple constituencies within the game development ecosystem.

For Game Designers. The Atlas would function as a design pattern library — a resource for inspiration and systematic thinking about engagement mechanics. Designers facing specific challenges could explore mechanics that have successfully addressed similar challenges, understanding both their trigger configurations and their ethical profiles.

For Publishers and Platform Holders. The Atlas could inform design review processes, providing a common vocabulary for discussing engagement mechanics and their potential effects. Publishers seeking to implement platform-wide policies on ethical design could reference Atlas classifications to identify high-risk mechanics requiring additional scrutiny.

For Researchers. The Atlas would serve as a shared research infrastructure, enabling systematic comparative studies of engagement mechanics across cultures, platforms, and time periods. Researchers could test hypotheses about which trigger combinations produce sustainable engagement versus problematic addiction patterns.

For Regulators and Educators. The Atlas could inform policy development and public understanding of gaming engagement mechanics. By making the structure of these mechanics more transparent, it could support evidence-based regulation and media literacy education.

The Shikake Atlas is currently in conceptual development as part of a broader research program bridging Shikakeology, behavioral economics, and game studies. The immediate research agenda includes: taxonomy refinement, case compilation, framework validation.

As Izushi and Aoyama emphasize, the formation of new industries and practices often depends on «cross-sectoral fusion of creative talent» [Izushi, Aoyama, 2006, p. 1857]. The Shikake Atlas project invites such fusion — bringing together insights from Japanese shikake research, behavioral economics, game design practice, and ethical analysis.

The Shikake Atlas represents the translation of theoretical synthesis into a practical resource. It aims to make the wisdom embedded in successful engagement

design more accessible, more systematic, and more ethically informed. The win-win principle is embedded in its architecture, ensuring that designers considering a pattern are prompted to reflect on potential harms and vulnerabilities.

This paper has proposed a theoretical synthesis of Shikakeology and behavioral economics as a framework for understanding and designing ethical engagement in video games. Several conclusions emerge from this synthesis.

First, video game mechanics can be systematically understood as complex digital shikake. The taxonomy of physical and psychological triggers developed by Matsumura and colleagues maps directly onto game design elements: auditory and visual feedback, analogies and perceived affordances, challenge and reward structures, social proof and social norms. What distinguishes games from other media is the density and interactivity of these triggers — players do not merely observe but actively participate in the behavioral loops they create.

Second, behavioral economics provides the explanatory mechanisms that Shikakeology alone cannot supply. Concepts such as hyperbolic discounting, payment isolation, reference dependence, and the gambling effect explain why shikake triggers work — why a daily login bonus feels compelling, why a near-miss in a loot box intensifies desire, why a leaderboard position motivates continued play. This explanatory layer transforms Shikakeology from a descriptive taxonomy into a predictive and design-relevant framework.

Third, the ethical distinction between shikake and dark patterns hinges on the win-win principle. When mechanics solve genuine problems for users or communities — encouraging physical activity, fostering social connection, enabling creative expression — they function as shikake. When they exploit cognitive vulnerabilities for corporate gain — manipulating minors through payment isolation, engineering compulsion through variable ratio schedules — they become dark patterns. The difference lies not in the mechanics themselves but in intent, transparency, and outcome distribution.

Fourth, the proposed Shikake Atlas offers a pathway from theory to practice. By classifying game mechanics along multiple dimensions — behavioral triggers, cognitive mechanisms, engagement outcomes, ethical risks — the Atlas would provide designers with a systematic resource for ethical engagement design. It would also serve researchers, publishers, and regulators seeking common vocabulary and empirical grounding for discussions of game design ethics.

The Japanese video game industry's historical success in creating engaging experiences offers valuable lessons. Drawing on cultural resources from manga and anime and institutionalizing quality-control philosophies, Japanese developers cultivated intuitive mastery of behavioral design. The synthesis proposed here aims to make that mastery more systematic, more transferable, and more ethically informed — not by copying specific mechanics, but by understanding the underlying principles that make them work.

Several directions for future research remain open. Empirical validation of the proposed framework through controlled studies of player behavior would test its predictive power. Cross-cultural comparisons could reveal how cultural context moderates the effectiveness and ethical implications of specific shikake configurations. Development of the Shikake Atlas as an open knowledge commons would invite collaborative refinement and real-world testing. Most importantly, ongoing dialogue between researchers, designers, and players is needed to ensure that engagement design serves human flourishing rather than undermining it.

As Matsumura and colleagues envision, the ultimate goal of Shikakeology is to enable «anyone to create new shikakes» [Matsumura et al., 2015, p. 428]. The framework developed here suggests that this creative power must be paired with ethical responsibility. When grounded in genuine understanding of human psychology and genuine commitment to user well-being, shikake-informed game design can create experiences that are not only engaging but truly worth engaging with.

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**PATTERNS OF DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONAL INDUSTRIAL
COMPLEXES IN THE CONTEXT OF THE EVOLUTION
OF TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE**

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***Abstract.** This article examines the patterns of development of regional industrial complexes in the context of the evolution of transport infrastructure. The author identifies patterns that arise between the level of industrial development and the development of transport infrastructure as it transforms and evolves into a new organizational form — «communications and integration platforms».*

***Keywords:** patterns, industry, transport, transformation, communications and integration platforms.*

The sanction policy towards the Russian Federation and the adopted counter-measures, which modify historically established routes and supply chains, significantly alter the requirements for domestic transport infrastructure, opening new opportunities for its development. In these conditions, it becomes especially important to clarify stable, objectively existing interrelations formed within the system of interaction between the level of industrial development and the state of transport infrastructure [3].

Such development patterns can be viewed as a system of stable factors and stages that determine the state of an object, its formation process, and transformation, whereby the emergence of a particular factor inevitably leads to a predetermined outcome [2].

Based on the analysis of scientific publications [1], [4], we highlight the following key aspects of the regular development of industry related to the development of transport infrastructure:

— pattern of accessibility: if transport infrastructure ensures a high level of territorial accessibility (corridors, nodes, hubs), the intensity of industrial production inevitably increases, and the market for regional enterprises expands;

— pattern of investment dependence: if the transport system is modernized and acquires new technological capabilities, the investment attractiveness of the region inevitably increases, leading to growth in capital investments in the industrial sector;

— pattern of spatial integration: if the transport infrastructure connects industrial complexes into a unified network, a spatial continuum inevitably forms, ensuring coordination of production and distribution processes;

— pattern of innovative transformation: if the transport system implements digital and automated technologies (monitoring, flow management, intelligent platforms), then the transition of industry to innovative development models inevitably accelerates;

— pattern of socio-economic effect: if the transport infrastructure ensures sustainable movement of resources and information, then the levels of employment, income, and quality of life inevitably increase, which, in turn, stimulates the industrial development of the region.

In the systemic transformation of these patterns, a crucial role is attributed to the evolution of transport infrastructure, which manifests in the systemic transformation of its functions — from traditionally ensuring the physical movement of goods and passengers to fulfilling the role of a comprehensive economic mechanism that creates conditions for synergy in economic development, accelerates investment flows, establishes new production linkages, and improves the economic efficiency of regional industrial complexes by forming communication-integration platforms. These platforms represent a fundamentally new form of infrastructural development processes that ensure coordination and stability of resource movement within the spatial continuum of the regional economy.

Regarding “communication-integration platforms” as a new form of infrastructural development of the transport system, according to [6], [7], they are defined as multifunctional organizational and economic systems that ensure sustainable interaction between regional industrial complexes and transport infrastructure based on an established system of centers for resource exchange, information, and service provision.

Their key characteristic is that they transcend narrowly transport-related functions and form the economic foundation of spatial integration, enabling coordination of production, information, and distribution processes among industrial enterprises and sectors, thereby ensuring sustainable intra-regional and interregional communication.

The theoretical basis for the formation of the platform is the theory of large transport systems, and for the emerging transport infrastructure management platform to be in demand and effective, it is necessary to consider the features and development trends of transport, as a large-scale production-technical, information, economic, and social system [5].

In other words, these are not merely “logistic carriers” between systems (as classical IT integration platforms are), but **economic-communication nodes** that link

transport corridors with industrial clusters; ensure comprehensive service and rapid movement of resource and information flows; create conditions for the emergence of new development patterns of regional industrial complexes. Among these patterns, we can identify:

- the pattern of digital transformation, which consists in the fact that if transport infrastructure is transferred to digital platforms for flow management, the speed and transparency of production and investment processes inevitably increase;
- pattern of network connectivity, the essence of which lies in the fact that if stable transport corridors and nodes are established, the integration of industrial complexes into a unified regional and interregional system inevitably strengthens;
- pattern of spatial concentration — if transport hubs become centers of economic activity, the concentration of production capacities and growth of industrial clusters around them inevitably occur.
- the pattern of investment acceleration, which implies that if transport infrastructure attains a new quality (speed, connectivity, digitalization), then the inflow of investments and capitalization of regional industrial complexes inevitably accelerate;
- the pattern of service integration, meaning that if the transport system expands the range of service functions (maintenance, information, and communication services), then a new model of interaction between industry and transport infrastructure inevitably forms, ensuring increased economic efficiency.

In general, the above development patterns of regional industrial complexes in the context of the evolution of transport infrastructure are objective in nature and, combined with the traditional development patterns of the transport system, form a unified integrative continuum of spatial-economic development. This continuum constitutes a system of interconnected factors, where transport infrastructure serves not only as a means of physical movement but also as an institutional-economic mechanism that ensures sustainable synergy between industrial and regional growth.

Traditional regularities of the transport system are manifested in the dependence of transport intensity on the level of urbanization, in the correlation between the development of transport corridors and the structure of production linkages, as well as in the direct relationship between the accessibility of transport hubs and the investment attractiveness of a territory. These regularities are stable and confirmed by long-term observations: when a region gains access to new transport arteries, its economic activity inevitably increases, and a new employment structure is formed.

In turn, the new development patterns emerging in the context of the formation of communication-integrative platforms reinforce and complement the traditional ones, thus the development patterns of industrial complexes and the transport system form a system of mutual synergy, where the transport infrastructure ceases to be merely a servicing sphere and becomes a factor of economic development, with each new stage of its evolution generating corresponding changes in the structure of the regional economy.

This system of patterns can be represented as a multi-level model, where at the first level traditional dependencies are identified (accessibility → growth of transport → production expansion); at the second level new patterns emerge (digitalization → acceleration of investments → cluster formation); at the third level synergy arises, manifested in a stable spatial continuum where industry and transport operate as a unified economic system.

Consequently, the concept emerges that the development of regional industrial complexes cannot be considered independently of the evolution of transport infrastructure. If the transport system transforms into a communication-integration platform, a new form of spatial economic organization inevitably arises, ensuring the coordination of production, investment, and distribution processes.

Thus, this coordination constitutes the key regularity according to which when transport infrastructure acquires the characteristics of a communication-integration platform, a sustainable economic continuum inevitably forms, where resource flows develop synchronously with regional industrial growth, and transport infrastructure transforms into a mechanism for sustainable economic development through the creation of a system of service-distribution hubs that meet the diverse needs of economic development.

Given that this approach is relatively new and relevant, further research is planned to focus on addressing the issue concerning the organizational and economic structure of communication-integration platforms as a new form of infrastructural development of the transport system.

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IMPROVING PPP MODELS OF BRICS MEMBER COUNTRIES

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Abstract. *The purpose of this work is to provide a comprehensive analysis of public-private partnerships (PPPs) in the BRICS economies, with an emphasis on identifying common trends, specific problems and development prospects and rights. The scientific novelty of the work consists in an inter-regional comparison of the PPP experience, which makes it possible to identify universal and specific factors of success and failure, as well as to propose innovative approaches to solving emerging problems. The article analyzes the macroeconomic indicators of the BRICS countries for 2020-2024 in the context of the implementation of PPP projects, examines the main PPP models of the BRICS countries, considers the main directions for improving PPP models in modern conditions.*

Keywords: *BRICS countries, public private partnership, economy, digitalization, right.*

Amid global changes, countries are increasingly recognizing the necessity of deepening economic and political partnerships. The BRICS grouping is becoming a key mechanism that unites efforts to stimulate economic development and strengthen international peace.

The strengths of this alliance are reinforced through the exchange of knowledge in innovative approaches, contributions to technological projects, and investment engagement, all of which contribute to the growth of their economic power and the strengthening of relationships within the alliance framework.

Table 1 below presents the macroeconomic indicators of the BRICS countries for 2020-2023.

The main objective of the BRICS countries' association is the joint pursuit of accelerating economic development and enhancing their influence on the international stage through cooperation and mutual assistance among members.

Table 1. Macroeconomic indicators of BRICS countries for 2020-2022¹.

BRICS country	GDP of BRICS countries, trillion USD			Exports of BRICS countries, billion USD			Imports of BRICS countries, billion USD		
	2020	2021	2022	2020	2021	2022	2020	2021	2022
Brazil	1,75	1,83	1,9	209,2	313,9	334	166,3	284,9	273
Russia	1,49	1,84	2,34	337,1	550,4	591,5	231,6	379,8	259,1
India	2,5	2,7	3,0	275,5	636,0	773	367,9	768,8	453
China	14,6	15,8	16,3	2589,1	3756,0	3590	2069,6	3129,9	2710
South Africa	337	353	360	85,2	132,6	124	68,9	127,5	112

BRICS countries actively attract foreign investment and develop foreign trade. They create favorable conditions for foreign investors and cultivate trade relations with other countries, thereby contributing to economic growth. BRICS countries actively invest in research activities, innovation, and technological development. This enables them to develop new products and services, enhance production processes, and improve economic efficiency. To ensure economic competition, protect the rights of participants in procurement procedures, and prevent monopolistic practices, Federal Law No. 135-FZ dated 26.07.2006 'On Protection of Competition' is also in effect, and its provisions are further specified and supplemented by the norms of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation, as well as a set of regional acts regulating the specific procedures locally. Particular attention is paid to analyzing the effectiveness of partnership projects and monitoring the implementation of agreements: to this end, a procedure for assessing the comparative advantages of projects was developed and implemented (Resolution of the Government of the Russian Federation No. 1514 dated 30.12.2015), along with a control mechanism exercised by the public partner to oversee compliance with obligations (Resolution of the Government of the Russian Federation No. 1490 dated the same day).

According to the strategy developed by the Russian Ministry of Economic Development, the synergy between the private and public sectors lies at the core of interactions among BRICS countries. This involves the creation of joint ventures to carry out large-scale, technically complex initiatives, including the construction of infrastructure facilities, which require significant financial investments².

¹ Kovaleva E. I., Rastopchina Yu. L., Bozhkov Yu. N. Assessment of Export-Import Activities of BRICS and Its Prospective Directions // Journal of Applied Research.— 2023.— No. 3.— Pp. 87-93.

² BRICS Economic Partnership Strategy until 2025 [Electronic resource].— Access mode: <https://www.economy.gov.ru/material/file/636aa3edbc0dcc2356ebb6f8d594ccb0/>

PPP plays a vital role in the economies of BRICS countries, facilitating the attraction of investment, technology, and expertise from private companies for the implementation of various projects. This contributes to economic growth, infrastructure development, agriculture, energy, and social sectors, which, in turn, improves the quality of life of the population and creates new opportunities for the development of BRICS countries¹.

Depending on the favorability of conditions for PPP, each BRICS state has its own objectives and motivations that promote the development of this partnership².

The level of PPP development in BRICS countries can be evaluated by the ranking of BRICS countries by investments in PPP projects, compiled by the PPP Center (Fig. 1):

Figure 1. Ranking of BRICS countries by investment in PPP projects³

Currently, BRICS countries have coordinating centers that concentrate key functions driving the PPP market. The state also plays a significant role by centralizing the function of PPP development, including project selection.

¹ Features of PPP Projects in BRICS Countries: Studying Economic Integration and Energy Efficiency // ScientificArticles.Ru — Portal for Students and Graduate Students. — 2023. — [Electronic resource]. — Access mode: <https://nauchniestati.ru/spravka/osobennosti-proektov-gchp-v-stranah-briks/>

² Semenov A. V. Institutional and Organizational Alliance between the State and Business: Implementation of Socially Significant Projects in BRICS Countries // Economics and Management: Scientific and Practical Journal. — 2022. — No. 5(167). — Pp. 8-14

³ PPP Center Analytics [Electronic resource]. — Access mode: <https://pppcenter.ru/analitika/>

Since 2014, the Development Bank with a capital of \$ 100 billion, established by the BRICS countries to invest in infrastructure projects, has been operational.

In each BRICS country, a distinct practice of PPP has developed.

At the same time, the concession model has proven to be the most effective type of PPP in these countries. In particular, in China and India, the BOT model has become widespread, which assumes that the concessionaire not only constructs but also operates the facility until the investment is recouped, after which it is transferred to the state. According to this model, the rights to operate the facility are granted to the concessionaire, although the facility itself remains state property. Upon expiration of the concession term, the usage rights cease, and the facility is fully returned to the state. This scheme has established itself as an effective mechanism for investment recovery and is commonly employed in the implementation of infrastructure projects. In recent years, this model has been actively utilized in both Brazil and South Africa.

China occupies the most proactive position in the development of PPP mechanisms. Thus, the country's PPP market comprises 10,243 projects totaling over \$2.5 trillion. To facilitate the management of PPP projects and ensure transparency in the sector, the National Integrated PPP Information Platform has been launched in China. Use of the platform is mandatory during the preparation and implementation of PPP projects. Project data is submitted by the municipal or district subdivision, reviewed by the provincial center, and verified by the China PPP Center¹.

When the state attracts investment from the private sector and collaborates with it by sharing risks, this often leads to an increase in potential budgetary liabilities that may arise from certain events, even while reducing its explicit financial obligations.

Russia lacks an effective system that regularly assesses potential obligations, including those arising within the framework of public-private partnership. Nevertheless, there is intensive development underway for such a system. In the context of minimizing risks associated with contingent liabilities in public-private partnership projects, the practical experience of BRICS countries can offer valuable lessons for enhancing relations and interactions within PPPs in Russia.

In risk management strategies, especially regarding the fulfillment of contingent liabilities, BRICS countries employ various methods. An example of an advanced approach in this field is the practice in South Africa, where budget planning includes a special line item for financing contingent liabilities, known as reserves

¹ The BRICS countries were presented with the capabilities of the Rosinfra platform for preparing PPP projects [Electronic resource].— Access mode: <https://pppcenter.ru/press-tsentr/novosti/stranam-briks-predstavili-vozmozhnosti-platformy-rosinfra-dlya-podgotovki-gchp-proektov/>

for unforeseen circumstances. Specific frameworks for contingent liabilities have been established in Brazil, China, and India. For example, in Brazil, the maximum amount of payments from the central budget should not exceed 1 % of revenues, while at the regional level this threshold is increased to 5 %. For PPP in India, the following rule is established: during the subsequent five years, annual grant payments cannot exceed one quarter of the funds allocated for these purposes in the current Five-Year Plan.

Table 2. Profitability Ratios of PPP Projects in BRICS Countries¹

Country	Project	Investment (billion rubles)	Profit (billion rubles)	Profitability Ratio (%)
Brazil	São Paulo–Rio de Janeiro Expressway	87,96	13,2	15
Russia	Central Ring Road	175,92	21,11	12
India	Solar power plants	43,98	7,92	18
China	Metro in Shanghai	263,88	52,78	20
South Africa	Water treatment facilities in Cape Town	35,18	3,52	10
Egypt	Suez Canal	87,96	13,2	15
Iran	Development of port infrastructure	131,94	19,79	15
Ethiopia	Hydroelectric power station on the Omo River	52,78	5,28	10
UAE	Metro in Dubai	263,88	39,58	15
Saudi Arabia	Solar and wind power plants	219,9	32,98	15

Compiled by the author using materials: Semenov, A. V. Design of socio-economic mechanisms of public-private partnership in BRICS+ countries / A. V. Semenov // Economic Theory: Searching for Alternatives for Development: Collection of Scientific Articles.— Yekaterinburg: Institute of Economics of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2024.— Pp. 274-287.— DOI 10.17059/easet/2024/22.— EDN DBIVDG.

¹ Semenov, A. V. Design of socio-economic mechanisms of public-private partnership in BRICS+ countries / A. V. Semenov // Economic Theory: Searching for Alternatives for Development: Collection of Scientific Articles.— Yekaterinburg: Institute of Economics of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2024.— Pp. 274-287.— DOI 10.17059/easet/2024/22.— EDN DBIVDG.

All these rules allow for limiting the volume of budget expenditures for fulfilling conditional agreements and effectively managing the associated risks. Considering all the positive practices of the BRICS countries, it is possible to develop and implement the most effective PPP business model in practice, taking into account all risks and contemporary challenges.

In August 2024, Amendments were made to Federal Law No. 224-FZ regarding the regulation of the industrial PPP sector. The document describes the criteria and procedures for project selection, financial participation of the public party, specifics of termination, and other important aspects of agreement implementation.

The digitalization of PPP projects is transforming the economy and industry by enhancing management efficiency and reducing costs through process optimization. Digitalization is used for analysis, modeling, and forecasting, improving the understanding of processes and decision-making. In the service sector, digitalization fosters personalization and innovation, making the economy more competitive and future-oriented¹.

From a legal perspective, regulation of the public procurement sphere is based on a number of key federal regulatory acts. Central to this is the Federal Law dated 05.04.2013 No. 44-FZ, which comprehensively regulates the entire contract system in the public and municipal sectors, establishing transparent conditions for the procurement of goods, works, and services. Equally significant from the standpoint of procurement conducted by certain categories of legal entities is the Federal Law dated 18.07.2011 No. 223-FZ, which additionally establishes a special regime for enterprises with state participation and natural monopolies. The primary procedures and types of liability are also comprehensively stipulated in several other legislative acts: Federal Law No. 224-FZ, adopted in 2015, governs the creation and implementation of projects within the framework of public-private and municipal-private partnerships, while Federal Law No. 115-FZ dated 21.07.2005 establishes the mechanism for constructing legal relations under concession agreements.

It is necessary to organize and develop the institution of sponsorship support within the legislation of the Russian Federation. This will provide sponsors with the opportunity to independently allocate additional funding to the project. To conduct judicial oversight over corporate financing mechanisms. An instrument is required during project implementation to avoid resorting to independent guarantees and surety. Amendments adopted in 2024 introduce restrictions on expenditures by Russian Federation subjects and municipalities for PPP projects. The spending

¹ Strategies for the sustainable development of the PPP-based economic system / A. Babkin, A. Semenov, I. Babkin [et al.] // BIO Web of Conferences.— 2024.— Vol. 130.— P. 08024.— DOI 10.1051/bioconf/202413008024.— EDN CGPZQO.

limit is now set at 10% of annual budget revenues, and the total volume of obligations cannot exceed 100% (or 50% for subsidized regions) of the annual revenue. This may significantly restrict the number of implemented projects, especially social projects that require government support.

The amendments adopted on 18.02.2025 introduce clarifications to the law on concession agreements, mainly concerning projects related to heat supply, water supply, and wastewater disposal. A significant change is the direct prohibition of the participation of unitary enterprises and budgetary institutions as concessionaires. For its successful implementation, it is necessary to continue enhancing institutional and legal conditions, developing the competencies and experience of participants, and actively utilizing international experience and innovative approaches¹.

On the international level, Russia continues to maintain stable positions among the leaders in terms of both the volume and growth rates of the PPP project market. According to the World Bank, by the end of 2023, Russia ranked 7th globally in the number of concession initiatives launched, ahead of many countries in Europe and Central Asia. At the same time, the degree of private sector involvement in the implementation of infrastructure projects remains consistently high: in 2024, more than 30% of all PPPs were realized with the participation of development institutions (VEB.RF) and major non-governmental investors, indicating the attractiveness of PPP mechanisms to private businesses as well.

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THE IMPACT OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC FACTORS ON THE LIFE CYCLE OF A CONSTRUCTION COMPANY

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Abstract. *The purpose of this article is to identify and theoretically and methodologically substantiate the influence of key socio-economic factors on the parameters and patterns of the life cycle of a construction company. The scientific novelty of this study lies in the transition from the traditional analysis of the life cycle of an individual organization to the consideration of the life cycle of a construction company in the context of sectoral and macroeconomic dynamics. The author substantiated the proposition that the development stages of a construction company are synchronized with the phases of the economic cycle, and that the life cycle of the company is a derivative of the socio-economic trajectory of the national economy's development. As a result, a strong positive correlation was established between economic growth indicators and construction activity parameters: correlation coefficients between GDP and industry indicators range from 0.937 to 0.979 with high statistical significance. A negative correlation has been identified between the GDP deflator and the physical volumes of construction. The dynamic analysis of building commissioning over the period from 2000 to 2024 confirmed the synchronization of construction development phases with macroeconomic cycles: periods of economic growth are accompanied by an expansion of construction activity, whereas crisis phases and stagnation lead to its reduction. The practical significance of the study lies in the fact that the analysis of the life cycle allows correlating the stages of enterprise development with the phases of the economic cycle, identifying characteristic risks and constraints at each stage, and developing adequate managerial decisions that ensure sustainability and long-term operational efficiency.*

Keywords: *organizational life cycle, construction industry, macroeconomic factors, economic cycle, investments in construction, GDP.*

Introduction

The construction industry is traditionally considered in economic theory and practice as one of the system-forming sectors of the national economy, as it simultaneously performs the functions of infrastructure provision, investment multiplication, and social stabilization. It is precisely through construction that the material embodiment of investment decisions occurs, the formation of production and social infrastructure takes place, as well as the renewal of fixed capital in the majority of industries [8]. In this regard, the dynamics of the construction complex act not only as a consequence of general economic processes but also as an independent factor of economic growth.

The significance of the construction industry is confirmed by its macroeconomic parameters. According to available estimates, construction accounts for approximately 8.6% of Russia's gross domestic product and provides employment for about 11.2% of the economically active population. Between 2020 and 2024, the average cost of constructing one square meter increased by approximately 45%, from 68 to 98 thousand rubles [1], which ensured growth in total revenue despite fluctuations in the physical volumes of commissioning.

Thus, the Construction industry serves not only as an indicator of the phases of the economic cycle but also as a driver of economic development. On the one hand, the industry responds to fluctuations in investment activity, interest rates, and household incomes, which determines the pronounced cyclicity of its development. On the other hand, it is through construction projects that new production capacities, transport corridors, housing stock, and social infrastructure are created [5], establishing long-term prerequisites for economic growth.

The objective of this study is to identify and theoretically substantiate the influence of key socio-economic factors on the parameters and patterns of the construction company life cycle.

The hypothesis of this study is that the construction company life cycle is determined by socio-economic factors within the macroenvironment, primarily the dynamics of economic growth and inflationary processes, and that the development stages of construction companies are synchronized with the phases of the macroeconomic cycle.

Literature Review

In economic theory, the organizational life cycle is regarded as an objective trajectory of development, shaped by the interaction between internal managerial mechanisms and external market environment factors [2]. In classical life cycle models, each organization passes through a series of sequential stages — from inception and growth to maturity and potential decline, with each stage characterized by a specific management structure, type of organizational problems, and a set of strategic decisions [3].

The origins of this concept trace back to the works of K. Boulding, who as early as the mid-20th century proposed the idea of cyclicity in organizational development, comparing the evolution of organizations to biological systems. In subsequent decades, the theory was significantly developed. G. Lippitt emphasized critical managerial situations that determine transitions between stages, shifting the focus from quantitative growth parameters to qualitative changes within the organization. L. Greiner proposed a model in which a firm's development occurs through an alternation of evolutionary phases and revolutionary crises caused by the accumulation of internal contradictions [11]. In the 1980s-2000s, the concept received systematic development in the works of I. Adizes, who regarded the life cycle as the result of the dynamic interaction between managerial functions and the external environment, and crises as a natural mechanism of organizational evolution [4].

Thus, in the classical scientific tradition, the life cycle was predominantly interpreted as a development model of an individual organization, where the key factors were managerial decisions, structure, culture, and the scale of the firm's activities. However, since the 2000s, a methodological shift has occurred in the scientific discourse. Researchers, among whom can be noted I. Horta, A. Camanho, J. Johnes, and G. Johnes [10], as well as J. Markard [12] have demonstrated that the development of a company cannot be considered separately from the industry environment, as technological paradigms, institutional constraints, and market structure form the framework within which the evolution of specific firms takes place.

As a result, the concept of the life cycle began to be applied not only to individual organizations but also to entire industries. The life cycle of a company, in contemporary scientific discourse, is interpreted as a derivative of industry dynamics: the growth, maturity, or decline stages of a firm are determined not only by its internal managerial characteristics but also by the phase of development of the industry itself, the level of technological change, and the state of the competitive environment [9].

Materials and methods

The methodological foundation of the study is correlation analysis. Formula (1) is used to calculate Pearson's correlation coefficient:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x}) * \sum(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 * \sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (1)$$

Where — the mathematical expectation of the series x; and — the mathematical expectation of the series y. The interpretation of the correlation coefficient value is as follows: if the coefficient lies within the interval from 0.9 to 1, the relationship is considered very strong; from 0.7 to 0.9 — strong; from 0.5 to 0.7 — moderate; from 0.3 to 0.5 — weak. The calculation of the correlation coefficient allows not only the identification of a statistical relationship but also the determination of

the nature of socio-economic parameters' involvement in the formation of the life cycle stages of a construction company.

The empirical foundation of the study comprises official statistical data from the Federal State Statistics Service of the Russian Federation for the period from 2000 to 2024 [6]. The study employs the following indicators: the number of buildings commissioned (thousand units), the total area of commissioned buildings (million m²), the volume of investments in fixed capital in construction (billion rubles), gross domestic product per capita (rubles), gross domestic product (billion rubles), and the GDP deflator (%).

The results of the correlation analysis are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Results of the Correlation Analysis

R	Number of commissioned buildings, thousand	Total area of buildings, million m ²	Investments in fixed capital (construction), billion rubles	GDP per capita, rub.	GDP, billion rub.	GDP deflator, %
Number of commissioned buildings, thousand	1					
<i>p-value (2-tailed)*</i>						
Total area of buildings, million m ²	0,94617	1				
<i>p-value (2-tailed)</i>	0,000					
Investments in fixed capital (construction), billion rubles	0,95895	0,86089	1			
<i>p-value (2-tailed)</i>	0,000	0,000				
GDP per capita, rub.	0,97947	0,93743	0,973	1		
<i>p-value (2-tailed)</i>	0,000	0,000	0,000			
GDP, billion rub.	0,9786	0,93787	0,972	0,99991	1	
<i>p-value (2-tailed)</i>	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000		
GDP deflator, %	-0,4195	-0,57808	-0,30213	-0,40989	-0,41023	1
<i>p-value (2-tailed)</i>	0,037	0,002	0,142	0,042	0,042	

* **p-value (2-tailed)** represents the level of statistical significance of the obtained correlation coefficient in a two-tailed hypothesis test.

Source: author's calculations

Results and Discussion

The analysis shows a strong positive correlation between economic growth indicators and construction activity parameters. The correlation coefficient between GDP per capita and the number of commissioned buildings is 0.979, with the total building floor area — 0.937, and with investments in fixed capital in construction — 0.973. Similar values were obtained for the aggregate GDP indicator: 0.979, 0.938, and 0.972, respectively. All indicated dependencies are statistically significant at the $p = 0.000$ level, allowing for the conclusion of high reliability of the obtained results.

The above correlation values indicate an almost linear relationship between macroeconomic growth and the scale of construction activity. As the aggregate economy expands and population incomes increase, investment activity intensifies, driving demand for residential and commercial real estate, which directly impacts the number of commissioned facilities, their total area, and the volume of capital investments in construction. In other words, the construction sector acts as a sensitive indicator of overall economic development and responds to changes in the macroeconomic environment almost synchronously with GDP dynamics.

Fig. 1.— Commissioning of residential and non-residential buildings in the Russian Federation

Source: compiled by the author based on data from [6]

The effect of the price factor, reflected in the GDP deflator, is of an opposite nature. A moderate negative correlation is observed between the deflator and the number of buildings commissioned (-0.419 ; $p = 0.037$), while a stronger negative relationship is evident between the deflator and the total building area (-0.578 ; $p = 0.002$). The acceleration of inflationary processes and the increase in the overall price level are

accompanied by a reduction in the physical volume of construction. The relationship between the GDP deflator and investments in fixed capital in construction is also negative (-0.302); however, it is statistically insignificant ($p = 0.142$).

The obtained results allow us to conclude the high dependence of the construction sector on macroeconomic dynamics.

The dynamics of building commissioning indicators presented in Figure 1 generally confirm the conclusions regarding the close interrelation between construction activity and the phases of macroeconomic development.

The period from 2000 to 2007 is characterized by a sustained economic upturn driven by rising raw material prices, increased budget revenues, and expanding domestic demand. During this period, there is a consistent increase both in the number of commissioned buildings and in their total area. The number of introduced objects increased from 119.7 to 209.9 thousand, while the total area grew from 44.7 to 98.1 million m². The observed dynamics correspond to a phase of intensive economic growth and reflect the stage of accelerated development of construction companies, during which the expansion of investments and solvent demand stimulates active growth in construction volumes.

The period from 2008 to 2010 exhibits the consequences of the global financial and economic crisis. Although the number of commissioned buildings increased in 2009, the total area began to decrease, indicating a reduction in the scale of construction projects and a deterioration in investment conditions. The described period corresponds to the phase of economic downturn [7] and reflects the transition of construction companies from the growth stages to the stagnation stage.

Restorative growth of the economy and the construction sector is observed during the period from 2011 to 2014. It can be seen that the number of commissioned buildings increased from 227.2 to 304.2 thousand, while the total area increased from 99.0 to 138.6 million m² during the period from 2011 to 2014. can be interpreted as a phase of economic revival and a new upturn [7], accompanied by an expansion of investment activity and an increase in construction volumes.

Between 2015 and 2018, a slowdown in economic dynamics was observed amid external economic constraints and macroeconomic instability. After reaching peak values, both the number of commissioned buildings and the total area began to decline. The phase of economic stagnation reflects the stage of maturity or partial decline in the life cycle of construction companies. The period from 2019 to 2024 is marked by a new wave of growth in construction activity, despite external shocks, including the pandemic and changes in external economic conditions. The number of completed buildings rises from 305.5 thousand in 2019 to 496.7 thousand in 2024, while the total area increases from 146.7 to 170.8 million m². A particularly marked acceleration is observed after 2020, linked to state support measures for the construction industry, preferential mortgage lending, and

the intensification of residential construction [8] This stage can be characterized as a phase of economic upturn, corresponding to the growth stages and expansion of construction companies.

Thus, the dynamics of building commissioning throughout the entire period under consideration are characterized by pronounced cyclicity, synchronized with macroeconomic fluctuations. Periods of economic upturn are accompanied by accelerated growth in the number of projects and their total area, whereas crisis phases and stagnation are reflected in a reduction or slowdown of construction activity.

Conclusion

The analysis demonstrated that the construction company life cycle is shaped by macroeconomic factors that define the scale and nature of the construction sector's operation in Russia. The dynamics of economic growth and inflationary processes act as determinants framing the transition of construction companies between the stages of upturn, stabilization, and downturn. Correlation analysis confirmed that the strongest relationship exists between construction activity indicators and such measures as GDP and GDP per capita, which reflect the overall level of economic development and effective demand. These macroeconomic indicators determine the opportunities for expanding investment programs and initiating new projects, thereby reinforcing growth trends within the industry. Inflation and price factors exert a restraining effect by increasing construction costs and complicating project implementation; however, their impact is less significant compared to the dynamics of overall economic activity.

The research hypothesis received empirical confirmation. The obtained results demonstrate that the construction company life cycle is a derivative of the trajectory of the country's socio-economic development: macroeconomic trends determine not only the volume of demand and resource availability but also the strategic capabilities of companies, their financial stability, and their ability to adapt to the phases of the economic cycle.

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